

TRINITY ANGLICAN SEMINARY

JEW AND GREEK:
PAUL'S INTRA-ISRAELITE DEBATE IN ROMANS

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PREFACE

My journey to Trinity Anglican Seminary began seven years ago, before any thought of even attending seminary had entered my mind. On a fall day in 2018, I committed to memorizing the book of Romans. I had been studying Romans in depth for several years, and I arrived at a point in my research that memorizing Paul's greatest letter was the unavoidable next step. That decision changed the course of my life. After memorizing Romans, I began performing the letter for a couple local churches. The process of performing Romans for an audience dramatically changed the way I understood the letter as a whole; but this new understanding seemed at odds with some of the scholarship I was reading. At the same time, I became aware of the Lord's call upon my life in this very specific area of performing Romans for fellow believers. If I were to heed this call, I realized that through my performances, I was interpreting the letter for audiences, and that interpretation included the new insights I was seeing. I knew that I needed to resolve the tension between the way I now understood Romans and what I was reading in scholarship. So, in the summer of 2020, I enrolled in Trinity. This thesis is the culmination of the last five years of work, and I am excited about how the Lord has guided me throughout and prepared me for the future ahead. That future is not clear, and I continue to follow the Lord's leading as one who walks through the woods at night along unfamiliar but well-trodden paths with only a flashlight to illumine each step before me. May he grant me the wisdom to always look to the Lord Jesus Christ whatever the future brings.

The last five years have been a blessing in many ways – spiritually, intellectually, communally, through joys and trials, mourning and celebration. I have been greatly supported by the faculty and staff of Trinity, as well as by family and friends. I would like to specifically thank a number of individuals. Thank you to Rev. Dr. Jacob Rodriguez, my thesis advisor, for guiding

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Dennis Lee Lutero

Chapter 1 - Introduction

For I am not ashamed of this gospel, for it is power from God leading to salvation for everyone who has faith - not only for the Jew first, but also for the Greek.¹

This verse has been identified by many commentators as the theme for Paul's letter to the Romans. While there is much agreement on this point, it serves as the launching pad for all manner of exegetical and theological debates concerning the rest of the letter and what exactly it was that Paul was trying to communicate and to whom. These debates continue to this day unabated, and though much progress has been made in understanding many of the details within Paul's argument with regard to a variety of topics (much of it dealing with the "Jewishness" of the letter and Paul's place "within Judaism"), there seems to be no end in sight. This flurry of activity with no appreciable forward progress amounts to a stalemate in Romans scholarship, which is indicative of a crisis in the field. In a time of crisis, new and innovative approaches must be considered. My hope for this paper is that the exegetical changes I propose here, each a seemingly small adjustment, might in aggregate change our perception of the landscape and open up new (or forgotten) trails that lead to resolutions of the most fundamental challenges facing Romans scholars today.

The approach I am proposing in this paper is what might be seen as the next step in an exegetical evolution that has been in motion for just over a hundred years. Here is a truncated summary of what has taken place: since the time of the Reformation, many scholars have accepted the "Melanchthonian" view of Romans as an abstract "compendium of Christian

¹ Romans 1:16, author's translation.

doctrine,”² wherein “justification by faith” is defined with universal application to all peoples; then Stendahl, following the work of other scholars in the 19th and early 20th century, flipped this reading of Romans on its head:

... while Paul addresses himself to the relation of Jews to Gentiles, we tend to read him as if his question was: On what grounds, on what terms, are we to be saved? We think that Paul spoke about justification by faith, using the Jewish-Gentile situation as an instance, as an example. But Paul was chiefly concerned about the relation between Jews and Gentiles - and in the development of this concern he used as one of his arguments the idea of justification by faith.³

With this one move, Stendahl not only challenged justification by faith as Paul’s central message but also changed the scholarly understanding of the interpersonal dynamic of the letter from a universal abstraction to a dialog between “Jews” and “Gentiles.”

For the past 60 years, all scholarly work and progress on the letter to the Romans have taken place within this stated dichotomy - “Jews” against the rest of the world, Israelites vs. Non-Israelites. As Pauline scholarship shifted, first to a “new perspective” and then to a “within Judaism” perspective, a wealth of material has been generated that centers on Jewish law within the Pauline corpus and its interactions with these two groups. Scholars such as Collman, Fredriksen, Nanos, Novenson, Staples, Thiessen, and others have contributed greatly to these conversations. And yet, as they all wrestle with the place of the Torah in Paul’s writings, there remains a sense of befuddlement and dare I say frustration with how Paul seemingly applies the law (or does not apply it) to Gentiles, as well as with how he applies the law (or does not apply it) to “Jews.” I suggest that these apparent discrepancies in logic point to their own solution.

The first step toward clarity is to realize and accept that there are not two groups of

² Andrew A. Das, *Solving the Romans Debate* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2007, Kindle Edition), 26.

³ Krister Stendahl, *Paul Among Jews and Gentiles* (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1976, Kindle Edition), Kindle Locations 85-87.

people involved in Paul’s argument in Romans, but three. This truth arrives with the realization that the term “Jews,” traditionally considered synonymous with “Israel,” does not encompass all Israelites. These other Israelites are those people who are genealogically descended from Israel/Jacob but who are not part of the “Jewish” manifestation of Israelism.⁴ The concept of “Jew” in the first century had a geographic component, referring to those Israelites from Judah/Judea. More importantly, it referred to practicing Torah in a certain way, along with other cultural and societal practices that marked this group out as distinct from other Israelites. Israelites who were not “Jews” by birth could become Jews by adopting those practices, but that left a subset of Israelites who, for various reasons, chose not to follow that path. This includes those who still may have followed Torah, but not in the way that “Jews” did, as well as those who were apostate and may have followed other gods. For now, let us refer to this subset of Israelites that are not Jews as “non-Jewish Israelites.”

With our universe of people expanded from two subsets to three, several questions should immediately present themselves in our study of Romans and in discussions of Paul’s “theology” more generally: how do Paul and his fellow Jews categorize these non-Jewish Israelites - as Israelites or as Gentiles? Are they still part of God’s covenant with Israel? If so, are they still beholden to Torah? Of equal importance - how does Paul refer to this third group of people in his rhetoric within Romans? It is this final question that I will answer in this paper, and hopefully convincingly.

Allow me to explain my position by first returning to Romans 1:16 quoted above. There is a lacuna in New Testament scholarship concerning the pairing of the ethnic markers “Jew” and

⁴ Staples has used this term “Israelism” as well (Jason A. Staples, *Paul and the Resurrection of Israel: Jews, Former Gentiles, Israelites* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2024, Kindle Edition), 690), referring to Paul’s “perspective” as “within Israelism”; this phrase gets the point across but is somewhat clunky; I will suggest an alternative in the conclusion of this paper.

“Greek,” found here in Rom 1:16, as well as elsewhere in Romans, in several other Pauline letters, and in Acts. This is not to say that scholars have not commented on this phrase, whether in Romans or elsewhere, which they have; however, their comments are founded on the presupposition that “Greek” is synonymous with “Gentile,” referring to all non-Israelites from other nations, and thus the combination of “Jew” and “Greek” is shorthand for referring to “all humanity.” To the contrary, I assert in this paper that Paul uses the group marker “Greek” to refer to *non-Jewish Israelites* (primarily those from the tribes associated with the former Northern Kingdom of Israel), and therefore the presupposition that “Greek” and “Gentile” are synonymous is a linguistic mistake, as is the assumption that “Jew and Greek” refers to all humanity. The shocking but satisfying alternative understanding is that “Jew and Greek” refers not to “all humanity” but to “all Israel,” making Paul’s letter to the Romans an intra-Israel debate, wherein Paul, speaking to fellow Jews, argues for the inclusion of all Israelites, even those in the diaspora who may have apostatized and turned to idols, similar to their Gentiles neighbors. I argue that all three groups - Jews, non-Jewish Israelites, and Gentiles (non-Israelites) - are part of the discussion in Romans as well as part of the audience, but Paul’s primary concern is the status of his non-Jewish Israelite siblings.

In chapter 2, “Literature Review,” I will review a representative sample of Romans scholarship, focusing on the interpretation of the various ethnic group markers that Paul uses in the letter. I include in this chapter a side tour to discuss who Paul’s primary audience in Romans is - a separate question from the identification of the various group markers in the letter, but a question to which ethnicity is an integral part. I include a detailed discussion of Jason Staples’s groundbreaking 2021 monograph, *The Idea of Israel in Second Temple Judaism*.

Chapter 3, “Methods,” focuses on linguistic analysis as the core method that I use in my

analysis, with a brief discussion of select tools from discourse analysis and how I either align with or diverge from certain approaches. I discuss several topics that have informed my analysis of Paul's audience ("Audience Considerations"), including a comment on "deconflating" group markers, a discussion of the limits of historical criticism vis-a-vis the Edict of Claudius, and an explanation of the application of "fuzzy logic" as a thought experiment tool to help in the determination of Paul's intended audience. Finally, I briefly consider my engagement with Theological Interpretation of Scripture (TIS) and "Paul within Judaism" ("Other Considerations").

I begin my "Analysis" (chapter 4) with a brief discussion of Paul's background ("Paul the Letter Writer") and its impact on his rhetoric within Romans. This is followed by a section on his audience ("Paul's Audience - a First Look"), in which I explore the various direct address group markers, many of which are traditionally read as universal markers but have an ethnic Israelite facet that should be considered. I then examine the concepts of "Jew/Judah" and "Israel" in Romans 9 - 11 ("Ethnic Group Markers in Old Testament Quotations in Romans 9 - 11"), leaning heavily on the work of Jason Staples. I segue into the heart of my analysis, a discussion of the meaning of "Jew and Greek" in the letter ("'Jew and Greek' - Intra-Israelite Group Markers in Romans"). Finally, I bring all these threads together ("Synthesis"), discussing how these exegetical moves affect the overall understanding of the letter, resulting in a cohesive and coherent reading of Romans from start to finish.

In chapter 5, "Conclusions," I summarize and discuss the key findings in this thesis, using contemporary examples to relate my investigation process and the potential sea change that these findings might bring to today's world of Romans scholarship. I propose several subsequent exegetical and theological questions that arise from the assertions made here and suggest areas

for further research.

Due to space and time restraints and the expectations for a masters-level thesis, I have attempted to appropriately bound my thesis question and my response to it. In so doing, there is much within the exegesis of Romans that I have not touched on, or if mentioned, I have only done so in passing. I have not engaged with any of the extended debates concerning the role of Torah in Second Temple Judaism or the early Christian church. Likewise, I have not dedicated any space to theology writ large, to include but not limited to a discussion of the Reformation and the justification by faith battles between Protestants and Catholics, or any discussion of systematic theology generally. Textually, I have engaged very little with chapters 12 through 16 of Romans and any of the exegetical debates that occur around that material, even if it involves discussions concerning the ethnicity of Paul's audience (i.e., the ethnicity of names found in chapter 16).

Chapter 2 – Literature Review

1. Introduction

Life would be simple, and Paul would be at least a bit easier to grasp if he had just provided a glossary for each of his letters. Alas, he did not. He uses words and phrases that are known (or that he assumes are known) by his originally intended hearers, and so there is no glossary, and rarely an embedded definition to help the 21st century reader. Readers approach this challenge in one of two ways: they either presuppose a definition based on a traditionally accepted understanding of a word, or they dig a little deeper, using context cues and other grammatical, logical, rhetorical, historical, and sociological clues to make a determination that might be different from those traditionally received presupposed definitions. Scholars are also party to these two options; unfortunately, scholars are sometimes prone to presuppositions as well, as will be noted below. I will focus this literature review in these areas as we examine the various “ethnic” markers that Paul uses in Romans - Gentile, Greek, Barbarian, Jew, Israel, and Israelite. We will also briefly consider several other group markers that are implicitly “ethnic”: holy ones, called ones, beloved ones, and brothers/siblings. Even within these areas, my examination will not be exhaustive but representative of the most recent positions in each category.

2. Gentiles, Greeks, and Barbarians

Three nouns with ethnic denotations in Romans - ἔθνος (Rom 1:5, 1:13, 2:14, 2:24, 3:29, 4:17, 4:18, 9:24, 9:30, 10:19, 11:11, 11:12, 11:13, 11:25, 15:9, 15:10, 15:11, 15:12, 15:16, 15:18, 15:27, 16:4, 16:26), Ἕλληνας (1:14, 1:16, 2:9, 2:10, 3:9, 10:12), and βάρβαρος (1:14) - are traditionally considered together as group markers for the non-Jewish peoples of the world.

While not identical in meaning, they are treated as synonyms and their interpretation within the

text of Romans, as well as the rest of the Pauline corpus and the New Testament, is affected by this decision. We will examine each one in turn, as well as the pairing “Greeks and Barbarians” (1:14), the only pairing among these three words found in Romans, and in fact the only one found in the whole of Scripture.⁵

2.1. Ἔθνος

BDAG lists two definitions for ἔθνος, one for the singular form and one for the plural. In the singular, it is defined as “a body of persons united by kinship, culture, and common traditions, *nation, people*” (italics in the original).⁶ In the plural, it is defined as “people groups foreign to a specific people group.”⁷ BDAG notes the use of ἔθνη (plural nominative/accusative form) in the LXX as corresponding to the Hebrew עַמִּים, also translated as “peoples” or “nations.”⁸ It also lists several classic Greek sources (e.g., Polybius and Cassio Dio) in which the term is used opposite the plural of Ἕλληνας (“Greeks”) to indicate the entirety of humanity, “Greeks and the nations,” from a Greek point of view (a similar pairing with “Jews” or “Israel” is not found in the NT, however, contrary to common expectations).⁹ In the OT, “Israel” is often juxtaposed with “nations,” but not directly paired.¹⁰ In both of these cases, ἔθνη is not used to designate a

⁵ Βάρβαρος and Ἕλληνας are found together in a list in Col 3:11, however they are not directly paired: Ἕλληνας (Greek) is paired with Ἰουδαῖος (Jew), while Βάρβαρος (separated from “Jew and Greek” by “circumcised and uncircumcised”) is seemingly paired with Σκύθης, which is translated “Scythian” (I say “seemingly” because the final four terms in this list are not separated by καὶ like the first two pairs were).

⁶ BDAG, 276.

⁷ BDAG provides two alternate definitions under this heading: a) “those who do not belong to groups professing faith in the God of Israel”; and b) “non-Israelite Christians, gentiles of Christian congregations composed of more than one nationality and not limited to people of Israel.”

⁸ Holladay, *A Concise Hebrew and Aramaic Lexicon of the Old Testament* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmanns Publishing Co., 1971), 57.

⁹ Eph 2:11-12 comes close; however, the phrase ἐν σαρκί added as a qualifer of ὑμεῖς τὰ ἔθνη potentially changes the meaning of τὰ ἔθνη and must be considered in the exegesis of this passage.

¹⁰ Most English translations render the Hebrew עַמִּים as “nations,” although the KJV (and moreso the NKJV) uses “Gentiles” in various places.

particular ethnicity, but rather the sum of all ethnicities in opposition to a single ethnicity, either Greek or Israelite.

Some scholars have noted (and most accept) that ἔθνος is a multivalent term - it can denote the native people of a particular nation or the native land to which they are attached. This has resulted in the word ἔθνος being rendered both as “nation(s)” and “Gentile(s)” in most modern translations, depending on the perceived context. In each case where an author uses the term, he or she may have in mind one or the other of these facets of the definition, but in all cases both meanings are present - you cannot completely separate the people from the land, and vice versa. This presents an exegetical challenge wherever ἔθνος is used, and specifically in Romans. Cranfield notes this in his exegesis of Romans 1:6-7:

The words ἐν οἷς ἐστε καὶ ὑμεῖς are very often taken to be a clear indication that the Roman church was at this time predominantly Gentile;¹ but they could quite as well simply refer to its geographical situation in the midst of the Gentile world.² ¹¹

Cranfield offers in a footnote the example of Acts 21:21, another instance where ἔθνος is specifically used to refer to Jews living within other nations, and thus uses ἔθνος in a geographic sense:

and they have been told about you that you teach all the Jews who are *among the Gentiles* to forsake Moses, telling them not to circumcise their children or walk according to our customs. (ESV, emphasis added)

Cranfield, based on this logic and other factors, argues for a Roman audience of mixed ethnic origin, both Jews and Gentiles. While this understanding is generally accepted by NT scholars today, the ongoing debate concerns who Paul’s *intended* audience is in Romans: to whom is his grand argument in this letter directed? The answer for most scholars of the past 50 years has

¹¹ Charles E. B. Cranfield, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Epistle to the Romans, Volume I (The International Critical Commentary)* (Edinburgh: T. & T. Clark Limited, 1975), 68.

been that Paul’s argument is directed at Gentiles.¹² They base this assumption primarily on the use of the term ἔθνος in Romans, citing 1:5, 1:13, and 11:13. And yet, the majority of these scholars acknowledge that the tenor of the letter reads as very Jewish in character. They deal with this “double nature” in a variety of ways exegetically, while continuing to assert that Paul’s intended or “encoded” audience is indeed Gentile.¹³ Mason and Watson are standouts in this debate, arguing for a primarily Jewish audience. I will discuss their positions in the section “Jews, Israel, and Israelites” below.

In chapter 4, I accept Cranfield’s view of ἔθνος, that the term can be used in context to refer to a geographical location wherein a group of people are located who are not necessarily those people ethnically associated with that particular location. Understanding ἔθνος in this way is not to suggest that the meaning has changed; ἔθνος still refers to a “nation,” represented by its people and the land they traditionally inhabit.¹⁴ However, the term can be used, as determined by context and as shown above, to indicate the location of a group of people who are “aliens” in that “nation” or “nations,” i.e., Jews/Israelites in the diaspora. As seen in Cranfield’s discussion of Rom 1:6-7 above, neither view is falsifiable; within the isolation of the verse being considered, both options are plausible, and the ambiguity remains. It is only in considering the wider context of the passage, of the pericope, and of the letter as a whole that one can make a definitive case

¹² Mason lists supporters of a Gentile intended audience in “For I am not ashamed of the Gospel’ (Rom 1.16): the gospel and the first readers of Romans,” in *Gospel in Paul: Studies on Corinthians, Galatians and Romans for Richard N. Longenecker (JSNT, Supplement Series 108)*, ed. L. Ann Jervis and Peter Richardson (Sheffield, UK: Sheffield Academic Press, 1994), 255, footnote 3. To his list I add Rafael Rodriguez, Matthew Thiessen, Ryan Collman, Paula Fredriksen, Jason Staples, Matthew Novenson, N. T. Wright, Andrew Das, Stanley Porter, Stanley Stowers, Mark Nanos, Douglas Moo, and James D. G. Dunn.

¹³ Stanley K. Stowers, *A Rereading of Romans: Justice, Jews, and Gentiles* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1994), 21-22. See also Das, who reviews much of the scholarship on “encoded” readers/audience.

¹⁴ ἔθνος is a generic term and is usually used in the plural to refer to “nations” broadly; reference to a specific “nation” or group of people is determined by context.

for one view or another. That said, I believe there are some rules of thumb that we can apply to help us determine the use of ἔθνος in a given situation. I discuss these methods in chapter 4, “Analysis,” section 3.1.4, “Excursus – a “Gentile” Hermeneutic.”

2.2. Ἕλληνας

BDAG lists two primary definitions for the term Ἕλληνας: 1) “a pers. of Greek language and culture”; 2) all persons who came under the influence of Greek, as distinguished from Israel’s culture.”¹⁵ Note that neither of these definitions, in considering the use of Ἕλληνας in a New Testament context, make reference to Greece as a region or province or any associated Greek city-state of the first century.¹⁶ The second definition in BDAG includes two subordinate definitions: a) “gentile, polytheist, Greco-Roman”; and b) “used of non-Israelites/gentiles who expressed an interest in the cultic life of Israel.” Once again in these subordinate definitions there is no indication that the term is used to refer to a specific people associated with the land of Greece. While definition 2 seems to allow the universal application of Ἕλληνας to “all persons,” and therefore also to Jews/Israelites, both of its subordinate definitions restrict its applicability to “gentiles.” Accepting the primary definitions, my proposal in this paper that Ἕλληνας could refer to non-Jewish Israelites does not contradict BDAG. To take it a step further, I could argue, in concert with Hengel, that this definition could be applied equally to Jewish Israelites of the first century!¹⁷ However, this is not the case in Romans; Paul is contrasting the term Ἕλληνας with

¹⁵ BDAG, 318.

¹⁶ “Greece” (Ἑλλάς) is mentioned once in the NT, Acts 20:2; “Macedonia and Achaia,” mentioned in Rom 15:26, “generally refers to all Greece” (J. D. Douglas and Merrill C. Tenney, *Zondervan Illustrated Bible Dictionary: The Most Accurate and Comprehensive One-Volume Bible Dictionary Available* Revised ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2011, Kindle edition), “Achaia,” location 1036.)

¹⁷ Martin Hengel, *Judaism and Hellenism: Studies in Their Encounter in Palestine during the Early Hellenistic Period*, Reprint edition (Eugene, Oregon: Wipf and Stock, 2003), 104: “From about the middle of the third century BC all Judaism must really be designated ‘*Hellenistic Judaism*’ in the strict sense...” (italics original).

Ἰουδαῖος, which we will examine below.

It is worth noting up front that in all five occurrences of the term Ἕλλησιν in Romans, the word is directly paired with Ἰουδαῖος (four times) or βάρβαρος (1:14). Given this fact, it is challenging to discuss the interpretation of Ἕλλησιν without also talking about these pairings. In this section, I will look at how scholars understand Ἕλλησιν, both individually and as paired. I will then revisit the exegesis of the pairing of “Jew and Greek” after the investigation of Ἰουδαῖος.

As mentioned above, Ἕλλησιν is considered by most scholars as synonymous with ἔθνος, both in Romans and the rest of the NT.¹⁸ Scholars like Esler go into great detail describing the ethnic background of the “Hellenes,” but in the end revert to this conflation of the two terms into the concept of a generic “Gentile.”¹⁹ Like others, Esler arrives at this conclusion not because of the definition and background he provides but in spite of it. While defending a mixed audience in Romans, he makes this statement:

None of this suggests he is not speaking to Judeans, nor does his statement in the next verse of the debt he owes (that is, because of his success) to “Greeks and barbarians” (*meaning non-Judeans of all ethnic groups, although using language that typified the way that Greeks themselves divided their social world*) and whether educated or not.²⁰ (emphasis added)

Esler provides his connotation of “Greeks and Barbarians,” and then immediately qualifies his definition by pointing out that his understanding is counter to the use by Greek writers, and not in a parallel way. In similar fashion, Moo, referring to “Greeks and Barbarians” in v. 1:14, states: “Probably, then, Paul intends in the first pair to designate all of *Gentile* humanity, divided

¹⁸ Das, 59.

¹⁹ Esler, *Conflict and Identity in Romans: the Social Setting of Paul's Letter* (Minneapolis: Augsburg Fortress, 2003), 115.

²⁰ Esler, *Conflict and Identity in Romans*, 115.

according to linguistic/cultural criteria”²¹(emphasis original). Moo does not go to the lengths that Esler does to provide the background of either term, but arrives at the same place as Esler - insisting that “Greek” is a synonym for “Gentile”:

Still others are impressed by the way in which the phrase “to the Jew first and then to the Greek” (v. 16b) encapsulates two of the letter’s key themes: the incorporation of Gentiles within the people of God and the continuing significance of Israel.²²

In this excerpt, we see how the term “Greek” is paired with “Jew” and rendered “Gentile,” in contrast to its pairing with “Barbarian,” where it is understood as a subset of Gentile. For most commentators of Romans, this shift in meaning is done without explanation or comment.²³

The main focus of this paper is on Paul’s use of the term Ἕλλην. Despite the accepted interpretation of this term as equivalent to “Gentiles” by New Testament scholars, Ἕλλην is an ambiguous identifier, and therefore its use by Paul leaves room for exploring other options of interpretation. As discussed in the introduction, I suggest an alternate view to that which is traditionally held: that Paul is using Ἕλλην to designate non-Jewish Israelites. I propose that this usage is not a novel move by Paul but rather a common practice among Israelites, and thus immediately understood by his audience without further explanation. Thus, the pairing “Jew and Greek” in this reading refers to two types of Israelites – those primarily from the Southern Kingdom of Judah (and are following Torah) and those primarily from the Northern Kingdom of Israel (who are predominantly not following Torah). I will develop this position further in chapter 4, “Analysis.” There, I will also address whether Ἕλλην can still be used to refer to

²¹ Douglas J. Moo, *The Letter to the Romans, Second Edition (The New International Commentary on the New Testament)* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2018), 65.

²² Moo, *The Letter to the Romans*, 68.

²³ See, for instance, Beverly Roberts Gaventa, *Romans: A Commentary* (Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox, 2024, Kindle Edition), 138, 141, 146; Leander E. Keck, *Abingdon New Testament Commentaries: Romans* (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 2005, Kindle Edition), 49, 51, 54.

“Gentiles” generically and how we can determine in any given situation which rendering is appropriate (section 5.4, “Greeks” as “Gentiles”).

2.3. βάρβαρος

We have already briefly discussed the term βάρβαρος above in relation to Ἕλληνας; here we will examine the use of the word on its own. Βάρβαρος occurs just once in Romans in v. 1:14. It is found three more times in the rest of the Pauline corpus (twice in 1 Cor 14:11, once more notably in Col 3:11) and only twice more in the remainder of the NT, both times in Acts (28:2, 4), referring to the “native people” of Malta during Paul’s visit to the island after a shipwreck. BDAG defines βάρβαρος as “pertaining to using a language that is unintelligible to outsiders, *foreign-speaking, of foreign tongue*” (emphasis original).²⁴ The lexicon points out that the term βάρβαρος is onomatopoeic in construction, mimicking the perceived sound of someone speaking a different language that you do not understand. The second definition provided by BDAG connects βάρβαρος to its use in Greek culture, making it the antithesis of “Greek”: “pertaining to not speaking Greek or participating in Greek culture,” with the sub-definitions of “*not Hellenic*” (adjective form) and “*a non-Hellene, foreigner*” (substantive form). It is noteworthy that there is no discussion in the lexicon of how the term might be used differently by other cultures (i.e., Jewish/Israelite).

From these somewhat neutral definitions, commentators often focus on the negative connotations of the term. Indeed, the definition itself suggests that this word is used to distinguish “outsiders” from “insiders,” but Greek literature contemporaneous with the Second Temple Period heightens the derogatory use of the word. This act of “othering” was reflected in Greek dramas, as Esler outlines:

In line with a common strategy in stereotyping of projecting the opposite of insiders'

²⁴ BDAG, 166.

values onto outsiders, the tragedians defined the nature of Greek morality by attributing the vices that corresponded to these virtues, such as stupidity, cowardice, abandonment, and lawlessness," to "barbarian" characters in drama.²⁵

Even with this background, Esler, as quoted in the “Greeks” section above, sees Paul’s use of the term βάρβαρος as a matter-of-fact designation, albeit still tinged with a negative connotation:

To speak of "Greeks (Ἕλληνες) and barbarians (βάρβαροι)" is to adopt, for a moment, the stereotypical way in which people claiming for themselves Greek ethnicity, whether originating in Greece itself or from other parts of the Mediterranean claiming "Greekness" in the manner I have described in chapter three, see all other outgroups as uncivilized people speaking outlandish languages (= βάρβαροι). Paul is claiming he has been successful with people of all sorts.²⁶

Dunn similarly rehearses the etymology and history of use of the term, but eventually lands on the more generic interpretation:

In using the phrase here, however, Paul is not necessarily accepting the viewpoint of the “Greeks” or designating particular groups as “barbarians.” By now it had simply become a standard phrase to include all races and classes within the Gentile world.²⁷

While Dunn and Esler provide some background of the term βάρβαρος before accepting it as just another synonym for “Gentile,” others do not bother with any alternate views, accepting the “Gentile” definition straightaway as received common knowledge.²⁸

3. Jews, Israel, and Israelites

Just as we saw above with the terms Gentile/Greek/Barbarian, most scholars treat the terms Jew/Israel/Israelite synonymously, with the two groups each representing half of the universe of humankind: the people of the nations, and the people of Israel, called “Jews.” It is not

²⁵ Esler, *Conflict and Identity in Romans*, 61.

²⁶ Esler, *Conflict and Identity in Romans*, 138-139.

²⁷ James D. G. Dunn, *Romans 1-8*, Volume 38A (Word Biblical Commentary) (Grand Rapids: Zondervan Academic, 2018, Kindle Edition), 33.

²⁸ Das, 62; Keck, 49.

worthwhile to discuss these three words separately, since almost all scholars, past and present, presuppose that all three refer to the same group of people. Therefore, I will address them together in this section.

First, the lexical definitions (BDAG) and occurrences in Romans and the NT:

Ἰουδαῖος: pertaining to being Judean (Jewish), with focus on adherence to Mosaic tradition, *Judean*; used as both an adjective and a noun. Occurs 11 times in Romans (1:16, 2:9, 2:10, 2:17, 2:28, 2:29, 3:1, 3:9, 3:29, 9:24, 10:12) and 182 times elsewhere in the NT.²⁹

Ἰσραήλ: BDAG lists three definitions: 1) the patriarch Jacob, *Israel*; 2) the people/nation of Israel, *Israel*; 3) Christians as entitled to the term Israel, *Israel*. Occurs 11 times in Romans (9:6 - 2 times, 9:27 - 2 times, 9:31, 10:19, 10:21, 11:2, 11:7, 11:25, 11:26).³⁰ It occurs 57 times elsewhere in the NT.

Ἰσραηλίτης: *Israelite*. Occurs twice in Romans (9:4, 11:1) and 7 more times in the NT (John 1:47, 2 Cor 11:22, 5 times in Acts - 2:22, 3:12, 5:35, 13:16, 21:28).

For much of the 20th century, the discussion around the terms “Jew” and “Israel” was not whether they both applied to the Jewish people - everyone assumed as much - but whether the terms were used in different situations. The cornerstone in this effort was the work of K. G. Kuhn, in his definition of Ἰσραήλ as an “insider” term (used by Jews self-referentially when talking amongst themselves), while Ἰουδαῖος was used as an “outsider” term (what Jews were called by Gentiles, or what Jews called themselves when talking with Gentiles).³¹

²⁹ In some translations (ESV, RSV et al), the word “Jews” is inserted though it is not present in the Greek: 3:2, 3:9 (first occurrence in the verse), and 11:14.

³⁰ The ESV, NIV, RSV, CSB, and the NET all use “Israel” in 11:11: “So I ask, did they stumble in order that they might fall? By no means! Rather, through their trespass salvation has come to the Gentiles, so as to make Israel jealous.” This is an interpolation; Ἰσραήλ does not occur in the Greek.

³¹ Staples, *The Idea of Israel in Second Temple Judaism: A New Theory of People, Exile, and Israelite Identity* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2021), 26-27ff. Jason Staples discusses at length the influence of

When we turn to commentaries on Romans, there is little if any discussion concerning the differentiation of the two terms Ἰουδαῖος and Ἰσραήλ - the authors presuppose their equivalence. In his introduction to Romans 9-11, the chapters which include all 11 occurrences of Ἰσραήλ in the letter, Dunn states, “The problem is that God’s word of call and promise to Abraham has evidently not been fulfilled (as Paul counts fulfillment) in his own people the Jews.³²” Keck equates the two terms in his exposition of 9:3-5: “Nonetheless, the designation of his biological kindred as “Israelites” signals the religious significance of the people (“Jews” is generally used to emphasize the ethnic contrast with Gentiles).”³³ Esler, in describing the link between people and land, makes this observation:

In *the Judean Antiquities* of Josephus, for example, the word Ἑβραῖοί is most commonly used of the people in the patriarchal and Egyptian period, while Ἰσραηλίτης comes to be used most frequently of them when Joshua has led the people across the Jordan; but from the time, in book 11, when Cyrus gives them permission to return to Ἰουδαία to rebuild the temple, they are referred to on most occasions as Ἰουδαῖοι.³⁴

Esler reads these three terms as referring to one group who is known by several different names throughout time. Like the others, he equates Jews and Israel/Israelites.

3.1. Jason A. Staples – The Idea of Israel

This monolithic view of the terms Ἰσραήλ and Ἰουδαῖος being synonymous shifted dramatically with the publishing of Jason Staples’s monograph *The Idea of Israel in Second Temple Judaism* in 2021. In this first volume of a two-volume opus, Staples catalogs a wealth of material, from

Kuhn’s article and subsequent work, as well as the history of the progression of these assumptions through the 20th century.

³² James D. G. Dunn, *Romans 9-16*, Volume 38B (Word Biblical Commentary) (Grand Rapids: Zondervan Academic, 2018, Kindle Edition), 518.

³³ Keck, 227.

³⁴ Esler, *Conflict and Identity in Romans*, 64.

the Hebrew Bible to extra-biblical writings from the Second Temple period, showing that “Jew” and “Israel” are indeed not equal. He summarizes his findings well in the opening of his concluding chapter:

Remarkably, the one perspective not significantly represented in this body of evidence is the one usually assumed by modern scholars: namely, that Israel is equivalent to the Jews (Ioudaioi/Yehudim). Rather than being an accurate historical or sociological reconstruction of the data, that assumption is best characterized as a theological position based on later polemics.³⁵

Staples also shatters the notion that “Israel” and “Jew” should be considered “insider” and “outsider” terms, where “Israel” is used by Israelites to refer to themselves and “Jew” is the “non-Jewish” name for Jews, a view originating with Karl G. Kuhn in a 1938 article and broadly espoused and applied:

Moreover, there is also no ancient evidence that suggests “Jew” should be understood as an outsider term while “Israelite” and “Hebrew” function as insider terms. Instead, the evidence is overwhelming that the three terms and the concepts they represent are neither synonymous nor coextensive in the Second Temple period, with each having its own specific nuance, overlapping with but not identical to the meaning of the others.³⁶

As mentioned earlier, Staples has made this same claim about the distinction between Israel and *Ioudaioi* for the New Testament in general and in Romans in particular in a 2011 paper entitled “What Do the Gentiles Have to Do with “All Israel”? A Fresh Look at Romans 11:25-27.”³⁷ In his second volume, *Paul and the Resurrection of Israel: Jews, Former Gentiles, Israelites*, Staples expands this treatment to all of the New Testament, and specifically to the rest of Romans, continuing to argue for a definitive distinction between Ἰσραήλ and Ἰουδαῖος:

As previously discussed, although Paul regularly uses the term *Ioudaios* (“Jew”) elsewhere, Rom 9 marks a sudden shift to “Israel” terminology, which appears only six other times in the undisputed letters but thirteen times in Rom 9–11. Unfortunately, the

³⁵ Staples, *The Idea of Israel*, 339.

³⁶ Staples, *The Idea of Israel*, 339.

³⁷ Jason A. Staples, “What Do the Gentiles Have to Do with “All Israel”? A Fresh Look at Romans 11:25-27.” *JBL* 130, no. 2 (2011), 371-390.

scholarly discussion of these chapters has been muddled by the assumption that “Israel” simply means “the Jews.”³ For example, Dunn opens his treatment of Rom 9 by reminding the reader, “Whatever is made of Paul’s talk of ‘Israel’ in v 6, it should not be forgotten that he prefaces the whole discussion with the firm statement, ‘the Jews are Israelites.’”⁴ But this is a curious admonition since Paul does not in fact say this.³⁸

In summary, according to Staples, when Paul uses “Israel” in Romans, just as his contemporaries and predecessors throughout Second Temple literature, he means one of three things: 1) Israel in the ancient past (all twelve tribes); 2) the Northern Kingdom of Israel in the divided monarchy; or 3) reunited Israel (all twelve tribes) in the eschatological future. The corollary is that “Israel” is never used as a synonym for “Jew/s” and vice versa.³⁹

This line of reasoning that Staples offers has been well received by other biblical scholars, including NT and Pauline scholars. Sloan states that “his arguments about the relation of the labels “Israel” and “Jew” are helpful in themselves (I find them convincing).”⁴⁰ Tilling, after pushing back on much of Staples’s thesis, still concludes: “Staples has persuaded me about the importance of restoration eschatology. He has convinced me that I misunderstood the relationship between the words “Israel” and “Jew”.”⁴¹ Garroay also does not accept all of Staples’s assertions, but he fully supports the newly-described Jew/Israel distinction:

Thus, as Staples reminds readers over and again, in Jewish literature of the Second Temple period, “Israel” often does not mean “Jew,” “Jew” often does not mean “Israel,” and historians should stop proceeding as if they do.⁴²

³⁸ Staples, *Paul and the Resurrection*, 384.

³⁹ Appendix A provides copies of two tables, one from each of Staples’ recent books, both showing data on the group markers “Israel” and “Jews” in Josephus. The minimal overlap between these two terms, not to mention Josephus’s own explanation for why and when it happened, is solid evidence for Staples’s thesis. See each book (details listed in the footnote for each table) for more in-depth information.

⁴⁰ Paul Sloan, “The Idea of Israel in Second Temple Judaism: A New Theory of People, Exile, and Israelite Identity.” *Bulletin for Biblical Research* 33.2 (2023): 228, accessed February 14, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5325/bullbiblrese.33.2.0227>.

⁴¹ Chris Tilling, “Divine Unconditionality or a Staple Diet of Ifs and Buts?: A Review of Paul and the Resurrection of Israel,” *Religious Studies Review* 50.3 (2024): 550.

⁴² Joshua D. Garroay, “Discovering the Lost Tribes of Israel in Romans 9–11,” *Religious Studies Review*

Ehrensperger, on the other hand, pushes back on Staples's thesis, but in ways that show that she misunderstands the main points being made by Staples, which he corrects in his response to her review:

I do not argue that Jews cannot be labeled Israelites or that first-century Jews refrained from referring to themselves as Israelites but rather that not all Israelites are Jews and that "Israel" was consistently understood as a category including but not limited to Jews.⁴³

However, Staples takes a dramatic turn from this core claim of a distinction between the terms Israel and Jews: he asserts that in Paul's argument for Israel and Israelites, he is really arguing for "gentiles" and their inclusion in the covenant:

Specifically, Paul argues that after being divorced from the covenant for infidelity and behaving like the nations, the bulk of non-Jewish Israel had effectively become *gentilized*, having assimilated among the non-Israelite nations. As such, the bulk of **non-Jewish Israel could be reckoned as ethnically dead, having been assimilated and consumed by the nations, no longer ethnically distinct as a people.**⁴⁴ (italics original; bold added)

In both volumes of his work, Staples argues against a "replacement" theology where Jews are replaced by Christians and for a "restorationist" theology where all Israel, all twelve tribes, will be restored to their covenant, only to turn around and, in effect, propose a replacement theology where all gentiles are now considered as Israelites.

Ehrensperger refutes this part of Staples's argument as well, stating what she believes is the view put forth by Staples and giving him the benefit of the doubt that he is still talking about people who are genealogically Israelites:

On his journey, Jason Staples has found *ethne*, addressed by Paul in his letters, who, in his view, actually are the lost tribes of Israel, the ten tribes that disappeared after the Assyrian conquest of the Northern Kingdom called Israel. In Staples's view, Paul's

50.3 (2024): 529.

⁴³ Jason A. Staples, "Ethnic Transformation and Israel's Resurrection in the Pauline Epistles and Beyond: In Grateful Dialogue with Reviewers," *Religious Studies Review*, Vol. 50, No. 3, September 2024, 554.

⁴⁴ Staples, *Paul and the Resurrection*, 661.

addressees, the *ethne* in Christ, are actually and truly Israelites. But they had been so assimilated and mixed up with the surrounding cultures and peoples that they did not know anymore who they really were.⁴⁵

Staples responds:

Kathy Ehrensperger's critique represents the book as arguing that Paul's gentile converts had actually been "Israelites who did not know that they were Israelites ... who had forgotten who they really were". In the book, however, I explicitly argue against that position:

Paul does not suggest that there are "disguised" Israelites among the nations who have simply forgotten their true ethnic heritage and are now being restored through recognition of their Israelite lineage. The nations/gentiles are not unknown Israelites. On the contrary ... the point is that the bulk of northern Israel has actually become "not my people" (=gentiles). ... Israel's redemption is therefore not a matter of finding and identifying unknown Israelites among the nations ... but rather involves recreating Israel from the gentiles through the transformative work of the spirit. (286).⁴⁶

Ehrensperger seems to misread Staples on this point, which means that some of her critique based on her reading misses the mark. However, she still makes a few points that apply to Staples's actual thesis and thus she calls it into question. Ehrensperger is not alone in questioning Staples with regard to his redefinition of Israel: Garroway⁴⁷ and Sloan (presciently in his review of Staples's first book, *The Idea of Israel*⁴⁸) both raise concerns.

While Staples's overall thesis in *Paul and the Resurrection of Israel* has not gained traction among his peers, his groundbreaking insight of the Jew/Israel distinction, presented both

⁴⁵ Kathy Ehrensperger, "Israel and the Nations: Who does Paul Think They are?", *Religious Studies Review*, 50.3, (2024): 539.

⁴⁶ Staples, "Ethnic Transformation", 553.

⁴⁷ Garroway, "Discovering the Lost Tribes of Israel," 530.

⁴⁸ Sloan, "The Idea of Israel in Second Temple Judaism," 229: "Through a thorough examination of the Hebrew Bible and the Jewish texts that interpret it, Staples shows that an expectation of covenant restoration was widespread among groups of the period and that a reunification of Israelites and Jews into the one people, "Israel," was a feature of that restoration. Scholars who opt for an alternate construal of "Israel" language and/or downplay the significance of the ongoing perdurance of "the age of wrath" in Second Temple literature, including the New Testament, must now grapple afresh with Staples's arguments to do so."

in *The Idea of Israel* and more briefly in *Paul and the Resurrection of Israel*, has gained supporters and momentum. This same insight is foundational to my thesis, as will become evident in my analysis (chapter 4).

3.2. Excursus: Jews as Paul's Primary Audience in Rome

As mentioned above, while the majority of NT scholars hold the view that Paul's intended hearers in Romans are primarily Gentile (notwithstanding the presence of "Jews"), there are a few brave souls that have gone against the grain and assert that Jews are the primary audience (again, notwithstanding the presence of Gentiles). We have already detailed Cranfield's exegesis of Rom 1:5-6 above and his acceptance of the "geographic" sense of Ἔθνος as a viable interpretation. However, Cranfield masterfully sits on the fence regarding to whom Paul is directing his overall message; having touted both sides of the argument over who Paul's primary audience is, he ends with a discussion of Käsemann's approach to the question. After considering a list of factors that Käsemann presents that seem to indicate Paul's appeal to the Jewish portion of the Romans, he concludes:

But we question whether the various features of the epistle which Käsemann lists, such as Paul's gentle attitude toward the weak and his emphasizing of the salvation-historical advantage of the Jew,¹ are rightly explained as actually *motivated* by Paul's desire to win Jewish Christian support whether in Rome or in Jerusalem.² The impression we get from our study of Romans is rather that the things which Käsemann lists here are to be explained as arising directly and necessarily from Paul's understanding of the gospel itself.³⁴⁹ (*italics original*)

In the end, Cranfield holds fast to his perch atop the fence and his conviction that the Roman congregation is indeed split down the middle:

The truth would seem to be that it is impossible to decide with anything like absolute certainty whether at the time Paul wrote to them the majority of the Roman Christians were Gentiles or Jews, and that we ought therefore to leave this question open. What is quite certain is that both the Jewish-Christian, and the Gentile-Christian, elements were

⁴⁹ Charles E. B. Cranfield, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Epistle to the Romans. 2: Commentary on Romans IX - XVI and Essays*, Reprint 1998 (Edinburgh: Clark Limited, 1998), 823.

considerable: it was clearly not a matter of an overwhelming majority and a tiny minority.⁵⁰

Even though Cranfield remains noncommittal, a few others have taken his insights and run with them. Watson, while proposing two distinct “congregations” in Rome, one Jewish and one Gentile, cites Cranfield in his discussion of 1:5ff, favoring the understanding that Paul is primarily addressing Jews that “live in the midst of Gentiles.”⁵¹

Mason also agrees with Cranfield that 1:5-6 can refer to Jews “among the nations” and prioritizes this reading. He then shows how 1:14-15 - “Greek and Barbarians, the wise and the foolish” - does not refer to Paul’s Roman audience, making five arguments that refute this reading. I will not replicate them all here, but this excerpt is demonstrative:

If this is what Paul has in mind [that “Greeks and Barbarians” do not refer to his Roman audience], then οὐτως does not mean ‘I am coming to you because I am obligated both to Greeks and barbarians, and you people of course fit this description’, but rather, ‘in fulfilling my obligation to both Greeks and barbarians, I must naturally pass through Rome; hence my desire to visit you’. This interpretation matches Paul’s sense in 15.19-24 exactly: it is his mission to Spain that will bring him incidentally through Rome.⁵²

To leave no doubt that he sees Paul’s primary audience as “Judean-Christian,” Mason concludes:

I have argued that these few references to Gentiles (a) cannot take methodological priority over the orientation of the letter as a whole and (b) can be plausibly understood in ways that do not involve a Gentile audience. It is much more economical to understand them this way than to interpret the rest of the letter as if it were addressed to Gentiles.⁵³

Finally and most recently, John Van Maaren, in a presentation delivered on January 27th, 2025, as part of Houston Christian University Spring Research Seminar, provided epigraphic and textual evidence that shows the use of the phrase ἐν τοῖς ἔθνεσιν (found in v. 1:5

⁵⁰ Cranfield, *Romans Vol 1*, 21.

⁵¹ Francis Watson, “The Two Roman Congregations: Romans 14:1-15:13,” in *The Romans Debate*, ed. Karl P. Donfried (Grand Rapids, MN: Baker Academic, 1991), 213.

⁵² Mason, “For I am not ashamed of the Gospel,” 272.

⁵³ Mason, “For I am not ashamed of the Gospel,” 287.

and 1:13) overwhelmingly signifies a geographic sense, referring to the location of a group within an area that is not their native land.⁵⁴

This short list of scholars provides compelling evidence for a primarily Jewish (intended) audience in Romans, standing in sharp contrast to the army of their peers that hold to a Gentile audience contrary to the Jewish/Israelite material found in chapters 1-11. There has been a proliferation of hypotheses from these scholars that attempt to answer the “double nature” of Romans while maintaining a Gentile intended audience. The results are convoluted, do not account for all parts of the letter, and are ultimately unconvincing. My own analysis sides with those who read in Romans a Jewish intended audience, as will be made clear in chapter 4.

4. Other Group Markers

In addition to the ethnic group markers listed above, Paul uses four other terms in Romans - ἀγαπητός, κλητός, ἅγιος, and ἀδελφός – that are all usually treated as universal terms, applied either to all believers or, more generally, to all humankind in certain circumstances. However, each of these words, used in Romans in the plural, have been demonstrated to refer explicitly to the house of Israel as group markers in the Hebrew Scriptures (a detailed analysis of the occurrence and use of each term in the OT and NT is found in chapter 4, “Analysis”). I will briefly comment below on the exegesis of these terms by NT commentators.

4.1. Beloved (Ones), Called (Ones), Holy (Ones)

The words ἀγαπητός (beloved), κλητός (called), and ἅγιος (holy) are all adjectives, but are often used as substantives, denoting a person or, in the plural, a group of people. I have placed these

⁵⁴ John Van Maaren, “Paul's Addressees in Rome Living among the Nations,” presented via Zoom January 27, 2025, as a part of Houston Christian University Spring Research Seminar (unpublished). Copy provided by author.

three terms together because they all occur in Rom 1:7, where they are typically translated: “To all those in Rome who are loved by God and called to be saints: Grace to you and peace from God our Father and the Lord Jesus Christ” (ESV). In this rendering, ἀγαπητός and κλητός are translated as periphrastic participles, while ἅγιος is translated as a substantive adjective in apposition to πᾶσιν τοῖς at the beginning of the verse. Moo’s description of Paul’s use of the terms ἀγαπητός, κλητός and ἅγιος is indicative of the traditional interpretation of these group markers by Pauline scholars:

In designating the Roman Christians as “beloved by God” and “called to be saints,” Paul implies that they are God’s chosen people; for both phrases echo OT designations of Israel.⁹⁷ In so transferring language used of Israel in the OT to Christians, Paul initiates an important theme of the first eight chapters of the letter. In addition, these two descriptions remind the readers that who they are depends on God’s love and call.⁵⁵

Moo et al. recognize the connection of these terms specifically to Israel and its people in the covenant as detailed in the OT, but they immediately discount this understanding in Romans, preferring to read these markers as applying to all believers in Paul’s audience. They make this move as a presupposition based on their understanding of Romans as directed to Gentiles, with no further substantiation from the text of Romans or any other text, New Testament or Old.⁵⁶

4.2. Brothers/Siblings

The word ἀδελφός, typically translated “brother,” “sibling,” or “brothers and sisters” in the plural, occurs 18 times in Romans: 5 times in the singular, 13 times in the plural; of the plural occurrences, 10 are in the vocative. Some commentators acknowledge that Jews call each other “brother,” invoking a kind of “fictive kinship.”⁵⁷ Longenecker and Dunn are quick to point out

⁵⁵ Moo, *The Letter to the Romans*, 53.

⁵⁶ Craig S. Keener, *Romans* (Eugene, OR: Cascade Books, 2009), Kindle Edition, location 992.

⁵⁷ Richard N. Longenecker, *The Epistle to the Romans* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 2016, Kindle Edition), 135; Das, 123-126; Mark D. Nanos, *The Mystery of Romans: The Jewish Context of Paul's Letters*

that “Greek” and “other religious” associations followed this same pattern of usage. Das, considering arguments from Gagnon and Nanos, concludes that Paul uses “brothers” to indicate Christ-believers, to the exclusion of non-believing Jews, with the exception of Rom 9:3, which he discounts due the qualifying statements from the surrounding verses. Other scholars, however, without pointing to this historical reference of usage by the Jews, presuppose that “brothers” is being used by Paul to refer to all believers in his audience, regardless of ethnicity.⁵⁸ Other commentators do not even address the use of the term.⁵⁹

5. Conclusion

We see that the traditional view of the actors in Romans is dominated by the “Jew”/ “Gentile” binary with no room for consideration of other groups. There is also an abstraction of group markers typically associated with the house of Israel so that they are applied to “all believers” without thoroughly considering the possibility that these terms still apply to ethnic Israel. By way of summary, the table below shows the group markers discussed and the traditional views of their definitions/descriptions:

(Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1996, Kindle Edition), Locations 892-894; James D. G. Dunn, *Romans 1-8*, Volume 38A (Word Biblical Commentary) (Grand Rapids: Zondervan Academic, 2018, Kindle Edition), 31.

⁵⁸ Keck, 48; Gaventa, 63.

⁵⁹ Melancthon, Philipp, *Commentary on Romans* (Kindle Locations 1312-1319). Concordia Publishing House. Kindle Edition; Neil Elliott, *The Rhetoric of Romans: Argumentative Constraint: And Strategy and Paul's Dialogue with Judaism* (Minneapolis, MN: Fortress Press, 2006, Kindle Edition), Kindle Locations 669-674; Andrew David Naselli, *Romans: A Concise Guide to the Greatest Letter Ever Written* (Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2022, Kindle Edition); Aaron Sherwood, *Romans: A Structural, Thematic, and Exegetical Commentary* (Bellingham, WA: Lexham Press, 2020, Kindle Edition), 117-118; F. F. Bruce, *Romans: An Introduction and Commentary (Tyndale New Testament Commentaries (IVP Numbered) Book 6)* (Downer's Grove, ILL: InterVarsity Press, 2014, Kindle Edition), 82.; Krister Stendahl, *Final Account: Paul's Letter to the Romans* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1995, Kindle Edition), Kindle Location 298; Craig S. Keener, *Romans*.

Table 1 - Traditional Interpretations of Ethnic Group Markers in Romans

Group Markers		Accepted Applications		
Greek	English	"Gentiles"	"Jews"	All Believers
ἔθνη	Gentiles/nations	✓		
Ἰουδαῖος	Jews		✓	
Ἕλληνες	Greeks	✓		
Ἰσραήλ	Israel		✓	
ἀδελφοί	Brothers/siblings			✓
ἅγιοι	Holy (ones)			✓
κλητοί	Called (ones)			✓
ἀγαπητοί	Beloved (ones)			✓

Even the scholars that advocate for a Jewish audience in Romans hold to these definitions; the argument for a primarily or intended audience of Jews in Romans stands on its own apart from how these terms are interpreted. The one qualification is that ἔθνη has a polysemic character, referring to both a group of people and the land they indigenously inhabit, which as seen above affects one's reading of audience in the letter. My goal is to show the strong plausibility that the terms "Greek" and "Gentile" should be distinguished from one another, just as "Jew" and "Israel" also represent two distinct groups. I will provide an updated version of this table with my recommended adjustments to these definitions in chapter 4, "Analysis."

Chapter 3 – Methods

1. Introduction

The assertion that I am making in this thesis, that the term “Greek” as used by Paul in Romans is to be understood as referring to non-Jewish Israelites, is on the surface a matter of lexical analysis and an exploration of what Porter refers to as the lexicogrammar (a lexicogrammar “includes the lexicon as the most delicate level of grammar, in which the cotextualized [sic] meaning of a lexeme is modulated by meaningful grammatical structures”).⁶⁰ Even so, my approach to exegesis in this endeavor has been multidisciplinary in nature by necessity. With the overarching goal of understanding Romans as a first century hearer would and as the author originally intended, I have had to contend with the various critical methods in use today by scholars who propose different and often conflicting readings of Paul’s letter. Even so, my own starting point in this endeavor is what might be best referred to as type of “discourse analysis,” with the awareness that this phrase has been defined in a number of ways in the literature.⁶¹ I will first describe the elements of my approach that I believe fit under this “discourse-focused” umbrella and how they differ from other definitions. I will then briefly discuss several other methods with which I have interacted, whether that has been to adopt, reject, or transform them.

2. A Focus on Discourse

When I began to study Romans more deeply about a decade ago, the primary motivating factor was to understand the letter as a whole. Previously, every sermon and bible study that used

⁶⁰ Stanley E. Porter, *Linguistic Analysis of the Greek New Testament: Studies in Tools, Methods, and Practice* (Grand Rapids: Baker Publishing Group, 2015), 165.

⁶¹ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 216.

Romans as its text presented only parts of the text in abstraction. Pastors and theologians alike would attempt to show how their exegesis of the selected excerpts from the text fit into the overall letter; and yet, whenever I would read the letter straight through from beginning to end, I would experience cognitive dissonance. The verses drawn from Romans, even when extracted in larger chunks, did not fit neatly back into the apparent arguments that Paul seemed to be making in the letter writ large. As a way of attempting to break through these discontinuities, I started consuming Romans in its entirety in one sitting: both by reading the text start to finish, as well as listening to others read it to me. I did this daily over a period of months and years. As I internalized the structure of Romans in this temporal fashion, the message of the letter as a whole became the guiding organizational principle for my engagement with the exegesis of others. I began personally (somewhat tongue in cheek) referring to this as a “Whole Letter Hermeneutic.” What I did not realize at the time was that I was taking part in a form of discourse analysis.

Discourse analysis as a single entity is difficult to define because it is indeed not a singular “thing.” Porter sidesteps the question of “what is discourse analysis” by suggesting that is it not a thing but things, in two senses: 1) there are a multiplicity of forms or schools of thought that differ in their definitions of what discourse analysis is, and 2) every one of those definitions of “discourse analysis” is a collection of various methods/approaches/tools, “things” that make up that particular definition.⁶² Porter identifies four major types of discourse analysis, each based on a formally defined approach associated with a school/region/researcher(s). He then adds a fifth “eclectic” category, which is a collection of those researchers who do not subscribe to any of the previously identified schools and take an “a la carte” approach to tool/method selection in their work. I am, rightly or wrongly, part of this final group. I did not

⁶² Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 216.

train under any of the other four systems, nor did I study any of them to adopt as my own. Thus I will describe the elements of my own approach, continuing to use Porter as a conversation partner.

2.1. Levels of Exegesis

In discussing a multidisciplinary approach to exegesis, Porter proposes a three-level system of categorizing the various elements of exegesis based on what “context” they address: textual context, which Porter labels the “discourse level”; “context of situation,” which is extratextual but indicated by the “linguistic features of the text”; and “context of culture,” the wider “cultural system that defines the parameters in which such a discourse can potentially occur.⁶³” Porter views these three levels hierarchically, from broadest (context of culture) to narrowest (discourse level). Porter discusses the “movement of exegesis” between these levels:

Exegesis typically moves out of the relatively explicit environment of specific texts, through reconstructions of their immediate situations, and eventually toward a description of the relatively implicit categories that define a culture. This movement usually is found within elementary books on exegesis. The actual interpretive process is, of course, much more complex. Even if, especially with ancient languages but also with contemporary language usage, we begin with expression, there is a complex reciprocal interstratal movement between specific instances of language (expressed by means of the lexicogrammar) and their meanings in their context of situation and more generalized understandings of their content and context of culture.⁶⁴

Porter places textual criticism, language analysis, and discourse analysis within the discourse level. In my exegesis of Romans, I indeed work between these levels as suggested, but I focus my attention, as well as give precedence to, the discourse level as defined here. Porter tends to agree:

One of the hallmarks of modern linguistic analysis is that elements of a language are not

⁶³ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 162-163. Porter acknowledges in this chapter that these terms are borrowed from systemic functional linguistics (SFL) as devised by Halliday.

⁶⁴ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 163.

studied in isolation, but must be seen in their larger linguistic and nonlinguistic contexts. Discourse analysis argues that the appropriate context is the discourse. With this larger context established, the interpretation of the individual elements can then take place.⁶⁵

Whether you ascribe to a linear movement between the levels or the more complex “interstatal” movement described above, I believe that others have prioritized context of culture in their exegesis, at times to the exclusion of a comprehensive exegesis at the discourse level. I address this approach and its implications below in “Limits of Historical Analysis.”

2.2. SFL, Register, and Metafunctions

Porter has been a strong proponent and popularizer of the use of systemic functional linguistics (SFL) in the study of New Testament Greek.⁶⁶ As I have mentioned, I am not at this point conversant in any of the “discourse analysis” schools; however, I find that my approach to exegesis fits within the framework described in SFL, particularly the concepts of register and the various metafunctions of a text.

The concept of register has already been touched upon above in the discussion of context of culture and context of situation. The register of a text refers to several different elements, briefly described by Porter:

In Halliday’s work, the concept of register attempts to describe how the components of the context of situation correlate with the variety of language being used. Halliday differentiates three components of the context of situation: field, tenor, and mode. Field is concerned with the subject of a discourse, tenor with its participants, and mode with its medium and other organizing principles.⁶⁷

These categories provide helpful ways of thinking about a text and the social factors that shape it. In this thesis, I focus primarily on tenor, seeking to understand Paul’s argument more clearly

⁶⁵ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 150-151.

⁶⁶ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 201.

⁶⁷ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 199.

by identifying the most likely participants in the debate based on a closer reading of the available group markers used. Even so, the field of Romans, i.e., the subject of Paul’s discourse, overlaps with the tenor, since the subject, by my estimation, is more appropriately described as a who (and thus a “participant” in the dialogue, per se, albeit an indirect one) rather than a what. Paul is not arguing about justification/righteousness, faith, and salvation as abstract concepts; he is arguing on behalf of a group of people, whose status is impacted by these different concepts.

Halliday provides another way of considering the effects of register by defining several different “metafunctions” of a text. Porter describes these “larger structures” that are the targets of discourse analysis:

These include patterns that make a text a cohesive discourse (the so-called textual metafunction): lexical choice and participant choice that indicate the topic of a discourse (the so-called ideational metafunction), and the social factors embedded in the discourse, especially regarding participants (the so-called interpersonal metafunction).⁶⁸

These metafunctions map onto the components of register:

Field is related to Halliday’s ideational metafunction, including the transitivity network, which describes who does what to whom in what way and when, as well as to certain lexical choices. Tenor is related to interpersonal metafunction, including participant structure as well as mood/modality (or Greek attitude). Mode is related to textual metafunction, such as differences in the expression of discourse (i.e., writing versus speech, etc.) and also to textual properties such as cohesion.⁶⁹

These ways of decomposing the discourse functions found within a text have been helpful in categorizing the different exegetical moves I have made in Romans. They not only provide a new vocabulary for discussing my exegetical proposal, but also give structure to my investigations, which I surmise have the potential to lead to further discoveries.

⁶⁸ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 167-168.

⁶⁹ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 199-200.

2.3. Neither Bottom-Up nor Top-Down

Porter describes and contrasts the “bottom-up” and “top-down” approaches to discourse analysis, citing problems with each.⁷⁰ A bottom-up model focuses on smaller structures (words) and builds from the lowest level to higher levels of organization, while a top-down model focuses on larger structures (think paragraph, pericope, or even an entire text), then works down to the small functions of language in order to determine meaning. One challenge for both of these approaches is that neither one accounts for the temporal nature of a text. In a bottom-up approach, word studies that look at frequency and distribution of concepts within a text are atemporal, ignoring the linear and sequential nature of the occurrences of those words and concepts. Likewise, a top-down approach, in search of “superstructures” often driven by ancient rhetorical handbooks, makes the same mistake. Even though a top-down approach might have the appearance of attending to the sequential aspects of a text by identifying the boundaries of the classical rhetorical categories (narratio, propositio, partitio, etc.), which follow a structured order, this method still views the text statically, ignoring the linear nature of discourse. Each section, though connected to what comes before and after, is analyzed as a discrete element, abstracted from the rest.

As someone who has memorized the entire text of Romans and performs the letter from start to finish, my approach to discourse analysis, in contrast to a bottom-up or top-down model, has been linear by default. Among the many benefits of engaging with Romans in this way, I note two things that happen: first, experiencing the text in this manner removes the artificial barriers of chapter and verse, as well as paragraph and pericope, that often work against an objective approach to the text (even sentence structure is loosened, as you consider meaning at

⁷⁰ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 219-221.

the clausal level); and second, meaning becomes not only sequential, but also accumulative, and sequentially so - our understanding of the text grows moment by moment, in a very specific, unalterable way because a text as originally written is designed to be experienced in a linear fashion. This does not mean that there is not value in considering a text in either a bottom-up or top-down mode - both approaches can bring insight to the relationship of smaller linguistic structures to larger superstructures of organization and vice versa. However, my approach treats these tools as secondary to a sequential/accumulative approach. Some might try to suggest that this model is just a variation of a bottom-up approach since it seems to be concerned initially with the smaller structures of language (word, phrase, clause); however, I am not focused on applying a static structure to text in blocks of content of ever-increasing size. My goal is to understand the author's overall arguments through the sequential accumulation of information, which alters the status of those arguments along the way, until a final disposition of all arguments is reached at the end of the text. Rather than "bottom-up" or "top-down," I tentatively refer to this model as a "start-to-finish" approach. Time will tell if this label sticks.

2.4. Logic First

One by-product of experiencing Romans "start-to-finish," accumulating information and hearing a debate unfold in real time, is that many traditional understandings of passages are brought into question. You begin to realize several possibilities:

- Some sequential phrases presented as supporting one another are in fact contradictory
- Some verses presented as starting a new section are inextricably linked to the previous verse/section
- When examining the original Greek, translators have at times opted for a "lazy translation" in order to harmonize a verse/section with a preconceived tradition/doctrine

I initially discovered these kinds of discrepancies one by one in my ongoing exegesis of the

letter. Only later in my study did this evolve into a hermeneutic of sorts that I attempted to apply to my work with every passage of Romans. I have called this process by several different names over time, but I currently call this a “logic first” approach. I imagine that every exegete would agree that attending to the logic of a clause, both in isolation and with respect to its surrounding clauses, is important to the task of interpretation, and each investigator would most likely state that they indeed do this in their own work. However, in practice, logic tends to take a backseat, either to tradition and extratextual historical reconstructions on the one hand, or to grammatical or rhetorical structures on the other, resulting in the loss of the objective meaning of clauses and their syllogistic impact on a segment. A “logic first” approach is a step up from grammatical analysis, on which logic indeed depends; however, this approach forces you to deal with the logical propositions in each clause and connect them with what goes before and comes after. Only then would other methods - historical, traditional, rhetorical - be brought in to flesh out the story being told in the text proper. This type of analysis, which lays bare the contradictory nature of certain sequential clauses throughout Romans, walks you inevitably down a path of considering the dialogical structure of the letter.

2.5. The Dialogical Structure of Romans

There has been much written about the apparent contradictions in Paul’s argument in Romans. In some cases, scholars will solve a contradiction by attributing the contrary phrase to an “interlocutor,” perhaps a real person or an amalgamation of several people, suggesting that Paul is repeating an objection from such an interlocutor in order to respond to it. This is well and good; however, there continue to be debates over particular passages where this method has been used. Much of the disagreement revolves around whether there are appropriate discourse markers in the text that signal a change in speaker. If not, then, some scholars say, the passage cannot be

read in this way and must be attributed to Paul. In most cases, then, tradition holds sway, and some contradictions are “resolved” by redefining words or even the meaning of whole passages in an attempt to harmonize the troublesome text in accordance with a preconceived systematic theology. Many of these such readings are so embedded in our collective understanding of certain texts that most people do not think twice about the apparent discrepancies. This approach plays havoc with the overall exegesis of a text like Romans and masks the author’s original message.

Limiting the identification of “other voices” in Paul’s writings to a somewhat arbitrary list of discourse markers ignores the logic of a clause or sentence, which I contend is the strongest of discourse markers. If one clause argues for a particular position, and the following clause argues for a different position, even if only changing the logic slightly, it should be considered a different voice in some sense. A significant problem with the discourse marker debate is that a lot of scholarly energy has been spent on particular passages determining the difference between whether Paul is speaking rhetorically (asking a leading question or making a contrary statement in the form of a Socratic debate) or if he is using prosopopoeia (speech in character), thus mimicking an absent or imagined interlocutor.⁷¹ While this distinction is not without value, it should be of secondary concern compared to the structure of the overall argument being made and how the contrary statement contributes to the ongoing debate. In an effort to avoid this “red herring” - spending time labeling a passage as a rhetorical statement from Paul versus a segment of “speech in character” - I propose treating all contrary statements as simply counter arguments, regardless of who is imagined as speaking them. This “for the sake

⁷¹ For an in-depth discussion of the challenges with diatribe and prosopopoeia in Romans, see Douglas A. Campbell, *The Deliverance of God: an Apocalyptic Rereading of Justification in Paul* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2009, Kindle Edition), 809-826.

of argument” approach has a freeing effect: by ignoring the question of when an interlocutor might be speaking and thus removing this consideration from your exegetical equation, you are released to then consider all counter arguments as “ideational interlocutors,” each statement carrying on a dialog with the ideas before and after it. This change in dealing with contrary statements has a significant positive impact on my performance of Romans, and vice versa.

2.6. Excursus: Performance as Exegesis

We know that translating a text from an original language to a new target language involves interpretation. No two languages are so synchronized in lexicon, grammar, and semantics that you can just translate each word in order and expect to get a coherent text in the new language.

However, interpretation does not end there. In fact, any time you engage with a text that was composed in your native tongue, you must still interpret the words and make sense of them. This is equally true whether you are reading for yourself or reading to others. This phenomenon is more acute when a text is verbalized for others to hear. There is a marvelous example of verbal interpretation in a BBC video clip from 2016 where Paapa Essiedu, the actor playing the role of Hamlet at the time for the Royal Shakespeare Company, receives unsolicited advice from a host of British actors, most who have also played the role of Hamlet before. After Essiedu recites the first line of Hamlet’s most famous soliloquy, “To be or not to be, that is the question,” the other actors emerge one by one from the wings to give Essiedu advice on how to deliver the line, each one stressing a different word and thus changing the meaning of the sentence (the punch line is when then Prince Charles arrives to deliver the final version, at which point all the other actors, previously contending for their own version, realize that the Prince’s version is, of course, the correct one). This skit beautifully demonstrates how interpretation occurs even in the simple act of speaking the words on the page.

When I first endeavored to memorize Romans, I was less aware of the concept of verbal interpretation. I had been listening to an audio recording of the letter for years and realize now that I tacitly treated it as an “audio text” - simply a verbalization of the words on the page, nothing more. In fact, I had selected a version that had not been “dramatized” - single narrator, no background music, no sound effects - so that I could stay “true” to the text. Once I began performing the letter, however, my view changed. I immediately understood that verbalizing a text that had already been translated and thus interpreted still required me to make interpretive decisions in my delivery. Even as I rehearsed on my own with no audience, I discovered that I could not avoid “embodying” the words: I needed to look toward the different groups that Paul was addressing; I needed to gesture in ways that mirrored or complemented the words coming out of my mouth; I needed to change my facial (and body) expressions to match the different emotions that Paul was trying to communicate to his original audience. I was interpreting the words in my body.⁷² Through this process, I began to see new information in the text that was always there but that I was unaware of before.

As I continued to practice, at times reciting the entire text of Romans start to finish in one sitting, another thing happened: my oral and bodily interpretation of the letter did not always match what I had been taught about certain passages. My delivery might reveal a logical non sequitur that previously was viewed as a smooth flow of thought. Conversely, sequential sections of the letter that traditionally were presented as distinct and separate arguments flowed together when delivered audibly. Sometimes these discrepancies led me to change my performance. Other times, when I was convinced that my performance was an accurate reflection of the words on the

⁷² Sarah Agnew is a scholar who also performed Paul’s letter to the Romans and wrote her dissertation about her experience, which she then published as *Embodied Performance: Mutuality, Embrace, and the Letter to Rome* (Eugene, OR: Pickwick Publications, 2020). Ms. Agnew has some great insights, but our focuses are significantly different, therefore I do not interact with her thesis much in this paper.

page, I investigated the translation I was using and the underlying original Greek for answers explaining the dissonance. These efforts have often disclosed a collective “lazy exegesis” of certain verses on the part of translators, which then have been perpetuated across most modern versions of the New Testament.

Even as I began performing Romans for audiences, this process of discovering meaning in the text through embodiment continued, and I refined my delivery after each performance. In fact, this discovery process was heightened exponentially with the presence of an audience: communicating with real people receiving feedback from them has the power to immediately confirm or refute some of your interpretive choices.

At the same time, I found that just as performance is a capable (and greatly overlooked) tool for exegesis, it is also an effective way to communicate my interpretation to others. In a sense, biblical performance has become its own “hermeneutic circle” for me, my interpretation informing and being informed by each performance of the letter. As my understanding of Romans has changed, my performance has evolved, which in turn opens up the possibility of new insights that were not possible before, or at least not as likely. An example of this synergy is the addition of interlocutors to my performance. By adding other “cast members” to the play to speak the parts I thought might be written as “speech in character” by Paul, I gradually came to the conclusion outlined above, that the logic of a clause was most important in determining if it represented another voice (real or ideational), not the presence or absence of discourse markers or whether a passage was an example of prosopopoeia. And so, now that I had interlocutors in the play, I could assign other lines to them that would be more impactful for the audience coming from the mouth of a physical opponent, whereas before in the mouth of Paul they might have missed the nuances of the counterpoint being made.

To conclude this excursus, I note that the phrase “performance as exegesis” has taken on a double meaning: performance is both an exegetical tool for discovering meaning, and a tool for communicating exegetical decisions in the most direct way. Lastly, biblical performance as I have practiced it, focused on performing the whole letter with the goal of understanding the letter as a whole, is a form and method of discourse analysis.

3. Audience Considerations

I present here briefly several topics that could be categorized differently, but I have lumped together because they are integral to the discussion of the audience of Romans.

3.1. Deconflating Group Markers

I have chosen to evaluate individually on its own merits each group marker used by Paul in Romans. As suggested in chapter 2, there is a host of presuppositions that scholars bring to the study of Romans that are not dictated by the text of the letter itself:

- Terms like “brother,” “holy one,” and “chosen one” are treated as universal markers referring to all believers, with no consideration for their ethnic character and use in the covenant community of Israel
- The terms “Jew” and “Israel” are treated as synonymous, though they have been shown to be distinct by Staples (with other scholars in agreement)
- The terms “Gentile” and “Greek” are treated as synonymous, with no explanation of Paul’s word selection at different points in the letter

By starting my exegesis without these presuppositions, I make a clean run at understanding and defining each term contextually based on Paul’s use of the term in the flow of his argument.

There are two notable driving forces at work as I study Romans that have led to this approach, both tied to the strength of Paul’s argument: the logical structure of the letter body; and Paul’s demonstrated method of word selection throughout the letter. First, the logical structure, when

followed using the “start to finish” method mentioned above, limits the definition of certain terms, actually removing from consideration some options (often those held by the majority opinion) and pointing to other options. Second, Paul’s intellect and demonstrated expertise as a rhetor suggest that his word choices are not based on creating “flowery language” but rather are selected to communicate a specific point within his argument. Here I offer a micro thought experiment: Why would the man who uses the word δικαιοσύνη multiple times in the same letter to signify as many as five different concepts, then turn around and use ἔθνος and Ἕλληνας as synonyms within the same letter with no apparent purpose? I assert that he would not, and that we should be looking for what those differences are. As Runge points out in a discussion of the foundational elements of discourse grammar, “choice implies meaning.”⁷³

3.2. The Limits of Historical Criticism

Porter has this to say about the “context of culture,” the third level of exegesis mentioned above that includes considering the cultural/historical background of a text:

The study of backgrounds, whether Greco-Roman or Jewish, is of primary importance for exegesis.³³ After all, knowledge of the world in which the New Testament developed is much of what the context of culture consists, including not only genre but also other literary, religious, and historical realities. Despite what some scholars seem to imply, however, this does not mean that we can equate background knowledge with exegesis. The study of background data allows us to theorize the possible textual worlds relevant to a context of culture, but in the end each text instantiates a specific situational configuration, and it is in relation to this configuration that the text must be interpreted.⁷⁴

Contrary to this sentiment from Porter, exegetes often start with historical background and bring it to the text as a controlling interpretive paradigm. Two related instances are Paul’s status as “apostle to the Gentiles” and the historical Edict of Claudius, which reportedly mandated the

⁷³ Steven E. Runge, *Discourse Grammar of the Greek New Testament* (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson Publishers, 2010), 5.

⁷⁴ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 178.

expulsion of Jews from Rome for a period of time.⁷⁵ While the phrase “apostle to Gentiles/Nations” is indeed found in the NT, even in Romans itself, there is plenty of evidence, from the Pauline corpus and from Acts, that indicates Paul worked with the people of Israel extensively throughout his missionary career. And yet, when scholars approach Romans, they presuppose that Paul’s primary if not sole focus is on converting Gentiles, completely discounting any evidence to the contrary, creating a false dichotomy. Along with this bias, some scholars will see the Edict of Claudius as proof that, at the time of the writing of Romans, the majority of believers in Rome were Gentiles and thus, they rationalize, the target audience of Paul.

I have included this discussion here (as opposed to the section above on discourse analysis) because this line of thinking is most often used in Romans to dictate the identity of Paul’s audience with little or no corroboration with the actual text of the letter. As Porter indicates in the quote above, this approach to the exegesis of Romans is wrong-headed and ignores the basic linguistic content of the letter. Allow me to demonstrate the weakness in this approach with another thought experiment. Even though the effects of the Edict of Claudius on the Jewish population of Rome have been challenged by scholars, let us assume for the sake of argument that the church in Rome at the time of the writing of Romans was overwhelmingly Gentile, with only a handful of Jews participating in the Jesus movement. Now, imagine yourself in a similar situation: you are writing a letter to Christian brothers and sisters in another city; you are the member of a small denomination, which happens to be outnumbered by the largest denomination in the city by 100 to 1. Does the size of the other denomination dictate who you are writing your letter to? Absolutely not. Presumably you are communicating with people you

⁷⁵ Acts 18:2.

either know or are in association with, and you are writing about a specific topic involving those particular people. You might suggest that this analogy breaks down because Paul was in association with both Jews and Gentiles in Rome. Allow me to adjust the scenario. You are a member of a multi-ethnic megachurch in a large city. There are three large ethnic groups represented within the membership; one group makes up half the church, while the other two each make up about 25% of the church body. You are writing a letter to the church to address an issue of unity between the groups, caused by a particular theological position taken by one of the groups. Do you assume that the group behaving badly is the largest of the three groups, solely because they have the most people? Of course not; such an assumption would be absurd.

Likewise, the arguments for a Gentile audience in Romans based on a historical reconstruction of the events surrounding the Edict of Claudius are equally absurd. The logical content of the text must take precedence, analyzed from the three metafunctions: textual, ideational, and interpersonal. Even so, because of the ambiguity that exists in the group markers used in Romans, it is a challenge to not only determine who the primary audience is at any given moment, but also to go against the received interpretation of the majority. To help in this specific task, I have recruited a thought tool from the field of mathematics - fuzzy logic.

3.3. A “Fuzzy Logic” Approach to Audience Reception

One of the ongoing challenges within Pauline scholarship and particularly research on Romans is the debate on what groups are represented in Paul’s audience, both the audience writ large as well as those specific groups that were the intended recipients of the letter. This choice is usually couched as an either/or decision, as well as in an all-or-nothing manner: even when scholars acquiesce to the fact that the audience in Rome almost certainly contained both Jews and Gentiles, they insist that Paul wrote Romans in its entirety either to Gentiles or to Jews, with no

overlap. I surmise one reason this continues to be a point of debate is because the content of the letter, albeit read in piecemeal fashion and as an abstract collection of propositions, has the appearance of universal appeal. The idea of selecting a specific group as Paul's intended audience is diametrically opposed to the view that Romans is a message meant for all. I suggest that a balance might be achieved, at least temporarily as part of one's investigation, by considering the strength of the reactions by each distinct group within the audience as we imagine them listening to each part of the debate laid out by Paul. By accepting the sum of all reactions as valid, we avoid the either/or dichotomy, while simultaneously being able to see which group is most affected at each stage of the argument.

This approach is akin to a form of "approximate reasoning" developed for use initially in electronics applications called "fuzzy logic." The concept of "fuzzy sets" was first proposed by Zadeh in a 1965 paper.⁷⁶ It was from this origin that fuzzy logic came into being. Zadeh explains:

Perhaps the simplest way of characterizing fuzzy logic is to say that it is a logic of approximate reasoning. As such, it is a logic whose distinguishing features are (i) fuzzy truth-values expressed in linguistic terms, e.g., true, very true, more or less true, rather true, not true, false, not very true and not very false, etc.; (ii) imprecise truth tables; and (iii) rules of inference whose validity is approximate rather than exact.⁷⁷

By allowing two or more statements to be true, i.e., both Jews and Gentiles can be Paul's audience members in Romans, we avoid a false dichotomy that insists that we select one over the other. However, by assigning a relative value to each group's *reaction* to specific elements within the argument, we can compare different group reactions and make informed decisions as to which group might be the intended audience at any given point in the letter. More significantly

⁷⁶ L. A. Zadeh, "Fuzzy Sets," *Information and Control*, 8 (1965), 338-365.

⁷⁷ Lotfi A Zadeh, Rafik Aziz Aliev, *Fuzzy Logic Theory And Applications: Part I And Part II* (Hackensack, NJ: World Scientific Publishing Company, 2018, Kindle Edition).

for the purposes of this study, I have applied this logic to each group's reaction to the use of specific group markers, like ἀδελφοί and ἅγιοι, to suggest that labels such as these may not have been viewed as universal markers at the time of the letter's composition.

4. Other Considerations

4.1. Theological Interpretation of Scripture (TIS)

As a believer, I wholeheartedly support a theological interpretation of Scripture, as opposed to the modernist alternative that strips any thought of God out of our exegesis. As Porter states:

There are a number of scholars who wish to argue that, in the light of developments in postmodernism, interpretation of the Bible should be seen as an intracommunity activity: it is the believing community that appropriates the legacy of interpreting the Bible. This approach to interpretation is to be commended, as it has made a significant effort in reclaiming the Bible from the secular academy and restoring its place as the unique possession of the church.⁷⁸

However, this stance is not only appropriate for believers but also for any honest historian dealing with ancient theological texts, whether Christian or otherwise. This choice is simply a matter of reading a community's writings in context.

Even so, there are some caveats, particularly within the Christian faith community, when invoking TIS as a method, as Porter warns:

Not all is so optimistic, however, since theological interpretation has major limitations: (1) it draws selectively from a great diversity of opinion, while simultaneously asserting the primacy of its interpretations; (2) it often (at least in some of its manifestations) tries to recognize the results of historical criticism while simultaneously invoking interpretations that are precritical or premodern in their origins; (3) theological interpreters tend to view their method as exegesis rather than as the arbitration between interpretive options that it really is; (4) in at least some forms, it is predicated upon a postmodern stance and hence relies upon the church for its limited authoritative basis.⁷⁹

⁷⁸ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 179.

⁷⁹ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 179.

In my own approach to exegesis, I try to keep these caveats in mind, with specific attention to the first: as I investigate any first century text, I want to give weight to the theological dimensions of the arguments put forth by the author, while at the same time being keenly aware of modern theological interpretations that are not necessarily in line with or even remotely related to what the author is communicating to his first century audience. As N. T. Wright likes to say, “we need twenty-first-century answers to first-century questions, not nineteenth-century answers to sixteenth-century questions.”⁸⁰

4.2. Paul Within Judaism

New Testament scholarship concerned with Pauline “theology” has undergone a number of shifts in “perspectives” over the past century, from what has been referred to as a “Lutheran” perspective coming out of the Reformation and focused on “justification by faith,” to the “New Perspective on Paul” (NPP) tied to the work of E. P. Sanders, N. T. Wright, James D. G. Dunn, and others, to others in a “post NPP” camp, and most recently into the “Paul within Judaism” phase, led by scholars like Nanos, Fredriksen, and a host of others. For each perspective and each scholar who is purportedly a part of a particular perspective “school,” there are qualifications to how closely they adhere to a list of the key distinctives defining that school.

I am writing in a time when the Paul within Judaism school is in ascendancy, and much of the literature that I have consumed in preparation for this thesis comes from scholars firmly within this school or overlapping with it. Here is a synopsis of this perspective:

Foremost, beyond the commitment to the quest to understand the historical Paul already noted, letting the theological chips fall where they may, if you will, the research is undertaken with the assumption that the writing and community building of the apostle Paul took place within late Second Temple Judaism, within which he remained a

⁸⁰ N. T. Wright, *Paul and the Faithfulness of God: Two Book Set (Christian Origins and the Question of God 4)* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2013, Kindle Edition), 1307.

representative after his change of conviction about Jesus being the Messiah (Christ). This also means that the “assemblies” that he founded, and to which he wrote the letters that still provide the major basis for this research (including the letter to Rome, although a community that he did not found), were also developing their (sub)culture based upon their convictions about the meaning of Jesus for non-Jews as well as for Jews within Judaism.⁸¹

I personally do not link myself with any particular school in this regard; that said, I resonate with the view put forth above by Nanos. However, I do not think it goes far enough in reclaiming Paul’s heritage. Paul within Judaism is a corrective, but it essentializes Judaism within the broader Israelite ethnicity of which Paul is a member. This omission continues to turn a blind eye on this aspect of God’s covenant with Israel. Jason Staples, speaking in a recent seminar on “within Judaism,” made this comment:

The Samaritans should be our first indication that the within Judaism perspective does have some significant limitations as a historical framework; Judaism and Jewishness artificially limits the scope when talking about Yahwists from the Second Temple Period and those claiming Israelite status even before the development of Christianity.⁸²

It is telling that within the Pauline corpus Paul never refers to himself individually as a Jew, but on a couple occasions he does state, “I am an Israelite” (Rom 11:1; 2 Cor 11:22).⁸³ For these reasons, my personal hermeneutic in this respect is to think of “Paul the Israelite” as I seek to understand the arguments that Paul puts forth in Romans. Of course, it is the text of Romans itself that has overwhelmingly led me to this view of Paul. The hermeneutic circle is alive and well.

⁸¹ Mark D. Nanos and Magnus Zetterholm, eds., *Paul within Judaism: Restoring the First-Century Context to the Apostle* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2018, Kindle Edition), 9.

⁸² Jason A. Staples, presenting during Enoch Seminar, “The ‘Within Judaism’ Perspective,” 1/7/2025, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cOZEa64jGZ4&t=21376s>

⁸³ The only times we hear the words, “I am a Jew” coming from Paul’s lips is in Acts (21:39, 22:3).

Chapter 4 – Analysis

1. The Structure of this Chapter

The focus of my analysis is to convince the reader of the plausibility of three key assertions concerning Romans: 1) that Paul distinguishes between Jews and non-Jewish Israelites, referring to non-Jewish Israelites as “Greeks,” and connecting them with the former Northern Kingdom of Israel through OT citations; 2) that Jews are Paul’s “target” audience throughout the letter (notwithstanding a short aside in chapter 11 to Gentile hearers in the audience); and 3) that non-Jewish Israelites are the primary object of the debate that Paul is arguing. To this end, I have structured this analysis in five distinct but intertwined sections. In the first two sections, I conduct some “ground clearing” of the traditional views. “Paul the Letter Writer” looks at Paul’s own ethnicity and examines the impact of the phrase “apostle of the Gentiles” on exegesis. In “Paul’s Audience – a First Look,” I take a similar approach to examining the question of Paul’s audience in Romans, which in current scholarship is widely assumed to be Gentile. In the next two sections, I make the case for deconflating the four primary ethnic group markers in Romans. “Ethnic Group Markers in Old Testament Quotations” explores chapter 9 through 11, highlighting those verses with references to Israel and examining the context of the OT citations concerning the former Northern Kingdom. “Jew and Greek – Intra-Israelite Group Markers in Romans” presents data and arguments from various texts to support my claim that Paul uses “Greek” in Romans as a group marker to identify non-Jewish Israelites, primarily those associated with the tribes of the former Northern Kingdom of Israel. In the final section, “Synthesis,” I incorporate the items discussed in the previous analysis sections into a brief walkthrough of Romans 1-11, showing how these shifts in understanding make sense of Paul’s

argument as a whole, further strengthening the plausibility of this alternate reading.

2. Paul the Letter Writer

As we begin our discussion of how an accurate understanding of ethnicity informs our exegesis of Romans, we must start with the author of the letter, Paul. Much has been written on the New Testament letters as letters. My intent is not to revisit this material, but rather to highlight Paul as the author of Romans and explore how his own ethnicity and cultural location impacts our understanding of the rhetoric of this letter.

Scholars are unanimous on attributing the authorship of Romans to Paul of Tarsus, the same identified in the Acts of the Apostles. While there are likely others involved in the process of producing the letter,⁸⁴ we will be focusing on Paul as the singular authorial voice, and thus looking at how his ethnic background affects the rhetoric of Romans.⁸⁵

2.1. The Ethnicity of Paul

The majority of what we know about the apostle Paul, including his ethnicity, is found in the New Testament, both in the letters of the Pauline corpus and in Acts. He is traditionally portrayed as a Jew⁸⁶ and a member of the Pharisees, community activists that were part of a

⁸⁴ Some of Paul's letters specifically name other authors; in Romans, an amanuensis, Tertius, is named in chapter 16.

⁸⁵ Porter, *Linguistic Analysis*, 162. With respect to "authorial intention," I am in synch with Porter: "At the outset of this discussion, let me state that I believe there are such things as authorial intentions, though I am skeptical of being able to recover them in any immediate way (and certainly I do not believe that we can recover psychological motivations). From the perspective of the exegete, however, these intentions are recoverable only to the extent that they are embedded within the linguistic expression of a text.⁹ Moreover, authorial intentions are rarely embedded explicitly, but more often are discernable only insofar as a text can be positioned with reference to the typical communicative situations that are characteristic of a particular culture. In other words, from the perspective of the exegete, posited authorial intentions are extrapolations made on the basis of contextually interpreted linguistic evidence."

⁸⁶ Acts 21:39; Acts 23:6.

conservative “renewal movement”.⁸⁷ After his Damascus Road encounter with Jesus Christ, he is referred to as the “apostle to the Gentiles.”⁸⁸ While this designation is not itself an ethnic marker, its use and proper understanding has ramifications for how Paul’s ethnicity affects the exegesis of Romans, and this phrase will be explored below.

Even though Romans does not contradict the traditional model of Paul’s ethnicity outlined above, Paul does offer a different view of himself in the letter, both directly and indirectly, a view which informs the new approach to understanding Romans that I am proposing.

2.2. Paul’s Ethnic Self-Identification in Romans

Paul’s ethnicity is on display in the very first verses of the letter. As an “apostle appointed to the gospel of God,” he is identified as a commissioner of the God of Israel in verse 1. If there is any doubt about this specificity, verse 2 ties the “gospel” to “his [God’s] prophets” and the “holy Scriptures,” clear references to the Jewish prophets and their writings found in the Tanakh (the Torah, the prophets, and the writings). Even before this designation, the third word of the letter, Χριστοῦ (the genitive form of Χριστός), is the first explicit indication of Paul’s identification as a member of the people of Israel. Χριστός, the Greek rendering of the Hebrew מָשִׁיחַ, “anointed (one),” marks Jesus as the “anointed one” of the Jews. This is more than the anointing of a priest, as can be seen in verses 3 and 4: Jesus is the genealogical descendant of King David and his successor in the Davidic line of kings, and Paul is his “servant” (v.1).

When we turn to look for evidence in Romans of the received understanding of Paul as a Jew and a Pharisee, we find none. In fact, as we expand our search to the entire Pauline corpus,

⁸⁷ N. T. Wright and Michael F. Bird, *The New Testament in its World* (Minneapolis: Zondervan Academic, 2019), 117, 126.

⁸⁸ Acts 9:15; Rom 11:13.

there is only one reference to each of these designators: Paul includes himself in “we Jews” in Gal 2:15; and he refers to himself as a “Pharisee” in Phil 3:5.⁸⁹ So how does Paul identify himself ethnically in Romans? He does it in three distinct but related ways: 1) as a descendant of Abraham; 2) as an Israelite; and 3) as a member of the tribe of Benjamin. Let us examine each of these terms in turn, finishing with a discussion of Rom 11:1, where all three markers come together.

Abraham: Paul first refers to Abraham in Rom chapter 4. In three verses in this chapter (vv. 1, 12, 16), Paul makes indirect references to Paul’s own belonging within the Abrahamic family: in v. 1, he uses the phrase Ἀβραάμ τὸν προπάτορα ἡμῶν, often translated “Abraham our forefather”; in v. 12 he uses the phrase πίστεως τοῦ πατρὸς ἡμῶν Ἀβραάμ, “faith of our father Abraham”; and in v. 16 he refers to Abraham appositively as the one “who is the father of us all” (ὃς ἐστὶν πατὴρ πάντων ἡμῶν). The majority of scholars interpret these statements spiritually, thus allowing them to interpret them universally, as applying to all people everywhere, including Gentiles. However, I will show through my exegesis below that this is not the only option and that these statements can be understood as explicitly implying genealogical descent from Abraham.

Israelite: The name Ἰσραήλ occurs 11 times in Romans;⁹⁰ in none of these uses does Paul tie himself directly to the name. However, the word Ἰσραηλίτης occurs twice, and both times are connected to Paul. The first instance is in Rom 9:4, where Paul uses it in the plural in apposition to “my brothers, my kinsmen according to the flesh” (τῶν ἀδελφῶν μου τῶν

⁸⁹ In Gal 1:13-14, Paul talks of his “former life in Judaism”; we must look to Acts for Paul’s more explicit statement, “I am a Jew” (Acts 21:39, 22:3), words put in his mouth by the author of Acts. Similarly, Paul is recorded as stating that he is a Pharisee in Acts 23:6 and 26:5.

⁹⁰ A search of several modern translations (NRSV, NIV, ESV, CSB, RSV) will return 12 instances of Israel; in these versions the translators have interpolated “Israel” for “them” in v. 11:11.

συγγενῶν μου κατὰ σάρκα, v. 3). The second occurrence is in Rom 11:1, which we discuss next.

Benjaminite: In Rom 11:1, we have Paul's clearest ethnic self-identification in Romans: "I ask, then, has God rejected his people? By no means! For I myself am an Israelite, a descendant of Abraham, a member of the tribe of Benjamin" (ESV). In declaring himself a descendant of Abraham, Israel, and Benjamin, Paul is doing two things at once: he is associating himself with a larger, more comprehensive group, the people of Israel in toto, by claiming his kinship with Abraham and labeling himself an "Israelite," while also distinguishing himself from the designation "Jew" by highlighting his tribal affiliation of Benjamin rather than that of the Southern Kingdom, Judah (see figure below). Rhetorically, then, we can surmise that this move also accomplishes two things: 1) the use of this familial language demonstrates that Paul was most likely arguing with his Jewish siblings and 2) on behalf of his Israelite (non-Jewish) siblings. The balance of this paper will bear out these two assertions.

Figure 1 Tribes of Israel in the Divided Kingdom

2.3. Apostle of the Gentiles?

While the oft-quoted title for Paul, “Apostle of the Gentiles,” is not an ethnic marker of Paul per se, it is interpreted by most scholars in such a way as to have ramifications for Paul’s own ethnicity. By assuming that Paul has been appointed as the apostle to minister to the Gentiles, i.e., to the ethnic people of the Gentile nations, the unspoken logical conclusion is that he has abandoned his own ethnicity and for all intents and purposes become a Gentile himself. As I shall argue in the rest of this paper, nothing could be further from the truth, and in fact, the opposite is true. For now, however, let us look at two reasons from within the Scriptural text that suggest we broaden our understanding of the phrase “apostle of the Gentiles.” The first comes from Paul’s Damascus Road narrative in Acts chapter 9. In the dialogue between Jesus and Ananias, Jesus reassures Ananias and tells him that Paul is “a chosen instrument of Mine, to bear

My name before the Gentiles and kings and the sons of Israel” (Acts 9:15, NASB). Here we see what is usually left out of most discussions of Paul’s apostleship: that, in the words of Jesus, Paul is called to also preach to the rulers in the nations and *the people of Israel found within those nations*. What is also hidden in this and most other translations is the fact that this list of three focus areas for Paul’s ministry is built on a τε καὶ construction: ἐνώπιον ἐθνῶν τε καὶ βασιλέων υἰῶν τε Ἰσραήλ.⁹¹ An alternate translation that displays the nuance of the original wording is “before not only Gentiles, but also [before] kings and [before] the sons of Israel.” The Greek of this passage puts the emphasis on the final two elements in the list, and one might argue that the strongest emphasis is on the final term, sons of Israel.

The second reason is the record of Paul’s missionary activity as recorded in Acts. Every time Paul entered a new city, his first recorded activity was a visit to the local synagogue to proclaim Jesus as the long-awaited Davidic Messiah. Even if you believe that Paul’s primary mission was to proclaim the gospel to ethnic Gentiles, you cannot discount the weight of this repeated activity and its bearing upon our interpretation of Paul’s letters.

⁹¹ NB: the Textus Receptus omits the first τε from this verse.

Chapter	Verse	Location	English Text
9	20	Damascus	And immediately he proclaimed Jesus in the synagogues, saying, "He is the Son of God."
9	28	Jerusalem	So he went in and out among them at Jerusalem, preaching boldly in the name of the Lord.
11	26	Antioch (Syria)	and when he had found him, he brought him to Antioch. For a whole year they met with the church and taught a great many people. And in Antioch the disciples were first called Christians.
13	5	Salamis (Cyprus)	When they arrived at Salamis, they proclaimed the word of God in the synagogues of the Jews. And they had John to assist them.
13	14	Antioch (Pisidia)	but they went on from Perga and came to Antioch in Pisidia. And on the Sabbath day they went into the synagogue and sat down.
14	1	Iconium	Now at Iconium they entered together into the Jewish synagogue and spoke in such a way that a great number of both Jews and Greeks believed.
17	1	Thessalonica	Now when they had passed through Amphipolis and Apollonia, they came to Thessalonica, where there was a synagogue of the Jews.
17	10	Berea	The brothers[fn] immediately sent Paul and Silas away by night to Berea, and when they arrived they went into the Jewish synagogue.
17	17	Athens	So he reasoned in the synagogue with the Jews and the devout persons, and in the marketplace every day with those who happened to be there.
18	4	Corinth	And he reasoned in the synagogue every Sabbath, and tried to persuade Jews and Greeks.
18	19	Ephesus	And they came to Ephesus, and he left them there, but he himself went into the synagogue and reasoned with the Jews.
28	17	Rome	After three days he called together the local leaders of the Jews, and when they had gathered, he said to them, "Brothers, though I had done nothing against our people or the customs of our fathers, yet I was delivered as a prisoner from Jerusalem into the hands of the Romans.

2.4. Conclusion

In Romans, Paul presents himself as an Israelite rather than a Jew, emphasizing his connection with all of Israel as opposed to just with the Southern Kingdom of Judah. I note this distinction and the other information provided above not with an historical-critical goal in mind but a rhetorical-logical one: how does Paul use his own ethnicity in the service of the argument(s) he builds throughout the letter?

Any interpretation of a text must begin with an understanding of the author, to the extent that knowledge of the author can be determined. However, while I have begun my analysis focusing on the author of the letter, this information is a minor (though integral) part of my overall thesis. Even so, I will show in the synthesis section below how Paul's ethnicity is brought to bear on his argument. Before that, we must discuss the audience of Romans.

3. Paul's Audience - a First Look

When we talk about the “audience” of a text, a differentiation is often made between the explicit audience that the author is objectively addressing in the text and an “encoded” audience - those people who the author is really addressing as indicated by the rhetoric of the text. I agree that this is a reasonable distinction to make; however, I will only discuss the explicit audience in this section and leave the discussion of the encoded audience of Romans for the synthesis section below. I have two reasons for this approach: first, I assert that Paul's explicit references to his audience in Romans have been misinterpreted and need to be attended to; and second, I assert that use of an encoded audience hermeneutic has its own issues that result in circular reasoning and is better addressed once all my own exegetical cards are on the table.

Before we delve into this topic, it is necessary to point out that it is appropriate to say that Paul is addressing more than one audience in Romans, and so it is more accurate to refer to “audiences” as we exegete the letter. In fact, lack of awareness of this detail has contributed to the misinterpretation of the letter down through the ages. While some contemporary scholars assent to this distinction, they do so in a general way and do not apply this understanding to their sentence-level exegesis. In this section, I will argue that Paul is addressing four specific audiences, all subsets of believers: Gentiles (in a different and much more limited way than what most scholars believe); Jews (Paul's rhetorical interlocutors in the letter); Israelites (all ethnic Israel, inclusive of Jews); and all believers in Rome.

The explicit audiences of Romans are marked in three ways, coinciding with the three grammatical persons used by Paul in his argument (first person, second person, and third person points of view). Second person is the most important for our purposes of determining the “who” of Paul's audiences. Second person includes pronouns translated as “you” in the singular or

plural, as well as direct address or appositive statements, which are nouns or predicate adjectives in the vocative form - thus “calling out” the specific groups that Paul is addressing. The bulk of this section on Paul’s audiences will be a study of these direct address noun forms. In the first person, when used in the plural, Paul sometimes will include himself in the audience group he is addressing.⁹² Paul’s use of first person plural pronouns and verb forms is consistent throughout the letter, with the glaring exception of chapter 11; I will discuss this omission in the section on “Gentiles” below. Finally, the use of the third person to refer to Paul’s audience might seem paradoxical, until you remember that Paul is addressing multiple audiences, and so can refer to one audience while talking directly to another. I will explore this dynamic in the synthesis section below.

3.1. “Gentiles”

I am starting my detailed discussion of Paul’s audiences in Romans with the word ἔθνος, translated alternately in Romans and elsewhere in the New Testament as either “Gentile” or “nation.” This word is not the first ethnically-related word in Romans (see section on Paul above), but it is the one that most contemporary scholars identify as the marker for Paul’s primary, if not exclusive, audience. By starting here, I hope to clear away the arguments most often used to support this claim in order to make room for another audience who I believe is the primary audience of Romans: believers descended from the ethnic Israel tribes.

First, let us talk about the word translated as “Gentiles.” The Greek word ἔθνος occurs 27 times in Romans, although the majority of those occurrences is in the plural form (25 of 27). As mentioned, it is alternately translated in the NT as “Gentile/s,” referring specifically to people (from the Latin *gens*, “family/race”), or “nation/s,” referring to a geographic region and perhaps

⁹² Rom 1:12 is an instance of this.

to an anachronistic version of the concept of a nation as we know it today. In Romans, most modern translations favor “Gentiles.” For instance, the ESV translates 21 occurrences as “Gentiles” (all in the plural) and the balance as “nation/s.” Most exegetes will tell you that the decision to choose one translation over the other is based on context. By “context,” however, they mean the historical-critical context that they have constructed, which makes their choice of translation somewhat circular. For example, if I believe, based on factors external to the letter, that Paul wrote Romans to Gentiles, then I will assume that whenever ἔθνος is used he is referring to the people; I will resort to “nation/s” only when I cannot make “Gentile/s” work within the logic of a particular passage. What happens logically, however, when you rely solely on the context provided by the letter itself? I assert that you lose the ability to differentiate between the two ideas of “Gentile” and “nation,” and thus you realize that we have created a false dichotomy within the single word ἔθνος. In Paul’s first century context, people and land are not only intertwined, they are an integrated concept - the people are from a specific place, and that place has a specific people associated with it. Paul, a competent rhetor, uses a single word in Romans for this concept, ἔθνος, and so will I as we continue to discuss this topic. Afterward, I will reveal my preference for the English translation of ἔθνος in Romans. For the purposes of this study, I will focus on three passages in Romans that are typically used to assert that Gentiles are Paul’s primary if not sole audience in the letter: two passages from the letter frame, Rom 1:5-15 and Rom 15:14-16, and one passage from chapter 11, Rom 11:13-15.

3.1.1. *Rom 1:5-15 – “Among the Nations”*

This first example from the frame of the letter actually includes two occurrences of ἔθνος, at Rom 1:5 and 1:13, but we will consider them together because they are inextricably connected through the logical flow of Paul’s exordium. It is this passage that most exegetes will point to

first when arguing for an exclusive Gentile audience for Romans, referring specifically to these two verses - “Paul is obviously writing to Gentiles, he says so in chapter 1!” Let us examine the evidence.

First, we must look at the text of vv. 5 and 6 together, since it is in v. 6 that ἔθνος in v. 5 is tied to a second person reference (the first in the letter) through a pronominal clause:

1:5 δι’ οὗ ἔλάβομεν χάριν καὶ ἀποστολὴν εἰς ὑπακοὴν πίστεως ἐν πᾶσιν τοῖς ἔθνεσιν ὑπὲρ τοῦ ὀνόματος αὐτοῦ
 1:6 ἐν οἷς ἐστε καὶ ὑμεῖς κλητοὶ Ἰησοῦ Χριστοῦ

Cranfield has rightly noted that this passage is ambiguous and can be translated either as a geographic reference, referring to people “in the nations,” or as a reference to the people themselves, and thus referring to a group of people “among” another group of people, “the Gentiles.”⁹³ Many scholars attempt to resolve this ambiguity in favor of the second reading of ἔθνος, “Gentiles,” through a less than accurate translation (what might even be called a paraphrase) of the pronominal phrase in v. 6. Using the NRSV as a representative example, here is a typical English translation of both verses:

5 through whom we have received grace and apostleship to bring about the obedience of faith among all the Gentiles for the sake of his name, 6 *including yourselves* who are called to belong to Jesus Christ... (emphasis added)⁹⁴

This translation and others like it ignore the repetition in v. 6 of the preposition ἐν in v. 5; the effect is that those who use this approach can assume that the group of people designated by the plural “you” of v. 6 are a subset of the group of people identified as “Gentiles” in v. 5, as opposed to a group of people who are “also” (καὶ) located in the geographic nations but not necessarily a subset/related to the people of those nations. I will demonstrate that this second

⁹³ See chapter 2, “Literature Review,” section 2.1, “ἔθνος.”

⁹⁴ See also ESV, CSB, RSV.

understanding is more likely the case, but before I do, let us consider the logical conclusions of the first reading. If correct, Paul would be saying, in effect, “I am called to proclaim the gospel to Gentiles, which you are.” This statement is a tautology and makes no literary or rhetorical sense, especially given Paul’s rhetorical acumen. Even if you add the qualification that he is writing to “those in Rome” found in v. 7, as some scholars do, it does not remove the awkwardness of this rendering: “I am called to proclaim the gospel to Gentiles, and that includes you Romans too!” There is no rhetorical force in either of these options. In addition, when the prepositional phrase in v. 6, ἐν οἷς ἐστε καὶ, is more accurately translated “among whom you also are” (NKJV, NASB), it reveals that reading the plural “you” as a subset of Gentiles within Gentiles is also a tautology with no rhetorical purpose. Some exegetes attempt to strengthen this reading by positing that the intent behind this statement is to assert Paul’s apostolic authority over the Romans even though he did not found the church in Rome. However, while Paul does refer to his apostleship here in chapter 1 and a couple other places in the letter (chapters 11 and 15), there is no hint of the Romans questioning that authority. This notion is imported from elsewhere in the Pauline corpus, notably 2 Corinthians. Here in Romans, understanding this statement as an assertion of Paul’s authority seems heavy-handed, especially at the beginning of the letter, compared to his winsomeness displayed in the rest of the letter frame (which is distinguished from his rhetoric found in the body of the letter). While this reading is feasible, I am not persuaded that it is plausible. I propose a more logical reading - seemingly more complex given the traditional understanding of Romans, but more satisfying in the end, taking into account all aspects of the text, including especially those elements ignored by other interpreters.

For my proposed reading, I start with a translation that is closer to the original Greek and uses “nations” vice “Gentiles”:

5 Through whom we received grace and apostleship to bring about the obedience of faith among all the nations for the sake of his name, 6 among which [nations] you are also, you called ones of Jesus Christ... (author's translation)

This wording is close to other formal equivalent translations, with a few key exceptions. As mentioned, I have opted to translate ἐν πᾶσιν τοῖς ἔθνεσιν “among all the nations,” not to do away with the people aspect, but to highlight the geographic component of ἔθνος. I have added “nations” to v. 6 to clearly show that ἐν οἷς refers to the same in v. 5. Also, in an effort to emphasize the geographic facet of “nations,” I have used “which” instead of “whom” in v. 6⁹⁵.

With this translation in place, which encompasses both the people and geographic facets of ἔθνος, we consider the meaning of v. 6a, “among which [nations] you are also.” Here we find the first direct address to Paul’s audience in ὑμεῖς. This reference is part of a prepositional clause and modifies “among which [nations],” indicating that the audience exists (ἐστε) among the groups of people from the nations or in the geographic regions of those people *in addition to some other group* (καὶ). The “other group” to which the audience is being compared and contrasted is the people of the “nations” referred to in v. 5. By including καὶ, Paul indicates that his audience is distinct from the people of the nations just mentioned. He is also subtly suggesting that his audience, while distinct from the nations, are not only physically among the nations, but also are viewed under the “obedience of faith” discussed in v. 5. Who is this other group that Paul is addressing? We are told in v. 6b: “you called ones of Jesus Christ.” This appositive clause clarifies who the “you” of v. 5 is - I assert that “called ones” is the first of multiple group markers in Romans that refer to the people of Israel, descendants of Jacob. I will unpack this below in the section “Called Ones.” Building on this translation and contextual reading of Rom 1:5-6, we turn our attention to the next “Gentile” reference, Rom 1:13-15.

⁹⁵ I could have just as easily translated ἐν as “in” for both v. 5 and 6 for the same reason, but I wanted to keep the focus on the more crucial changes in my translation.

As mentioned above, ἔθνεσιν (dative plural) in Rom 1:13 is linked to its occurrence in 1:5, not just by repetition but also by the logic of the message Paul is trying to communicate in this section of the letter. Having identified his audience as those faithful Israelites collocated with the nations, the nations that Paul indeed identifies as his primary mission, he now takes his indirect reference to proclaiming the gospel to “called ones” in vv. 5 and 6 and makes it explicit in vv. 13 to 15. Using the same approach that I used in vv. 5 and 6 above, here is my translation of vv. 13 to 15:

However, I do not want you to be unaware, siblings, that often I planned to come to you but was prevented until now so that I might have some fruit even among you, just as I also had among the other nations. I am obligated to proclaim the gospel, both to Greeks and to Barbarians, both to the wise and to the foolish; so, for my part, I am willing also to proclaim it to those of you who are in Rome.

I focus your attention on the use of καὶ, by which I will demonstrate that ἔθνεσιν, translated here as above as “nations,” does not indicate that Paul is talking to “Gentiles,” but rather to the faithful Israelites living among the nations. Starting with v. 13, there are three occurrences of καὶ. The first is the beginning of the parenthetical statement concerning Paul’s delay in coming (rendered “but” in most translations) and does not concern us here. The second and third occurrence are alternately translated “also” and “even” in most translations, as I have above. In Paul’s declaration of his intention to “have fruit even among you,” the “you” is the same “you” of v. 6. Likewise, “fruit” refers to the “obedience of faith” of v. 5. Thus, καὶ here has the same function as καὶ in v. 6, marking out Paul’s audience as a group distinct from the nations that he intends to serve in addition to those nations. The third καὶ in v. 13 occurs in the clause, “just as I also had among the other nations.” This is not a mere repetition of the sentiment communicated by “that I might have some fruit even among you”; by referring to “the other nations,” Paul is connecting this “added work” to the “added work” he has accomplished in other places besides Rome. Paul elucidates this thought in vv. 14 and 15: even though his primary mission is “to

Greeks and Barbarians,” he is “also” (in addition to) willing to proclaim the gospel to “those of you who are in Rome,” his Israelite audience. The “also” in v. 15, the last καὶ we will discuss here, brings together the two καὶs in v. 13, creating a chiasm of thought in these three verses.

Here I paraphrase this section in an ABBA format:

A I want to proclaim the gospel to you, my Israelite siblings,
 B even though you are not my primary mission;
 B my primary mission is to proclaim the gospel to Greeks and Barbarians,
 A but I am willing to proclaim the gospel to you as well, my siblings in Rome.

I have purposely left out of this paraphrase the reference to “nations” in v. 13; when we look at the clause containing ἔθνεσιν, “just as I also had among the other nations,” and consider the whole statement in the context of the passage, it becomes clear that it can be read parenthetically and omitted with no change to the overall meaning of the passage. I suggest that this reading of Rom 1:13-15 is more satisfying rhetorically, within the passage itself and within the letter to the Romans as a whole.

3.1.2. *Rom 15:14-27 – “Offering of the Nations”*

This passage from the other end of the letter frame is often cited as another proof that Paul’s audience is Gentile. Why? Because the word “Gentile” occurs in v. 16:

14 I myself am satisfied about you, my brothers, that you yourselves are full of goodness, filled with all knowledge and able to instruct one another. 15 But on some points I have written to you very boldly by way of reminder, because of the grace given me by God 16 to be a minister of Christ Jesus to the *Gentiles* in the priestly service of the gospel of God, so that the offering of the *Gentiles* may be acceptable, sanctified by the Holy Spirit.
 (ESV, emphasis added)

As discussed above, I prefer “nations” over “Gentiles,” not to refute that people are in view, but to acknowledge the multivalent nature of ἔθνη and include in the context of its usage the geography of the people. The fact is, I agree with the majority of scholars that Paul is referring to the people of the nations in this passage. So the question remains, can this passage only be read

to indicate that Paul’s audience for Romans is Gentile? I suggest that it does not. Let us start by examining the typical interpretation of this passage in service of claiming that Paul is writing to Gentiles. Keck is representative:

Perhaps aware that the positive characterization of the readers in verse 14 might prompt some of them to ask, “Why, then, did you write such an assertive letter?” Paul explains why he wrote “rather boldly,” either “on some points” (NRSV, NIV) or “at times” (REB)—namely, to remind them of his God-given mission (vv. 15-16). Earlier he had identified himself as an apostle (1:1, 5), indeed “the apostle of the Gentiles” (11:13, AT); but here he uses terms with well-known sacral meanings: He is a “minister” (*leitourgos*, one engaged in official duties with sacred significance) for the Gentiles, functioning “in the priestly service of the gospel of God,” so that “the offering of the Gentiles may be acceptable, sanctified [hallowed] by the Holy Spirit.” This “offering” (*prosphora*) does not refer to the money collected from the Gentile churches (see vv. 25-27) but to the Gentiles themselves, as in REB: “It is my priestly task to offer the Gentiles to him as an acceptable sacrifice.”⁹⁶

Keck reads 15:16 in context with vv. 14 and 15 and suggests that Paul is writing to his audience “boldly” to “remind them of his God-given mission.” The assumption is that the “Gentiles” of v. 16 are the same “brothers” of v. 14, and thus the claim of a Gentile audience. This interpretation raises several questions. If this is the correct reading, what is the logic in making such a statement? Why would Paul chastise his Gentile hearers to remind them that it is his job to share the gospel with them? Once again, as in the traditional interpretations in chapter 1, there is no rhetorical force behind this reading; it serves no purpose in Paul’s overall argument. Secondly, if Paul is talking to Gentiles, which he addresses as “my brothers” in v. 14, why does he then refer to his mission “to the Gentiles” or the “offering of the Gentiles” rather than use second person plural pronouns (“you”) to mirror the direct address in v. 14? One obvious response is that “my brothers” refers to all believers in Rome, including Jews, but that Paul is really addressing Gentiles, both with his statement in v. 16 and throughout the letter, so the argument goes. This assertion amounts to a lot of hand-waving bordering on eisegesis, and this entire reading breaks

⁹⁶ Keck, 360.

down under scrutiny.

I offer a more logic-driven approach, starting in v. 14. If we assume for the moment that Paul is talking to his Jewish/Israelite “siblings,” what is he reminding them of in v. 15? Rather than look forward, we must look back initially. He voices his satisfaction with them due to their goodness, knowledge, and teaching ability; these are the things that he has been reminding them of in his admonitions throughout the letter. In vv. 15b-16, then, we are given what appears to be two nested reasons: “because” ($\delta\iota\alpha$) he is “minister to the nations” and “so that” ($\iota\upsilon\alpha$) his “offering of the Gentiles” is acceptable. The traditional understanding of these two clauses is to read the first causal statement as primary and the second as amplifying the first. However, this interpretation is driven by presuppositions about Paul’s mission as solely the “apostle to the Gentiles,” presuppositions which drive exegetes to more heavily weight the first clause. In fact, these two clausal statements serve two different purposes: the $\delta\iota\alpha$ clause answers the implied question, “what gives you the right to correct us,” while the $\iota\upsilon\alpha$ clause answers the implied question, “for what reason are you correcting us.” Understood this way, the first clause can be read parenthetically (Paul in effect is saying, “because I have been appointed to do this”), making the second clause the primary focus of Paul’s argument in this passage. Paul can be heard to say: “You guys are doing great; however, I am admonishing you just as a reminder to continue doing great, so that my nations’ offering (as you know, this is my main job) is acceptable, sanctified by the Holy Spirit.” This reading shows at a minimum that it is not a foregone conclusion that Paul is addressing Gentiles in this passage (and thus in the whole letter), and that it might make more sense to read this passage as if he is addressing his fellow Jewish believers. In this case, “Gentiles” indeed can be read as referring to non-Israelites, similar to 11:13, with Paul justifying his somewhat harsh admonition to the Jewish/Israelite believers as

a way to avoid being a bad example to Gentiles.

To complete this discussion of “Gentiles” and Paul’s audience in chapter 15, let us look at 15:26-27. Paul bookends his discussion of “offering,” rhetorically reversing the offering of vv. 14-16, where Gentiles themselves are the offering, and talking now about the offering “from the Gentiles.” Here as well, “Gentiles” (v. 27) can be understood as indicating non-Israelite believers in “Achaia and Macedonia” (v. 26), while still assuming that Paul is addressing a primarily Jewish/Israelite audience.

3.1.3. *Rom 11:13 - Direct Address to “Gentiles”*

Finally, we look at the verse and its surrounding passage that most scholars point to as the “smoking gun” for determining that Paul is indeed writing to Gentiles, Rom 11:13. This verse contains the only direct address specifically to “Gentiles” in Romans. Direct address can be found throughout the letter, however, and Paul uses a variety of other group markers - “called ones,” “holy ones,” “beloved ones,” “brothers/siblings.” These markers are traditionally treated as referring to believers universally; however, because of the address to “Gentiles” in 11:13, many scholars assume that “Gentiles” are the primary or even exclusive audience that Paul is addressing. Dunn, representing the consensus view, states that “Paul is clearly writing to Gentiles” in Romans and that “this is obvious from 11:13-32.⁹⁷” He reasons this way:

The specific address (ὁμῖν is emphatic) does not necessarily mean that the Roman congregations were exclusively Gentile, since Paul could intend by this phrase to catch the attention specifically of the Gentile members of the Christian groups to whom his letter would be read (Cranfield). But a gentile majority is probably envisaged (so most), otherwise Jewish rejection would not be such a contrast to Gentile conversion and there would be less occasion for Gentile boasting over Jewish failure (vv 17–24); Hort, cited by SH, also draws attention to the fact that Jews are spoken of in third person terms in chaps. 9–11, whereas from here on Gentiles are directly addressed in second person terms.⁹⁸

⁹⁷ Dunn, *Romans 1-8*, xlv.

⁹⁸ Dunn, *Romans 9-16*, 655.

Dunn admits up front that Paul’s audience (“the Roman congregations”) is not necessarily “exclusively Gentile,” but then he proceeds to argue for a “gentile majority” based on “Jewish rejection,” Gentile boasting over “Jewish failure,” and “Jews” spoken of in the third person, all in chapters 9 to 11. Let me first state that I am in agreement with Dunn and most scholars that 11:13 and the attendant passage (which I end at v. 24, for reasons I will explain later) indeed refer to Gentiles, the peoples of the nations. I also agree that, while this direct address in 11:13 calls out Gentiles in Paul’s audience, it is not to be taken to indicate that they are the only group represented in the audience in Rome. However, it is there that my agreement ends. I argue in the bulk of this paper for a Jewish believer majority in the audience of Romans. In this reading, 11:13ff becomes an aside to those Gentile believers in the audience, before Paul returns to addressing the Jewish majority. I will detail all this below, but for now, allow me to address Dunn’s claims concerning “Jews” in chapters 9 to 11. First, the group marker “Jew” or “Jews” (singular or plural of Ἰουδαῖος) only occurs two times in chapters 9 to 11, at 9:24 and 10:12. The “Jewish” rejection and failure that Dunn refers to comes from those verses that mention “Israel”; Dunn has conflated the two terms, which we now know from Staples’s work is a mistake.⁹⁹ As for discussing “Jews” in the third person, when we look at the two verses where Ἰουδαῖος actually occurs, in each case it is in contrast to either “Gentiles” or “Greek,” which are both also in the third person, thus this argument is weak at best.¹⁰⁰ In the end, all we can know for certain based on 11:13 is that Paul was indeed addressing Gentiles in 11:13, which means that as a group they were part of Paul’s audience, but not necessarily the whole.

⁹⁹ See chapter 2, “Literature Review,” section 3.1, “Jason A. Staples – The Idea of Israel.”

¹⁰⁰ Given that Dunn conflates “Jew” and “Israel,” his argument, borrowed from Hort, is based on not just the term “Jew” but also occurrences of “Israel” in chapters 9 to 11; however, the two examples given here where other groups are referred to in the third person effectively counter this claim.

3.1.4. *Excursus – a “Gentile” Hermeneutic*

Given the discussion above, can we identify a hermeneutic to guide us in determining when Paul is using ἔθνος to refer specifically to a group of people vs. using it in a geographic sense? I think we can. The starting point, as always, is the context of the passage being examined. Beyond this consideration, I believe we can make several observations about the linguistic characteristics of the phrase in question that can help in our exegesis. I offer these guidelines in the form of questions:

Is there a preposition? Rom 1:5-6 and 1:13 use the preposition ἐν, which has numerous definitions and uses (12 in BDAG), but which is typically translated in these verses as “in” or “among.”¹⁰¹ These glosses are associated with the first definition listed in BDAG, which defines ἐν as a “marker of a position defined as being in a location.” Similarly, Rom 9:24 uses ἐκ, another location dependent preposition “denoting separation,” typically translated “from” or “out of.”¹⁰² In each of these cases, the use of these prepositions does not resolve the ambiguity of the term ἔθνος; in fact, it makes as much sense to consider the phrase “in/among Gentiles/nations” or “from/out of Gentiles/nations” as modifying a subject or object that can be described in both ways – in/among/from a group of people and in/among/out of certain land/territories associated with those people – while not indicating whether they are part of that people group ethnically or culturally. Although this acknowledgement only multiplies the ambiguities being dealt with, it brings clarity to the exegetical decision process: the decision on whether ἔθνος represents a people or a place cannot be made based on any of these prepositional phrases and must default to context and/or other linguistic markers in the text.

¹⁰¹ BDAG, 326-330. “The uses of this prep. are so many and various, and oft. so easily confused, that a strictly systematic treatment is impossible.”

¹⁰² BDAG, 295-298.

Is ἔθνος in the dative with no preposition? This is the case that we find in Rom 11:13, as well as other occurrences in Paul's letters: Rom 11:11, 1 Cor 1:23, Eph 3:8, 1 Thes 2:16. In these instances, ἔθνος is the indirect object of an action that is usually directed at persons.

Is ἔθνος adjacent to the personal pronoun "you"? Once again our prime example from Romans is 11:13, ὑμῖν δὲ λέγω τοῖς ἔθνεσιν ("Now I am speaking to you Gentiles"). In this configuration, ἔθνεσιν is an appositive to ὑμῖν, modifying the pronoun. This "personalization" of ἔθνος indicates that the author is talking to people as opposed to referring to a geographical location. This format is also found in 1 Cor 5:1, Eph 2:11, and Eph 3:1.

Are the actions being done by or to ἔθνος "human"? Where ἔθνος is the subject or direct object of a clause, any verbs that require a human to enact or to be acted upon is a sure sign that ἔθνος is being used to indicate people as opposed to land. Examples are: Rom 2:14 (doing the law); Rom 9:30 (pursuing righteousness); Rom 11:11 (receiving salvation); Rom 15:9-12 (glorifying, rejoicing, praising, hoping).

These questions cover a good number of situations found in the Pauline corpus. As a reminder, context of the passage and the text as a whole is always primary in determining the appropriate interpretation of any given instance of ἔθνος. Without one of the conditions above that specifically indicates people are in view, my suggestion is to treat ἔθνος as the multivalent term that it is, referring to both a people and the land they inhabit, and allow context, both locally and at the discourse level of the text, to be the driving factor in exegesis.

3.1.5. Conclusion

In conclusion, upon further study that is dependent on a closer reading of the text and a logic-driven exegesis, it is clear that the group marker ἔθνη used in these verses, so often cited as proof of Paul's primarily Gentile audience in his letter to Rome, serves a variety of rhetorical purposes

for Paul, but should not be used to specifically identify his audience as Gentile. The exception is 11:13, where ἔθνη is used as a direct address group marker to identify the audience of the 11:13ff passage only. To determine Paul’s audience(s) at various points in the letter, we need to reexamine the direct address group markers he uses throughout the rest of Romans. My assertion of a primarily Jewish audience will be strengthened below as we continue to consider the other direct address group markers used by Paul and to examine how they affect our exegesis of the letter in toto.

3.2. Other Direct Address Group Markers

As already mentioned, Paul uses four other direct address group markers in Romans that are typically read universally, referring to all believers in Rome. Paul makes no explicit statement in Romans itself that this is the case; it is a presupposition by the majority of exegetes and rarely discussed in the scholarly literature.¹⁰³ I will consider the first three together: κλητοί, “called ones”; ἅγιοι, “holy ones”; and ἀγαπητοί, “beloved ones.” I will then spend a little more time unpacking the term ἀδελφοί, “brothers/siblings.”

3.2.1. **“Called Ones”/ “Holy Ones”/ “Beloved Ones”**

Of these three markers, only two are found in Romans in the direct address plural form: κλητοί (called ones), 1:6; and ἀγαπητοί (beloved ones), 12:19. However, all three terms appear together in v. 1:7 in the plural dative form. For the purposes of this discussion, I am including them as a form of direct address because in the context of Romans they are used as the salutation of the letter. While there is nothing inherently “ethnic” in any of these words and they are typically understood as universal markers for all the believers that Paul is addressing in Rome, the truth is

¹⁰³ See chapter 2, “Literature Review,” section 4, “Other Group Markers.”

that all three terms are used by Jews/Israelites as self-identifiers in the Old Testament. Here are some examples (from the ESV):

“Called ones”:

Isaiah 63:19 - We have become like those over whom you have never ruled, like those who are not called by your name.

Jeremiah 14:9 - Why should you be like a man confused, like a mighty warrior who cannot save? Yet you, O LORD, are in the midst of us, and we are called by your name; do not leave us.”

Jeremiah 15:16 - Your words were found, and I ate them, and your words became to me a joy and the delight of my heart, for I am called by your name, O LORD, God of hosts.

Daniel 9:19 - O Lord, hear; O Lord, forgive. O Lord, pay attention and act. Delay not, for your own sake, O my God, because your city and your people are called by your name.”

2 Chronicles 7:14 - if my people who are called by my name humble themselves, and pray and seek my face and turn from their wicked ways, then I will hear from heaven and will forgive their sin and heal their land.

“Holy ones” (often translated “saints”):

Leviticus 11:44 - For I am the LORD your God. Consecrate yourselves therefore, and be holy, for I am holy. You shall not defile yourselves with any swarming thing that crawls on the ground.

Leviticus 20:26 - You shall be holy to me, for I the LORD am holy and have separated you from the peoples, that you should be mine.

Psalms 34:9 - Oh, fear the LORD, you his saints, for those who fear him have no lack!

Daniel 7:18 - But the saints of the Most High shall receive the kingdom and possess the kingdom forever, forever and ever.

Daniel 7:22 - until the Ancient of Days came, and judgment was given for the saints of the Most High, and the time came when the saints possessed the kingdom.

Exodus 19:6 - and you shall be to me a kingdom of priests and a holy nation.' These are the words that you shall speak to the people of Israel.” (spoken to the nation of Israel as a whole)

“Beloved ones”:

Psalms 60:5 - That your beloved ones may be delivered, give salvation by your right hand

and answer us!

Psalm 127:2 - It is in vain that you rise up early and go late to rest, eating the bread of anxious toil; for he gives to his beloved sleep.

Deuteronomy 4:37 - And because he loved your fathers and chose their offspring after them and brought you out of Egypt with his own presence, by his great power,

2 Chronicles 9:8 - Blessed be the LORD your God, who has delighted in you and set you on his throne as king for the LORD your God! Because your God loved Israel and would establish them forever, he has made you king over them, that you may execute justice and righteousness.”

Deuteronomy 6:6 - You shall love the LORD your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your might.

In all three of these cases, each group marker is used to refer specifically to Israel, either as individual people within the nation or to the nation as a whole. For “called ones,” it is most often tied to being called by the name of God, indicating that they are God’s chosen people. For “holy ones,” while it is used of the nation in its entirety, it is often a technical designation for priests. Finally, for “beloved (ones),” this appellation is associated with the reciprocal action of the Israelites “loving God,” as is seen in Deut 6:6, quoted above. While these examples do not preclude one from reading these markers in Romans as being universally applied to all believers to include Gentiles, this should not be a foregone conclusion. The weight of the historical usage of these terms as identifiers for the Israelite people must be fully considered when determining Paul’s audience in Rome. Recalling the discussion of fuzzy logic from chapter 3, imagine a mixed audience of Jews/Israelites and Gentiles. What are there different reactions to being addressed by one of these group markers? Surely the Israelites will feel in their bones the call of God to his designated people of Israel. The Gentiles, by contrast, might assume a general address to everyone in the audience, including themselves; but they will also know the specific meanings of these words from the Hebrew Scriptures, and know how their Israelite companions are most likely receiving them, in a much stronger and deeper way. In the absence of an explicit statement

from Paul or one of his contemporaries that these words are now being applied to Gentiles, I suggest that the more straightforward exegesis is to read these as Israelite group markers.

3.2.2. *“Brothers/Siblings”*

The term ἀδελφοί, translated “brothers” or “siblings,” deserves a more detailed examination. In Romans, it is the most frequent direct address word used, occurring ten times (1:13, 7:1, 7:4, 8:12, 10:1, 11:25, 12:1, 15:14, 15:30, 16:17). While it is not an “ethnic” marker in the sense that it explicitly indicates a specific group of people, it is “ethnic” in a relative sense because as a familial term it connects the speaker to the audience addressed by blood when used literally. However, the received reading of “brothers” in Romans and elsewhere in the Pauline corpus treats this term metaphorically, referring to all believers regardless of national/ethnic origin, creating what is often called a “fictive kinship.”¹⁰⁴ As I have done with the other group markers reviewed here, I first would like to point out that this metaphorical reading is not required by the semantic context of the word ἀδελφοί in any of these occurrences in Romans. The choice to view this term metaphorically and apply it to Gentiles as well as Israelites is made based on merely the appearance of the word “Gentile” within the letter a few times and the assumption that Paul is the “apostle to the Gentiles” and therefore must be writing to non-Israelites primarily, as discussed above. I urge you, for the time being, to consider that the alternate view - that Paul is addressing his Israelite kin specifically whenever he uses the word ἀδελφοί - is equally plausible.

To give strength to this alternative, let us look this time to the usage of ἀδελφοί in the rest of the New Testament, specifically in Acts. Most scholars agree that Acts was written after Romans. And yet the period of time covered by this book includes events that presumably occur

¹⁰⁴ E.g., Das, *Solving the Romans Debate*, 92-93.

both before the writing and delivery of Romans and after. Therefore, we can compare the use of the direct address plural form of ἀδελφοί in both texts and assume some level of continuity - both Paul and the author of Acts should be using the term in similar ways to indicate similar groups of people. In Acts, ἀδελφός occurs 57 times. 53 times are in the plural form; of those, we find 16 instances of ἀδελφοί being used in the vocative case (the most in Acts),¹⁰⁵ as shown in the table below:

Chapter	Verse	Situation	Audience
1	16	Peter to company of 120 brothers after the selection of Matthias; possibly refers back to "men of Galilee" in 1:11	Galileans, other Israelite followers
2	29	Peter at Pentacost	"Men of Israel" (2:22)
2	37	Peter at Pentacost	"Men of Israel" (2:22); "all the house of Israel" (2:36)
3	17	Peter at Solomon's portico	"men of Israel" (3:12)
6	3	The apostles to the disciples, choosing the 7 deacons in Jerusalem	"Hellenists [Greek-speaking Jews] and Hebrews" (6:1)
7	2	Stephen before the Jewish council in Jerusalem	"the people [of Jerusalem] and the elders and the scribes" (6:12); members of the Jerusalem council (6:15)
13	15	Rulers of the synagogue at Antioch to Paul and Barnabas	Paul and Barnabas
13	26	Paul to the synagogue leaders at Antioch	"sons of the family of Abraham" is appositive to "brothers"; "and those among you who fear God" is separated by and, not part of the appositive referring back to brothers; could be ambiguous, but tied with the "brothers" reference to Paul in v15 by the synagogue leaders, it makes this reading almost certain.
13	38	Paul to the synagogue leaders at Antioch	same as v26; v39 talks of freeing "everyone" from that which "the law of Moses" could not free you, implying an Israelite covenant audience.
15	7	Peter to the Jerusalem council (apostles and elders)	Apostles and elders of the early church in Jerusalem, presumably all Israelites
15	13	James to the apostles and elders at the Jerusalem council	Apostles and elders of the early church in Jerusalem, presumably all Israelites
22	1	Paul to the crowd after his arrest at the temple	"Jews from Asia" (21:27), "Men of Israel" (21:28)
23	1	Paul before the chief priests and council	"Jews" (22:30), "chief priests and all the council" (22:30)
23	5	same as 23:1	same as 23:1
23	6	same as 23:1	same as 23:1
28	17	Paul in Rome	"local leaders of the Jews"

Instances of Ἀδελφοί in Acts in Vocative Form

In all 16 cases, the immediate context demonstrates that the group being addressed is Jewish/Israelite. Gentiles are never in view. In these examples, the group marker ἀδελφοί is used in Acts in a literal sense, as a familial/ethnic indicator. You can argue that, technically, the author of Acts is still employing a form of "fictive kinship" since the audience members being addressed are not truly siblings who are born from the same mother, and you would be correct.

¹⁰⁵ The 53 plural occurrences of ἀδελφός in Acts by case: nominative, 10; accusative, 10; dative, 8; genitive, 9; vocative, 16.

However, this is the common usage of the word for “brothers/siblings” in the Old Testament, both in its Hebrew and Greek forms, and strengthens my argument - those born of the Abrahamic family and of the people of Israel are referred to as siblings, while those of other nations are not.

As we expand our investigation of ἀδελφοί to the rest of Acts and beyond the strictly vocative form, we see a similar pattern of use: in the remaining 37 occurrences, two are referring to literal “brothers” (1:14, Jesus’s brothers; 7:13, Joseph’s brothers); 32 can be determined by context to be referring to Jews/Israelites. The remaining three occurrences are in chapter 15 and warrant a brief discussion. In Acts 15:23, the Jerusalem council addresses a letter to Antioch from “the brothers” (ἀδελφοί) to “the brothers” (ἀδελφοῖς) τοῖς ἐξ ἔθνῶν – “to those [from/out of/among] the nations.” The traditional reading of this verse renders this greeting as “to the brothers from the Gentiles,” with the assumption that “brothers” then includes the presence of Gentile believers. Because of this understanding, it is to be assumed then that the occurrences of ἀδελφοί in 15:1 and 15:32 would also include Gentiles. I have two different lines of inquiry that question this reading of 15:23 and that might result in an alternate reading that limits the understanding of ἀδελφοί to Jews/Israelites; however, time and space prohibit that discussion here. Suffice it to say that for this paper I concede that these three occurrences of ἀδελφοί are traditionally understood to include Gentiles. With that said, the overwhelming majority of occurrences of ἀδελφοί in Acts refer solely to Jews/Israelites, both before and after the exceptions found in chapter 15.

Is it possible that Paul was innovating this usage of the word ἀδελφοί to apply to Gentiles? Certainly. However, we have no textual evidence anywhere in the Pauline corpus that explicitly indicates that has happened, only assumptions based on presuppositions made primarily external to the text. This, of course, is an argument from silence; nevertheless, it is a

data point worth mentioning. The mere presence of Gentiles in Paul’s audience in Romans, as evidenced by his direct address to them in 11:13, is not enough reason to mandate that they are included in his address to “brothers/siblings” – such an assertion is equally arguing from silence. More convincing textual evidence would come in the form of an explicit claim that Gentiles were now counted among the ἀδελφοί (similar to the statement in Acts 11:26 concerning the first use of the term “Christians”). While it has been shown that other groups in the first century also used ἀδελφοί to self-identify non-familial members in a metaphorical sense, the Israelite context and usage should not be ignored.¹⁰⁶

In all of the examples above, my main goal has been to suggest that the assumption that Paul is writing primarily to Gentiles in his letter to Rome is far from being set in stone. At the end of this analysis, once additional evidence is presented, we will revisit the topic of Paul’s audience in Romans in the “Synthesis” section, where I will make a much stronger argument suggesting that Paul’s audience is indeed his fellow Israelites.

4. Ethnic Group Markers in Old Testament Quotations in Romans 9-11

Chapters 9 to 11 of Romans are typically read as addressed to Gentiles, providing an argument for the “election” of Gentiles by God, while also offering a defense in support of the Jews still being part of the kingdom of God through the gospel. This reading is dependent on two hermeneutical moves: 1) assuming that Paul is writing to Gentile believers throughout Romans, and 2) assuming that Paul applies OT Scriptures quoted in this section in a new way to Gentiles, though the selected passages were originally directed at Israelites. These two assumptions are dependent on one another, and can cause one to engage in circular reasoning: if you insist that 1) is true, then you

¹⁰⁶ David G. Horrell, “From adelphoi to oikos theou: Social Transformation in Pauline Christianity” *JBL* 120 (2) 2001, 296.

must accept that 2) is true in order to make sense of the OT citations Paul uses; at the same time, if you assume that 2) is true, then naturally Paul must be talking to Gentiles, thus 1) must be true as well.

As seen in the first part of my analysis, mandating a primarily Gentile audience in Romans is not the only possible reading supported by the text, and in fact a strong case can be made for a primarily Jewish/Israelite audience. We can make such a case by following the hermeneutic laid down by many New Testament scholars, including no less than the likes of Richard Hays and N. T. Wright, both highly respected and accomplished Pauline experts. That hermeneutic involves taking Old Testament references in the New Testament and reading them in their original textual, rhetorical, and historical context in order to fully understand the purpose behind each citation's selection.¹⁰⁷ By taking this perspective, you no longer need to assume that Paul is doing something "novel" by quoting OT verses and applying them to Gentiles - all quotations from the Hebrew writings can and should be read in their original context and analyzed in the flow of the argument that Paul is conducting with his Jewish audience. What we find when we take this approach is that a new (old) dynamic is at work in Paul's rhetoric: the driving argument is not about Gentiles and Jews, but about Jews and non-Jewish Israelites, those from the former Northern Kingdom of Israel in the divided monarchy. Gentiles are sometimes used as a foil (2:14, 9:30) and come into the discussion directly at the end of chapter 11, but the primary discussion is in support of Israel, those Israelites displaced from what was the Northern Kingdom.

We will examine below selections from each of these chapters that contain OT quotations with explicit and/or implicit ethnic markers and highlight the interplay in Paul's rhetoric between

¹⁰⁷ Richard B. Hays, *Echoes of Scripture in the Letters of Paul* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1989), 31; N. T. Wright, *Paul and the Faithfulness of God*, 1453. Unfortunately, both Hays (67) and Wright (1185), after advocating for this hermeneutic, turn around and allegorize these passages and apply them to Gentiles.

the Southern Kingdom (Jews) and the Northern Kingdom (Israel). Before we do so, however, we must address another presupposition: the idea that “Jew” and “Israel” are synonymous terms in Paul’s letters and throughout the New Testament. This view has been brought into question by Jason Staples in his monograph *The Idea of Israel in Second Temple Judaism*.¹⁰⁸ In this comprehensive study, Staples investigates the use of the terms Ἰουδαῖος and Ἰσραήλ (along with several other ethnic markers) across Second Temple literature, interacting with both the OT and the NT, as well as Jewish apocalyptic literature (Ben Sira, Psalms of Solomon, 4 Ezra, 2 Baruch) and the works of Josephus and Philo. Staples concluded that, in fact, the terms “Israel” and “Jew” are never used in the literature synonymously. “Israel” is employed in one of three ways: 1) to refer to all Israel (all twelve tribes) before the kingdom divided after the death of Solomon; 2) to refer to the Northern Kingdom of Israel, which included the ten northern tribes, during the divided kingdom, both before and after the Neo-Assyrian conquest of the Northern Kingdom; and 3) to refer to all twelve tribes reunited in an indeterminate eschatological future. “Jew” is used to denote those Israelites from the Southern Kingdom of Judah or those who have chosen to follow their way of living. In no case noted by Staples are the Jews referred to as “Israel,” in the sense that they are the sum total of Israel with no regard for the tribes of the Northern Kingdom. In other words, no “replacement theology” exists in the extant literature whereby Jews become the “new Israel.” In Romans, then, we must differentiate between the various senses of the term “Israel” based on the context of the argument. This context, as we shall see, is driven by the OT citations found throughout these three chapters.

¹⁰⁸ Staples, *The Idea of Israel*. See chapter 2, “Literature Review,” section 3.1, “Jason A. Staples – The Idea of Israel.”

4.1. Romans Chapter 9

As many scholars have noted, chapter 9 begins a new section of the letter. I will show in the “Synthesis” section below how chapters 9 through 11 are seamlessly connected to the first eight chapters, but for now we will focus on 9-11. In 9:1-5, Paul lays out his plea for the inclusion of his “flesh” the “Israelites” in the family of God, and in so doing he identifies the object of the argument in these three chapters - non-Jewish Israelites, against whom his Jewish interlocutors are arguing to exclude from the covenant. This section acts as a rhetorical “rally point” for the overall argument. In the military, a rally point is a physical location designated as the meeting place for soldiers to return to if they get dispersed and need to reassemble. In the complex argument of Romans 9-11, keeping Romans 9:1-5 in view at all times helps remind us what and who we are discussing. As we examine the argument that Paul constructs in Romans 9 to 11, we must always come back to this rhetorical “rally point” to remind ourselves whose fates we are weighing.

In chapter 9, we will look at vv. 25 to 29:

Romans 9:25-26 – In this section, Paul cites from two different parts of the book of Hosea:

As indeed he says in Hosea: “...Those who are not my people I will call ‘my people,’ and her who was not beloved I will call beloved. And in the very place where it was said to them, ‘You are not my people,’ there they will be called sons of the living God.

These two declarations are from Hosea 2:23 and 1:10, respectively. The majority of scholars claim that Paul is applying these verses to Gentiles, because of the mention of Gentiles in the preceding verse and because of the presupposition that he is primarily addressing Gentiles throughout the letter. However, when these quotations from Hosea are read in their original context, there is no room for loosely applying these statements to any other group than the Northern Kingdom of Israel. Hosea 1:6 and the beginning of 1:10 make it clear that the prophet is referring to Israel, and 1:11 shows that “Israel” refers to the Northern Kingdom in a divided Israel, with the nation of

Judah in the south:

And the children of Judah and the children of Israel shall be gathered together, and they shall appoint for themselves one head. And they shall go up from the land, for great shall be the day of Jezreel. (ESV)

No one argues that, read in context, these verses indeed are about the Northern Kingdom of Israel. However, because of the presupposition that “the apostle to the Gentiles” is writing to Gentiles, a flat, non-contextual reading of this text is preferred so that it can be twisted and applied to the Gentiles. It is through this faulty logic that Paul is then accused of doing something different with Holy Writ; scholars have made him into a proof-texter who disregards the context of the original text.

Romans 9:27-28 – The Hosea reference is immediately followed by a quotation from

Isaiah:

And Isaiah cries out concerning Israel, “Though the number of the sons of Israel be as the sand of the sea, a remnant of them will be saved, for the Lord will carry out his sentence upon the earth fully and without delay. (author’s translation)

This quotation is from Isaiah 10:22,23. It echoes Hosea 1:10 - “the number of the children of Israel shall be like the sand of the sea” is found at the beginning of that verse, but you miss the direct connection between Rom 9:25-26 and 9:27 because Paul does not quote the whole verse. “Israel” once again refers to the Northern Kingdom, as can be seen by reading Isaiah 9. Isaiah 9:21, the last verse leading into chapter 10, is representative:

Manasseh devours Ephraim, and Ephraim devours Manasseh; together they are against Judah. For all this his anger has not turned away, and his hand is stretched out still. (ESV)

Manasseh and Ephraim, the two sons of Joseph, are “half tribes” that represent the Northern Kingdom of Israel. This verse points out their animosity towards Judah, the Southern Kingdom, and God’s anger toward the Northern Kingdom because of it. However, by Isaiah 10:20, the Lord promises that Israel will return to the Lord and rely on him, albeit it is only a portion of the people

who will be saved, a “remnant.” This notion of a remnant being saved is a qualification placed upon Hosea 1:10 as excerpted in v. 26. If you view these OT citations as point and counter point, vv. 27-28 are implying, “Yes, fine, I concede that God has indeed promised to rescue the Northern Kingdom of Israel, but look here, it will not be all of them, because Isaiah says only a remnant will be saved.” As we will see below, this point/counterpoint continues in the next OT citation.

Romans 9:29 – Here we see a second quotation from Isaiah, this time from chapter 1, verse 9:

And as Isaiah predicted, “If the Lord of hosts had not left us offspring, we would have been like Sodom, and become like Gomorrah. (ESV)

Verse 29 continues the series of connected OT quotations started in v. 25. Where the connection between vv. 25-26 and vv. 27-28 is the matched wording between the quoted OT verses, here the connection is the author of Isaiah. However, in this instance, Paul is reaching back to the start of the book of Isaiah to provide a counter to the Isaianic quote in vv. 27-28. At the beginning of Isaiah, the author is specifically addressing the Southern Kingdom of Judah, as designated by v. 1:1:

The vision of Isaiah the son of Amoz, which he saw concerning Judah and Jerusalem in the days of Uzziah, Jotham, Ahaz, and Hezekiah, kings of Judah.

By quoting Isaiah 1:9, Paul is saying, along with the author of Isaiah, that “we Jews are no different than our brothers of the Northern Kingdom – there, but for the grace of God, go I.” This sentiment echoes the arguments that Paul has already put forth in Romans chapters 2 and 3, that “none is righteous.” As we look at the OT citations in the next two chapters, we see this idea of a Northern Kingdom remnant repeated implicitly in Romans 10 and explicitly in Romans 11.

4.2. Romans Chapter 10

In chapter 10, we will look at the OT quotations in vv. 12 to 21 and show how, similar to chapter

9, they form the backbone for a connected argument and ultimately point to Northern Kingdom Israelites as the object of that argument.

Romans 10:12-13 - In vv. 12-13, Paul asserts that there is no distinction between “Jew and Greek” (a phrase that I assert denotes “all Israel” as opposed to “all humanity”; I will explain this reading in the next section) and that “all who call on the name of the Lord will be saved” - a quote from Joel 2:32. This reference is actually the third allusion to Joel. Paul uses the phrase “shall not be put to shame” twice - first in 9:33, and again in 10:11. These words in Romans mimic the same in Joel 2:26, 27, where the author twice states “And my people shall never again be put to shame” (ESV). The book of Joel concerns the people of Israel (2:27, 3:2, 3:16); these references appear to refer to the nation as a whole, perhaps prior to the divided monarchy, or in an eschatological future.¹⁰⁹ This understanding of “Israel” makes sense, both in Joel and here in Romans, given Paul’s focus on “all” in both v. 12 and 13 (albeit a qualified “all” with the mention of “Jew and Greek” - again, to be covered in the next section).

Romans 10:14-15a - Paul then asks a series of rhetorical questions in vv. 14-15 that are causally linked: “How then can they call upon him in whom they do not believe? And how will they believe in him of whom they have not heard? And will they hear without someone preaching? And how will they preach without being sent?” The “they” at the beginning of v. 14 reaches back to our rally point in 9:1-5, referencing non-Jewish Israelites. One could argue that “they” refers to all Israelites, following directly after 10:12 and the claim of “no distinction between Jew and Greek”; however, I view this as a sub-argument in the flow of Paul’s rhetoric, with v. 14 picking up the broader argument of the section (see 10:1-2). These questions are then followed by a

¹⁰⁹ Andrew E. Hill and John H. Walton, *A Survey of the Old Testament, Third Edition* (Grand Rapids: Zondervan Academic, 2009), 596-597. The dating of the book of Joel, for which there is little evidence, is difficult; scholars are divided, positing both a pre-exilic time period and a post-exilic 2nd century BCE time period.

dialogue of questions and answers that revisits each of the initial questions, providing OT quotations in what seems to approximate a chiasm:

A - Belief (v. 14)
 B - Hearing (v. 14)
 C - Preaching (v. 14, 15a)
 C' - Preaching (v. 15b, 16)
 B' - Hearing (v. 16, 17)
 A' - Belief (v. 16, 17)

Romans 10:15b - The first OT verse in this progression is from the beginning of Isaiah 52:7: “How beautiful are the feet of those who bring good tidings of good things!¹¹⁰” This excerpt from Isaiah seems to be in response to Paul’s question concerning preaching in v. 14, but we must consider the context of Isaiah to fully understand why this particular verse was chosen. Indeed, Isaiah chapter 52 begins with references to “Zion” and “Jerusalem” in both v. 1 and 2, indicating the message is directed to devout Israelites. Paul’s quote from v. 7, then, a generic platitude when read in isolation, is a unique statement of the coming good news to Israel. As Staples states, the writer of Deutero-Isaiah has in mind not just the Jews of the Southern Kingdom, but a fully restored twelve tribes of Israel (48:1, 49:5-6).¹¹¹ A broader vision encompassing the nations can be found throughout Deutero-Isaiah (chapters 40 to 55), but it is usually in a negative sense (45:1, 52:15) or a reference to Israel coming out of the nations and returning to the land (45:20, 49:6, 49:22).

Romans 10:16-17 - the next verse begins with the Greek ἀλλ (contracted form of ἀλλά) and provides a counterpoint to the previous statement, followed by another quote from Isaiah: “But not all heeded the gospel. For Isaiah says, “Lord, who has believed what he has heard from us?”

¹¹⁰ The ESV translates “bring good tidings” as “preach” to make the English more “on the nose” with “preaching” in v. 14; however, the Greek in v. 15 is εὐαγγελίζω, different from κηρύσσω in v. 14.

¹¹¹ Staples, *The Idea of Israel*, 122-128. See also Gary N. Knoppers, “Did Jacob Become Judah? The Configuration of Israel’s Restoration in Deutero-Isaiah” in *Samaria, Samaritans, Samaritans*, ed. József Zsengellér, (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2011), 39-67.

This quote is from Isaiah 53:1, which occurs nine verses after 52:7, quoted in v. 15. Verse 17 immediately follows with the connector ἄρα, translated “so” or “so then,” signifying a conclusion to what is stated in v. 16: “So belief from hearing, and hearing through the word of Christ.” Is Paul just asserting this claim from his own experience? I think not. I contend that he is offering this conclusion based on the context of Isaiah 53:1ff:

- [1] Who has believed what he has heard from us?
And to whom has the arm of the LORD been revealed?
- [2] For he grew up before him like a young plant,
and like a root out of dry ground;
he had no form or majesty that we should look at him,
and no beauty that we should desire him.
- [3] He was despised and rejected by men,
a man of sorrows and acquainted with grief;
and as one from whom men hide their faces
he was despised, and we esteemed him not. (ESV)

These first three verses of Isaiah 53 are the beginning of one of the most cited Christological chapters in Isaiah, indeed in all of the Hebrew Scriptures. Paul quotes Isaiah 53:1 with this whole chapter in mind, and he knows that his hearers, believing Jews who are steeped in the same Scriptures, will immediately understand his reference. His conclusion that “hearing comes through the word of Christ” is a direct allusion to the rest of the material in Isaiah 53. The first part of v. 17 echoes the logical progression found in v. 15, but then adds the qualifier that, as stated in Isaiah 53, the hearing must be hearing specifically about Christ, the Anointed One of Israel.

Romans 10:18 - Verse 18 is the first of two follow-on challenges to the one presented in v. 16, which Paul will then address together in vv. 20 and 21. The first part is traditionally translated as the question, “But I ask, have they not heard?” This is answered with Psalm 19:4, referring to the “voice” and “words” of creation glorifying God, as indicated in Psalm 19:1-3:

- [1] The heavens declare the glory of God,
and the sky above proclaims his handiwork.
- [2] Day to day pours out speech,
and night to night reveals knowledge.

[3] There is no speech, nor are there words,
whose voice is not heard. (ESV)

While part of the Hebrew Scriptures, this psalm is generic in nature and echoes the natural theology found in Romans 1:20. This is a counterpoint to Paul's assertion in v. 17 that the hearers in question, the unbelieving non-Jewish Israelites called out at the beginning of chapter 9, need to specifically hear the "word of Christ." Verse 18 suggests otherwise - they have God's creation and that should suffice.

Romans 10:19 - This next challenge questions not the hearing of unbelieving Israelites but their understanding: "But I ask, did Israel not understand?" (ESV). The answer is drawn from Deuteronomy 32:21: "I will make you jealous of those who are not a nation; with a foolish nation I will make you angry." (ESV) How does this quotation answer the question concerning Israel's understanding? The traditional reading, of course, focuses not on the fact that this comes from the Song of Moses in Deuteronomy 32 and thus addresses all of Israel, but rather on the "foolish nation," reading this as a proof text for the inclusion of Gentiles into God's plan of salvation. But this reading does not account for the question at the beginning of v. 19. Read in context, Deut 32:21 describes God's reaction to the idolatry displayed by the people of Israel, as detailed in Deut 32:15-18. Verses 19 to 22 give a fuller picture of God's response:

[19] "The LORD saw it and spurned them,
because of the provocation of his sons and his daughters.
[20] And he said, 'I will hide my face from them;
I will see what their end will be,
for they are a perverse generation,
children in whom is no faithfulness.
[21] They have made me jealous with what is no god;
they have provoked me to anger with their idols.
So I will make them jealous with those who are no people;
I will provoke them to anger with a foolish nation.
[22] For a fire is kindled by my anger,
and it burns to the depths of Sheol,
devours the earth and its increase,
and sets on fire the foundations of the mountains. (ESV)

The answer to the rhetorical question “did Israel not understand?” is better understood by considering the comprehensive narrative at this point in the Song of Moses - the argument at this point in Romans is that Israel knew what would happen if they forsook God and followed idols. Like v. 18, this counterpoint does not refer to the Northern Kingdom of Israel but quotes a verse from the Pentateuch that applies to all Israel. We can make two observations based on this verse: 1) by quoting from Deuteronomy and regarding the context surrounding the quoted verse, we see that the argument in these verses keeps in play the idea of Israel writ large in chapter 10 and throughout Romans 9-11; 2) while staying focused on Israel, this argument is a generic assertion like that found in v. 18. These two verses together argue for (or against) the same thing - they minimize the need for the preaching of the gospel to any Israelite, and therefore also to the Israelites of the Northern Kingdom, claiming that they already know everything that they need. The underlying message is “let them be damned.”

Romans 10:20-21 - As mentioned above, these two verses are a response to the counterpoints presented in vv. 18 and 19. In both v. 20 and 21, Paul once again draws from Isaiah. Verse 20 cites the beginning of Isaiah 65:1: “I was ready to be sought by those who did not ask for me; I was ready to be found by those who did not seek me.” (ESV) This version quoted in Romans differs slightly from the Hebrew, following the LXX instead. Similar to Rom 9:25-26 and 10:19, the traditional interpretation of this verse reads Gentiles into this quote from Isaiah; however, I continue to suggest that the original context of Isaiah offers the best path to understanding Paul’s rhetoric.¹¹² Chapter 65 is the beginning of God’s response to the lament that begins at Isaiah 63:7 and continues through to the end of chapter 64. Who is he responding to and who is the object of 65:1? The author of Deutero-Isaiah is speaking on behalf of Judah, the Southern Kingdom,

¹¹² Hays, *Echoes of Scripture in the Letters of Paul*, 74-75; Hays supports the traditional reading.

however he also has in mind the Northern Kingdom Israelites, as demonstrated in 63:7:

[7] I will recount the steadfast love of the LORD,
 the praises of the LORD,
 according to all that the LORD has granted us,
 and the great goodness to the house of Israel
 that he has granted them according to his compassion,
 according to the abundance of his steadfast love. (ESV)

Just prior to diving into this lengthy lament, the author first addresses the Lord's "steadfast love," setting up parallel statements that distinguish the two different groups: he speaks of what God "has granted us," referring to the Judahites, and then specifically names the "house of Israel," referring to what God "has granted them." This us/them distinction clearly shows that "house of Israel" in this instance does not refer to all of Israel but to the Northern Kingdom; it also shows that the Northern Kingdom, while distinct from Judah, is still considered part of God's family, which is immediately confirmed by v. 8: "For he said, "Surely they are my people, children who will not deal falsely." Knowing this, we can return to the second question above - who is the object of 65:1? Both groups are in view, and there is nothing in the preceding lament that would lead us to select one over the other as the group that God was "ready to be sought by," so it is logical to assume that both kingdoms are the objects of 65:1 - and by extension, of Romans 10:20. It is interesting, then, that in Rom 10:21 Paul quotes the very next verse, Isaiah 65:2, but with a significant amplification:

[21] But of Israel he says, "All day long I have held out my hands to a disobedient and contrary people." (ESV)

While the original statement in Isaiah 65:2 does not specify who God is talking about, Paul explicitly states that it is Israel. Does Paul mean all twelve tribes of Israel, or the Northern Kingdom? The traditional view is compromised by the conflation of the terms Israel and Judah/Jew and considers this a reference to Jews. Assuming that Staples is correct concerning the Israel/Jew distinction, we must adjust our understanding. You can logically and rhetorically make

the case for either reading, Israel writ large or the Northern Kingdom based on the argument structure in Romans. However, given the context of Isaiah, I favor reading Paul's reference to Israel as indicating the Northern Kingdom. Given the flow of the rhetoric in Isaiah 63-65, I suggest that Paul is explicitly pulling forward the reference to "the house of Israel" found in 63:7, and once again strengthening his argument for the inclusion of Northern Kingdom Israelites in the new covenant, despite their past sins.

4.3. Romans Chapter 11

Finally, let us examine Romans 11:1-6 and Paul's rhetoric built on an exchange between God and Elijah (1 Kings 19:9-18) that takes place just after Elijah's battle with the priests of Baal on Mount Carmel. In v. 1 Paul states that God has not forsaken the people of Israel, of which he is one.¹¹³ As an example of God not forsaking his people, Paul argues:

Or do you not know in Elijah what the Scripture says, how he pleads to God against Israel? "Lord, they killed your prophets, they demolished your altars, and I myself alone am left; they even seek my life." But what does the divine oracle say to him? "I kept for myself seven thousand men, anyone who did not bow the knee to Baal." (vv. 2b-4, author's translation)

In Rom 11:3, responding to the assertion in 11:2 that Elijah prays against Israel, Paul quotes 1 Kings 19:10 and 14, where two times Elijah responds to God's question, "What are you doing here?" with this sentence. This quote seems to confirm that Elijah indeed was set against Israel; however, Paul follows it immediately with another rhetorical question to correct this assertion: "But [ἀλλὰ] what does the divine oracle say to him?" The immediate answer is a quote of 1 Kings 19:18, which shows, despite Elijah's protest, God will save 7,000 Israelites who are faithful to him. I would like to point out several obvious facts: Elijah is a Northern Kingdom prophet, who

¹¹³ See discussion above in section 2.2, "Paul's ethnic self-identification in Romans."

was directed by God to contend with the king of the Northern Kingdom of Israel, Ahab (1 Kings 18:1ff). The 7,000 Israelites that God promises to save are Northern Kingdom Israelites. These facts are explicit in the text of 1 Kings, and yet scholars as prominent as Richard Hays and N. T. Wright have chosen to not address these historical data points in the exegesis of this passage.¹¹⁴ As seen before in earlier passages and with other scholars, they conflate Israel with Judea/Jew and assume that Paul is making a generic argument about Jews and referring to them as Israel. I propose that, taken in isolation and also as a part of the larger argument in Romans 9-11, Paul uses these verses from 1 Kings to illustrate God's continuing faithfulness to non-Jewish Israelites from the former Northern Kingdom.

Now that we have sampled the Old Testament quotations in Romans 9-11 and examined the ethnic connections within those citations, both explicit in the quoted text and implicit due to the context from which each quote is drawn, I suggest once again that a strong case can be made for reading the Northern Kingdom of Israel as Paul's primary object of argument in these chapters and believing Jews as his primary interlocutors. With that, we must now turn our attention to the ethnic markers "Jew and Greek," found paired in Romans five times, and most anomalously in the middle of the three chapters we just covered at Rom 10:12.

5. "Jew and Greek" - Intra-Israelite Group Markers in Romans

We have examined Old Testament quotations in chapters 9 through 11 and reinterpreted Paul's use of them in light of their original context and the insight from Jason Staples's work that the terms "Jew" and "Israel" can no longer be treated as synonymous. Given these factors, we demonstrated that a strong case can be made for reading these chapters as a debate about Jews

¹¹⁴ Hays, *Echoes of Scripture in the Letters of Paul*, 68-70; Wright, *Paul and the Faithfulness of God*, 1222-1224.

from the Southern Kingdom and non-Jewish Israelites from the Northern Kingdom. As we follow along with Paul’s argument in these chapters, however, we see Paul using a familiar ethnic marker pairing that seems out of place. In Rom 10:12, Paul once again refers to “Jews and Greeks,” stating that there is no distinction between the two when it comes to salvation. Traditionally this phrase is taken to be a shorthand for referring to all peoples in the world, where “Jews” represent all Israel and “Greeks” represent all non-“Jewish” peoples from the other nations. We now know that this understanding will no longer do. How should we now interpret the phrase “Jews and Greeks”?

Allow me to engage in a thought experiment as we unpack the meanings of these group markers in relation to one another using Venn diagrams. First, let us show the traditional representation of “Jew” and “Greek” as just stated:

However, accepting the premise that “Jew” is not synonymous with “Israel,” we must conclude:

If
 “Jew” ≠ “Israel”
 then
 “Jew” + “Greek” ≠ “All people”

Since the term “Jews” cannot represent all of Israel, then assuming that the phrase “Jews and

Greeks” refers to all humanity leaves non-Jewish Israelites out of this group. Where are they?

To maintain the traditional view that “Jews and Greeks” represents all humanity, we have several options. The first and most accepted option, that “Jews” represents all Israel and therefore accounts for non-Jewish Israelites as well, has been taken away by Staples’s research and by the semantic logic presented above. There are two remaining options, neither of which is compelling and both of which are dispelled by the same evidence. The first of these two is that Northern Kingdom Israelites no longer exist and therefore can be excluded from any reckoning of “all humanity.” This, in fact, is an argument that is often made by biblical scholars when discussing the covenant of Israel and whether the northern tribes of Israel will return.¹¹⁵ It is its own brand of “replacement theology” to suggest that the Jews are now the only remnant of Israel and thus represent all of Israel. However, the biblical record, both Old and New Testament, refutes this idea. Not only does scripture talk prophetically concerning the reconstitution of all twelve tribes

¹¹⁵ Dunn, *Romans 9-16*, 575; Staples, *The Idea of Israel*; Staples cites several authors who advocate this line of thinking: William J. Dumbrell, 84, footnote 11; Gordon McConville, 124; John Collins, 57.

of Israel, but the New Testament and other Second Temple literature refer to actual people who are identified as members of various northern tribes.¹¹⁶ They exist, therefore they must be accounted for in any reckoning of “all humanity.” The second of these options is that all Northern Kingdom Israelites were subsumed into the “nations” and no longer have status as Israelites, and thus can be counted among “the Greeks,” which purportedly represents all non-Jewish peoples. Again, the literature will not allow for this interpretation for the same reason given above - Northern Kingdom Israelites are still identified as such in the New Testament and in other contemporary Jewish and Christian writings.

If we cannot account for non-Jewish Israelites in our “all humanity” understanding of the pairing “Jews and Greeks,” then we must abandon this understanding and find another more suitable. If we accept that the phrase “Jews and Greeks” represents a superset that includes both named groups, and we know that term “Jews” does not represent all of Israel but a part of Israel, then one suggestion (based on logic alone at this point) is that “Jews and Greeks” might be shorthand for “all Israel” rather than “all humanity”:

Given Paul’s use of the phrase “Jews and Greeks” in the middle of his argument concerning the inclusion of Northern Kingdom Israelites as evidenced by the OT quotes in chapters 9 through

¹¹⁶ Tobit 1:2, 7:3; Judith 6:15; Luke 2:36.

11, this new proposed understanding makes internal logical sense. As we step back and consider these two terms more broadly, it also makes logical sense that there would be a group marker for non-Jewish Israelites just as there is a group marker for Southern Kingdom Israelites, the “Jews.” The Hebrew Scriptures are definitive in their use of the term “Israel” to refer to the Northern Kingdom in the divided monarchy, even while continuing to use the name to refer to all twelve tribes of Israel in aggregate as a unified entity, either in the united monarchy of the past or in the eschatological future. Even if it were determined after investigation that “Greek” was not a group marker indicating those Israelites from the Northern Kingdom, we should still expect and be looking for another group marker to represent them in the literature. As just noted, however, I suggest that “Greek” is that expected group marker.

I will include additional semantic evidence below (“Excursus: Israelites and Name Calling”) both from the first century literature and also from modern day examples. But first we must ask, does reading “Greeks” as a group marker for Northern Kingdom Israelites also make exegetical sense when we examine the pairing of “Jew and Greek” in the rest of Romans, as well as the rest of Paul’s corpus and the New Testament, and when we look at the use of the term “Greek” on its own in various other places in the contemporary literature? The balance of this section will attempt to answer these questions.

5.1. “Jews” and “Greeks” in Romans

The pairing of the terms “Jew” and “Greek” in Romans occurs five times - four times in the singular and once in the plural.¹¹⁷ In all five instances, if you replace the traditional understanding of this pairing as representing “all humanity” with the new understanding that these terms represent “all Israel” in the aggregate, this exegesis not only makes sense of the

¹¹⁷ Rom 1:16, 2:9, 2:10, 3:9 (plural), 10:12.

surrounding argument in each section of the letter, but strengthens the logic of the rhetoric in the letter as a whole. Rom 1:16 will be discussed in the “Synthesis” section below (section 6.2, “The Thesis of Romans and Paul’s Ethnic Argument”), and Rom 10:12 was previously discussed in section 4.2 above. Let us examine the other three occurrences:

Rom 2:9-10: These two verses follow the discussion in chapter 1 and the beginning of chapter 2 concerning who is righteous and unrighteous:

There will be tribulation and distress for every human being who does evil, the Jew first and also the Greek, 10 but glory and honor and peace for everyone who does good, the Jew first and also the Greek. (ESV)

Paul completes the idea in these two verses by declaring that “there is no partiality with God.” What quickly follows is a discussion on Torah (νόμος). There has been much ink spilt recently over the Jewish law and whether Paul thinks Gentiles should ever be held to that standard. Most recent scholars agree that the answer is no (see the discussion below in section 5.2.1, “The Group Marker ‘Greek’ and Circumcision”). I concur with this stance, and suggest that placement of these “Jew and Greek” statements in the middle of a discussion concerning the law strengthens the case for considering both “Jew” and “Greek” as intra-Israelite markers.

Rom 3:9: Here again is another instance where the Jew/Greek dichotomy is embedded within a discussion of law:

What then? Are we Jews any better off? No, not at all. For we have already charged that all, both Jews and Greeks, are under sin...

Paul follows this statement (vv. 10-18) with a list of incriminations quoted from Psalms, before concluding:

Now we know that whatever the law says it speaks to those who are under the law, so that every mouth may be stopped, and the whole world may be held accountable to God.

Again, as in Rom 2:9-10, a discussion of the Torah suggests that the subjects of this debate are

people eligible to participate in the covenant, i.e., Israelites, whether Jew or non-Jewish Israelites, here referred to as “Greeks.”

It could be argued that in each of these five occurrences, my assertions are just that and nothing more, with no more support than the traditional view. Aside from pointing to the surrounding context for each passage and insisting upon its Israelite/covenantal nature, my opponents on this point would be correct. And so we must go to other sources to demonstrate this particular use of the term “Greek” as an intra-Israelite group identifier for non-Jewish Israelites primarily from the former Northern Kingdom.

5.2. “Jews” and “Greeks” in the New Testament

As we look across the New Testament, we find the pairing of “Jew” and “Greek” (both in the singular and plural) in several letters in the Pauline corpus as well as in Acts.¹¹⁸ In addition to those found in Romans, there are four occurrences in 1 Corinthians (1:22, 1:24, 10:32, 12:13, all in the plural), as well as Galatians 3:28 and Colossians 3:11 (both in the singular). In Acts, we find this pairing five times (14:1, 18:4, 19:10, 19:17, 20:21, all plural). As in the traditional reading of Romans, all these occurrences are understood as signifying Israel writ large and all Gentiles, thus all the people in a particular locale. Once again, without exegeting each passage, I claim that you could read these terms as referring to Israelites only, “Jews” from the Southern Kingdom and “Greeks” for non-Jewish Israelites (primarily from the Northern Kingdom), and still make sense of the narrative and rhetoric of the surrounding text based on the internal logic of the section alone. However, this realization will not solve the difference of opinion between these two views. To do that, we must delve into the use of the term “Greek” in the New

¹¹⁸ There is one indirect pairing of these terms in the gospel of John, 7:35, where the Jews are discussing the Greeks.

Testament and see if we can determine its meaning in context. We will do this by examining the juxtaposition of “Greek” with the concept of circumcision in the curious cases of Timothy and Titus.

5.2.1. The Group Marker “Greek” and Circumcision

Scholars have long debated the Jewish practice of circumcision as found in the stories of Timothy and Titus in the New Testament, and that debate continues today undeterred. The texts in question are Acts 16, verses 1 and 3, and Galatians 2, verse 3. Let us see how we might use the practice of circumcision to better understand the use of the group marker “Greek” by analyzing these two passages together. Here are the three verses in question:

Acts 16:1: Paul went on also to Derbe and to Lystra, where there was a disciple named Timothy, the son of a Jewish woman who was a believer; but his father was a Greek. (NRSV)

Acts 16:3: Paul wanted Timothy to accompany him; and he took him and had him circumcised because of the Jews who were in those places, for [γὰρ] they all knew that his father was a Greek. (NRSV)

Galatians 2:3: Yet not even [οὐδὲ] Titus, who was with me, being a Greek, was compelled to be circumcised. (NKJV)

5.2.1.1. Paul’s View of Gentiles and Circumcision

Because I am arguing that a distinction must be made between the terms “Greek” and “Gentile,” it is important to understand what Paul’s views on circumcision are for various groups. As we begin to consider the Apostle Paul’s stance on Gentile circumcision, it is noteworthy that each of the scholars listed below affirms that the views of Gentile circumcision within the Jewish/Israelite covenant community are many and varied. Their view of Paul’s approach to circumcision, however, is consistent:

Paul insisted that Christ-following non-Jews remain non-Jews, and thus remain uncircumcised and not “under” Torah, but his arguments—and “the rule” that he says he upholds for all of his assemblies (1 Cor 7:17–20)—logically require that Christ-following Jews remain Jews, and thus, it follows, they remain “under” Torah, and would still, by

definition, circumcise their sons. (Mark Nanos)¹¹⁹

Paul's gospel did not free gentiles from needing to keep the Jewish law: according to Paul and many of his contemporary Jews, gentiles never needed to keep it. (Matthew Thiessen)¹²⁰

Therefore, when Paul speaks against Law observance, he speaks against non-Pauline construals of gentile Judaizing, not against Jewish Torah observance; and when he speaks against circumcision, he speaks against the circumcision of gentiles, not of Jews. (Paula Fredriksen)¹²¹

... Paul did not believe that circumcision could turn a non-Jew into a Jew, nor that it offers the non-Jew any benefit. (Ryan Collman)¹²²

Mark Nanos writes that “Paul insisted that Christ-following non-Jews remain non-Jews, and thus remain uncircumcised and not “under” Torah,” while “Christ-following Jews remain Jews,” and thus should continue to “circumcise their sons.” Matthew Thiessen states that “Paul’s gospel did not free gentiles from needing to keep the Jewish law: according to Paul and many of his contemporary Jews, gentiles never needed to keep it.” Paula Fredriksen says that Paul “speaks against the circumcision of gentiles, not of Jews.” Ryan Collman concurs that “Paul did not believe that circumcision could turn a non-Jew into a Jew, nor that it offers the non-Jew any benefit.” While Paul held a very specific view of Gentile circumcision, he was not alone in holding this particular view – other Jews espoused Paul’s line of reasoning as well.

Acknowledging, then, that Paul argued against Gentile circumcision – what are we to make of the circumcision of Timothy, as recounted in Acts 16, verses 1 to 3, the first of the two passages we are considering?

¹¹⁹ Nanos, *Reading Paul within Judaism*, “Preface,” location 241.

¹²⁰ Matthew Thiessen, *Paul and the Gentile Problem* (New York: Oxford University Press 2016), 161.

¹²¹ Paula Fredriksen, *Paul: The Pagan’s Apostle* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2017, Kindle Edition), chapter 4, location 2515.

¹²² Ryan Collman, *The Apostle to the Foreskin: Circumcision in the Letters of Paul* (Berlin: De Gruyter, 2023), 156.

5.2.1.2. *The Circumcision of Timothy*

As we consider the case of Paul's circumcision of Timothy, the immediate question that presents itself is why: what was Paul's logic in proceeding with this Jewish ritual, given the confusing nature of Timothy's heritage? We turn again to our previously cited scholars:

In [Acts] 15:30 and 16:4, Paul represents the Jerusalem church decision that gentiles are to observe the apostolic decree, and in 16:1–13 [sic], he circumcises Timothy. (Nanos)¹²³

Depending on how one determines genealogy, one could argue that Timothy was either a Jew or a Gentile. Some may see Timothy as a Jew, and Luke shows how careful Paul is to require circumcision in this sort of liminal case. (Thiessen)¹²⁴

The child of a Jewish father and a gentile mother would be a Jew, just as the child of a gentile father and a Jewish mother would be a non-Jew. (For this reason, the story in Acts 16.1–3 that Paul circumcised Timothy, whose father was a gentile, has confounded commentators.) (Fredriksen)¹²⁵

While I think Phil 3:3 indicates that Paul understood Timothy to be a Jew (at least for his own rhetorical purposes), the presentation in Acts 16:1 – 3 is problematic... (Collman)¹²⁶

Nanos references the circumcision of Timothy in a footnote while arguing for the strict Torah observance of Paul. Here he seems to indicate that Timothy is a Jew, presumably based on the matrilineal descent referred to in Acts 16:1. Thiessen highlights the fact that Timothy, given his Jewish and "Gentile" (the text says "Greek") parentage, could be considered "either a Jew or a Gentile." Because "some may see Timothy as a Jew," Thiessen states that "Luke shows how careful Paul is to require circumcision in this sort of liminal case." Fredriksen debunks any Jewish acceptance of matrilineal descent, stating that a "child of a gentile father and a Jewish mother would be a non-Jew," then goes on to admit that Acts 16:1-3 "has confounded

¹²³ Nanos, *Reading Paul within Judaism*, chapter 3, footnote 169, location 3224; context indicates he meant to reference 16:1-3 vice 16:1-13.

¹²⁴ Thiessen, *Contesting Conversion* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2011), 121.

¹²⁵ Fredriksen, *Paul*, location 1278-1281.

¹²⁶ Collman, *The Apostle to the Foreskin*, 422 (footnote 88).

commentators.” Collman does not directly address Timothy’s circumcision, but he deals with it in a footnote where he states that “Acts 16:1-3 is problematic and worth a brief discussion.” The footnote then continues for three pages. He cites the work of Shaye Cohen, who also shoots down the notion of matrilineal descent and does not believe that Luke thought he was “recounting the circumcision of a Jew”; he also cites Thiessen’s proposal just cited above, along with several others. In the face of this evidence, Collman writes: “If Luke’s account is historically accurate, it seems that Paul would have deemed Timothy to be a Jew—or at least Jew-ish. In light of Paul’s self-presentation in his epistles, it is highly unlikely that he would have knowingly performed a circumcision upon a non-Jew based on external pressure.”¹²⁷ Collman, like the rest, accepts the tension of the passage, noting the inconsistencies, and moves on. The conclusion of these NT scholars, notwithstanding the difficulties and seeming paradoxes of the passage, is that Paul determined that Timothy was “Jewish enough,” based on his mother’s ethnicity, to be circumcised.¹²⁸ In this understanding, Paul’s action is in response to the expectation of the Jews (16:3) that a male of Jewish descent (even if through the lineage of the mother) should follow the Torah, including circumcision.

This position is in sharp contrast to many of the church fathers and their “medieval continuators.”¹²⁹ Cohen lists Tertullian, Clement of Alexandria, Origen, John Chrysostom, Jerome, and Augustine as all assuming that Timothy was a gentile, albeit with different

¹²⁷ Collman, *The Apostle to the Foreskin*, 424 (footnote 88); Shaye Cohen, “Was Timothy Jewish (Acts 16:1 – 3)? Patristic Exegesis, Rabbinic Law, and Matrilineal Descent,” *JBL* 105 [1986]. Collman’s entire discussion in this footnote is germane.

¹²⁸ E.g., Wright, *Paul and the Faithfulness of God*, 362 and 455 (footnote 37); Ben Witherington, *Grace in Galatia: A Commentary on Paul’s Letter to the Galatians* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 1998), 373.

¹²⁹ Shaye J. D. Cohen, *The Beginnings of Jewishness: Boundaries, Varieties, Uncertainties* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1999, Kindle Edition), Appendix D, “Was Timothy Jewish?”, 363-377.

explanations of Paul's behavior in 16:1-3. None from this group even consider Timothy's mother's Jewishness when attempting to explain Paul's actions, but rather they focus on the expectation of the Jews mentioned in 16:3 as the driving factor. Contra this group, the views of Ambrosiaster, Nicalaus of Lyra, and Thomas Aquinas do count his mother's Jewish lineage as the reason for Paul's insistence on circumcision. Cohen, having dedicated 15 pages in an appendix to this topic, concludes:

Was Timothy Jewish? In all likelihood Luke did not think so. The vast majority of ancient and medieval exegetes did not think so. Ambrosiaster and his medieval followers did think so, but in all likelihood this interpretation is wrong because there is no evidence that any Jew in pre-mishnaic times thought that the offspring of an intermarriage follows the status of the mother. Was Timothy Jewish? The answer must be no.

Cohen seems to stand alone in his conviction that Timothy was not Jewish, were it not for the witness of a host of church fathers. Even so, he admits (in footnote 35 of this appendix) that despite this conviction, "even if Timothy is to be considered a gentile, the reference to the Jewishness of his mother is not irrelevant."

The bottom line to this discussion is that Timothy's ethnicity is not settled in the text, and exegetes past and present still wrestle with the ambiguities of this text, taking sides in either the "Timothy was a Jew" camp or the "Timothy was a gentile" camp. Both of these options are viable, given the textual material available. However, I am suggesting a "third way" of viewing Timothy's genealogy that I have not found described by any other exegete to date, but that I think is just as viable: Timothy, described as a "Greek," was a non-Jewish Israelite, part of the Israelite diaspora, raised with Gentile influences. While I have not found this exegesis elsewhere, Cohen seems to cite a conversation he had with J. Louis Martyn, wherein Martyn gets close to the model that I am proposing:

Prof. J. Louis Martyn suggests to me that Luke imagines that the early Christians confront a world consisting of three groups: Jews, gentiles, and those in between-i. e.,

"sympathizers," "God-fearers," and the like. Timothy, by virtue of his mixed lineage, is a member of this middle group. He is neither wholly a Jew nor wholly a gentile.¹³⁰

While Martyn does not mention non-Jewish Israelites, I humbly submit that a gentilized, formerly apostate Israelite with ethnic ties to one of the tribes from the former Northern Kingdom of Israel qualifies as an appropriate example of one of these “in between” groups that Luke imagines.

5.2.1.3. *The Non-Circumcision of Titus*

Now we turn to our second passage under consideration, Galatians 2:1-3, and specifically verse 3, which marks Titus as a “Greek.” In this section of Galatians, Paul is relating the story of his visit to the Jerusalem church leaders to discuss the gospel that he was proclaiming “among the Gentiles” to ensure he was not running “in vain” (2:2). Recounting to the Galatians that he had taken Titus with him, he reported that “even Titus, who was with me, was not forced to be circumcised, though he was a Greek” (2:3). How do our representative scholars understand Titus’s “Greekness”?

... the admission of Gentiles as equals (not just righteous Gentile associates) into the Jesus community or communities without proselytizing (i.e., Titus) ... (Nanos)¹³¹

Instead, and curiously, Paul reports that the Jerusalem leaders did not require his companion Titus to be circumcised “even though he was a Greek,” that is, a gentile. (Fredriksen)¹³²

Against these interpreters, I agree with Munck’s (*Paul and the Salvation*, 95) assessment of the supposed circumcision of Titus, “This interpretation is, of course, impossible, because it assumes that Paul consented to the circumcising of a baptized gentile—a thing that is out of the question.” (Collman)¹³³

¹³⁰ Cohen, *The Beginnings of Jewishness*, Appendix D, footnote 35.

¹³¹ Nanos, *The Irony of Galatians* (Minneapolis: Augsburg Fortress, 2002, Kindle Edition), 148.

¹³² Fredriksen, *Paul*, location 1812-1814.

¹³³ Collman, *The Apostle to the Foreskin*, 342.

Nanos, Fredriksen, and Collman definitively assume that Titus is a Gentile based on the group marker “Greek,” without further discussion. From there, each author discusses at length the debate over Titus’s circumcision found in Galatians 2 with the “pseudo-brothers.” Fredriksen enumerates a laundry list of possible reasons as to why there was a debate in the first place, before concluding “Whatever their [the false brethren’s] rationale, their motivation and their goal were, doubtless, to ensure the spread of the gospel.¹³⁴” Nanos speculates about the various political machinations of the “pseudo-brethren.” Collman, in a footnote, touches upon a minority view that Titus actually was circumcised, just not under compulsion; Collman’s own position, shared with Munck, is that this speculation is “impossible, because it assumes that Paul consented to the circumcising of a baptized gentile...” Thiessen does not discuss Titus’s non-circumcision, either in his two works previously quoted here or in any of his other recent works. Collman, Fredriksen, and Nanos all wrestle with the fact of the circumcision controversy in Galatians 2, but all three accept as given Titus’s “Gentileness” without question.¹³⁵

Knowing that I am proposing that “Greek” can be viewed as a group marker for non-Jewish Israelites, let us briefly examine the text of Galatians to see if anything would deny this reading. Probably the most compelling argument against my position might be raised from Gal 2:2 and the fact that Paul specifically calls out the gospel he is proclaiming to the Gentiles as the focal point of the story. “Greek” and “Gentile” must be synonymous due to the immediate context, so the logic goes. Recall from the previous section, however, that the non-Jewish Israelite I posit has his feet in both “camps” – an Israelite by genealogy, and a Gentile by

¹³⁴ Fredriksen, *Paul*, chapter 4, location 1977.

¹³⁵ E.g., Richard N. Longenecker, *Galatians*, Volume 41 (World Biblical Commentary) (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1990), 50; Douglas J. Moo, *Galatians* (Baker Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament) (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Publishing Group, 2013, Kindle Edition), 218.

upbringing and culture. Therefore, this “Greek” should be considered a subset of “Gentile,” as much as he is a subset of Israel (more on this below in section 5.4, “Greeks” as “Gentiles”).

Therefore, to paraphrase Paul’s rhetoric in vv. 1-3, “I went to the leaders in Jerusalem to discuss the gospel I was proclaiming to the Gentiles; I even had Titus with me – a Greek! – and not even he was compelled to get circumcised!” Both the traditional view of Titus as a Gentile “proper” (no Israelite ethnicity) and my view of Titus as a non-Jewish Israelite still work here; my intention is to show in the next section how my reading might be considered as the more plausible of the two.

5.2.1.4. *“Greeks” and Circumcision – Timothy and Titus*

Now that we have examined these two passages separately, what information can we garner by analyzing them together? In the case of Timothy, Paul has him circumcised because “they [the Jews] all knew his father was a Greek” (Acts 16:3). In the case of Titus, Paul’s refusal to have him circumcised is set against the fact that Titus is Greek – “not even Titus... being a Greek” (Galatians 2:3). In both cases, there is an *expectation* that “Greeks” are meant to be circumcised, contra the *expectation* of non-circumcision held for “Gentiles” (an expectation set for Gentiles in Acts 15 at the Jerusalem Council). Because of these expectations, Timothy and Titus, both identified as “Greeks,” can both be plausibly understood as some sort of Israelite, genealogically tied to the covenants of Israel, which include circumcision.

The immediate push back on this proposal is that this same expectation is present in the traditional views of Timothy and Titus. In Galatians, exegetes will rightly point out that the “false brethren” propagated the expectation that Gentiles must be circumcised, and this is indeed what Paul was combatting in his rhetoric of the letter. However, I assert that this is not the expectation in view in v. 3. Paul, in relaying the non-circumcision of Titus in Jerusalem, is

implying that there was an “expected expectation” by his audience in Galatians (the letter recipients, not the “false brethren”) that the Jerusalem leaders would want Titus, as a “Greek,” to be circumcised; however, Paul subverts this expectation when he reports that Titus was indeed not compelled to be circumcised – “But not even Titus” (ἀλλ’ οὐδὲ Τίτος). This is akin to a rhetorical “preemptive strike” by Paul against the expectation of Gentile circumcision by the “false brethren” voiced in vv. 4-5.

The argument against my case in Acts 16 is a bit more complex, since there are two traditional views of Timothy's ethnicity, either “Jew” or “Gentile.” For those subscribing to the “Gentile” view, the explanation of the Jewish expectation of Timothy’s circumcision (16:2) must lean completely on the assumption that Paul was acting expediently to avoid Jewish ardor against Gentiles for “disrespecting” their traditions.¹³⁶ Also, this view completely ignores the events of Acts 15 immediately prior to this vignette, where the Jerusalem counsel formally notified the believers at Antioch, including Paul, that Gentile circumcision was not required. This stance is even more problematic when you consider the text of Acts 16:4:

As they went on their way through the cities, they delivered to them for observance the decisions that had been reached by the apostles and elders who were in Jerusalem. (ESV)

If Paul thought Timothy was a Gentile, why circumcise him just prior to visiting cities to announce that circumcision was not required for Gentiles? In addition, this position opens up a host of other quandaries with respect to Paul’s apparent inconsistent theology and/or praxis, or worse his supposed “hypocrisy and mendacity.”¹³⁷ For those subscribing to the “Jewish” view of Timothy, the expectations of the Jews on the surface might be easier to support due to Timothy’s

¹³⁶ Cohen, *The Beginnings of Jewishness*, Appendix C, locations 3898-3900.

¹³⁷ Cohen, *The Beginnings of Jewishness*, Appendix D, locations 3885-3890.

Jewish mother, but they must contend with all those who point out that matrilineal descent was not recognized in the first century.

All of the traditional views for the ethnicity of Timothy and Titus, based on their identification as “Greeks,” are still plausible positions to take, but each has its problems. However, positing non-Jewish Israelite backgrounds for both Timothy and Titus makes logical sense of the available data with fewer attendant issues. Timothy, as a non-Jewish Israelite, could be circumcised by Paul as someone who had rights to the covenant of Israel; Titus, as a non-Jewish Israelite, could avoid circumcision as someone who, though of Israelite blood, had been raised as a Gentile and therefore not currently following the covenant of Israel, and thus could be used as a “super exemplar” by Paul as the person most likely to be directed by the Jerusalem leadership to be circumcised because of his Israelite lineage, and yet was not.

Thus, my first proposed conclusion from this investigation: “Greeks” are Israelites (in some sense). They are genealogically Israelites, physically descended from one of the twelve tribes of Israel, who by blood rights belong to the covenant, but who are not practicing their ancestral religion in the same way as the Jews, spanning the spectrum from worshipping Yahweh to worshipping other gods/idols and everything in between. This leads to my second proposed conclusion: “Greeks” are not “Gentiles” (in some sense). As ethnic Israelites, they are part of the diaspora, living *in* the nations while never *becoming* the nations, and yet following the cultural norms of the nations where they reside in a variety of ways and to varying degrees, which can result in a debate with others on whether they are actually “Gentiles” (I will unpack each of these assertions further in section 5.4 and in the “Synthesis” section below).

5.3. “Greeks” in the Works of Josephus

I will demonstrate below that it is plausible that Josephus used the group marker “Greeks” in his

writings to refer to non-Jewish Israelites, with the reminder that this intra-Israelite reading is always based on context and that there are places within each of these works where “Greeks” may also be used to refer to groups of ethnic Greeks or other non-Israelite people.¹³⁸ Accounting for the high-context nature of the Greek language and first century literature allows us to see the nuance applied to the use of this and other similar group markers in different situations. Having said that, it is time for a brief side quest to answer the initial question: what evidence do we have that Jews/Israelites used what appear to be generic geographical markers to refer to themselves?

5.3.1. *Excursus: Israelites and “Name Calling”*

We do have evidence, specifically in the works of Josephus, that demonstrates the use of geographical/cultural group markers being applied to Israelites in various situations, which we will examine here. However, let us consider another closely related question first, and that is, “if this assertion is true, why do we not see more explanations of this behavior in the Scriptural texts?” The classic text that demonstrates such an explicit definition is Acts 11:26, where we find the statement “and in Antioch the disciples were first called Christians” (ESV). While this is not a geographical marker, the implication is the same: why is the use of “Greeks” not similarly

¹³⁸ An example of the polysemy of the word “Greek” is this excerpt from the preface of Josephus’s *The Jewish War* ((Josephus, *The Jewish War: Books 1–7*, ed. Jeffrey Henderson et al., trans. H. St. J. Thackeray, vol. 1, Loeb Classical Library (Cambridge, MA; London; New York: Harvard University Press; William Heinemann Ltd; G. P. Putnam’s Sons, 1927–1928), 11.):

For myself, at a vast expenditure of money and pains, I, a foreigner, present to Greeks and Romans this memorial of great achievements. As for the native Greeks, where personal profit or a lawsuit is concerned, their mouths are at once agape and their tongues loosed; but in the matter of history, where veracity and laborious collection of the facts are essential, they are mute, leaving to inferior and ill-informed writers the task of describing the exploits of their rulers. Let us at least hold historical truth in honour, since by the Greeks it is disregarded.

Here we see Josephus invoke the term Ἕλληνας two times; the second occurrence of “Greeks” in the translation is an interpolation. It is possible that when Josephus refers to “Greeks and Romans,” he is claiming to write for other Israelites who, not being in league with the Jews during the Jewish/Roman War, were not aware of the details, along with the Romans, his new masters. He then gives the reason that he must step into this role of historian: the “native Greeks” (γνησίους, “the true/authentic ones”) ignore writing history because it is not profitable monetarily; this is echoed at the end of the passage, “Let us at least hold historical truth in honour, since by the Greeks it is disregarded.”

defined in the New Testament if it has a meaning other than referring to all people sharing a Greek cultural heritage (which is then conflated with the idea of “Gentile”)? The simple explanation is that the term “Greek” in this application was already in use during the Second Temple Period and beyond, and therefore the intended readers (and hearers) were already aware of this usage. Immersed in their own culture with an existing set of shared definitions, there was no need for authors to define the term in their writings.

Even so, we do find explanations of this usage pattern in a few places, some direct and some indirect, as we expand our gaze beyond the writings of the New Testament and look to other first century Jewish texts, specifically the works of Josephus. The first example and most obvious to consider is the use of the term “Jew” (Ἰουδαῖος). As readers of the New Testament, we are very familiar with this group marker and its English translation as “Jew”; however, there is a debate today among scholars concerning the most appropriate translation, some now opting for “Judean” as a more appropriate rendering, which brings out the geographic character of the original Greek word. There are a number of factors contributing to this discussion, including whether the use of this word implies geography or culture or a mixture of the two. To the point, however, is that these disagreements are compounded by the fact that the New Testament texts do not define the term explicitly for their audiences. However, when we turn to Josephus, we find that he indeed defines the term in *The Antiquities of the Jews*, as Jason Staples points out as he debunks the traditional view that “Israel” and “Jew” are “insider” and “outsider” group markers respectively:¹³⁹

It would of course be absurd to conclude that this terminological shift is because Josephus wrote the first eleven books of *Antiquities* to an insider audience but the rest of his corpus for outsiders. Instead, Josephus not only shifts from Israelite to *Ioudaios* at a

¹³⁹ Staples does a great job recounting the history of the insider/outsider reading in Part I of *The Idea of Israel*, 25ff.

specific point in his history but also gives a specific explanation for why he does so:

From the time they went up from Babylon they were called by this name [*Ioudaios*] after the tribe of Judah. As the tribe was the prominent one to come from those parts, both the people themselves and the country have taken their name from it. (Ant.11.173)¹⁴⁰

In this excerpt from Book 11 of *Antiquities*, we see the parallel with Acts 11:26 and the marking of the use of the term “Christians.” Josephus, writing in the second half of the first century, was also “swimming in the water” of Jewish culture; and yet, because he was documenting the longer history of Israel in this work, he explicitly marks the beginning of the use of the term Ἰουδαῖος and in so doing defines it for his readers and for us in the 21st century. He also makes the connection between the people and the specific land, both of which share the name of Judah.

This pattern of referring to Israelites/Jews by geographical group markers shows up in other places in Josephus’s corpus. Book 19 of *Antiquities* recounts how Claudius deals with an uprising between the Jews in Alexandria, Egypt, and their “Greek” counterparts. Josephus records an edict sent by Claudius to Alexandria:

"Tiberius Claudius Caesar Augustus Germanicus, high priest, and tribune of the people, ordains thus: Since I am assured that *the Jews of Alexandria, called Alexandrians*, have been joint inhabitants in the earliest times with the Alexandrians... (italics added)

By including a record of this edict, Josephus has defined for us (intentionally or unintentionally) the term “Alexandrian” with reference to the Jewish population of that city, while at the same time showing us the inherent ambiguity of such a term by including in the same sentence a reference to “Alexandrians” who are not Jews.

Finally, in *Against Apion*, Josephus refutes the claims of Apion that Jews are not true citizens of Alexandria, and in so doing gives us the most concrete explanation of this practice of

¹⁴⁰ Staples, *The Idea of Israel*, 45.

naming Jews/Israelites in the diaspora by the city in which they dwell:

His astonishment at the idea of Jews being called Alexandrians betrays similar stupidity. All persons invited to join a colony, however different their nationality, take the name of the founders. It is needless to go outside our race for instances. Our Jewish residents in Antioch are called Antiochenes, having been granted rights of citizenship by its founder, Seleucus. Similarly, those at Ephesus and throughout the rest of Ionia bear the same name as the indigenous citizens, a right which they received from Alexander's successors. Have not the Romans, in their generosity, imparted their name to well-nigh all mankind, not to individuals only, but to great nations as a whole? Thus those who were once Iberians, Tyrrhenians, Sabines are now called Romans.¹⁴¹

Here we see the elements of a developed practice – not a “one off” naming of Jews as Alexandrians, but a detailed explanation of how this happens in other cities as well. Even more compelling for our current discussion concerning the term “Greeks” is Josephus’s description of the application of the name “Romans” “not to individuals only, but to great *nations as a whole*” (italics added). The former Northern Kingdom of Israel was a separate nation in the divided monarchy of ancient Israel; is it not feasible that they too might have been referred to by an “empire” marker, but in this case the marker is “Greeks”?

To wrap up this excursus, let us consider modern-day equivalents to this practice of Jews/Israelites referring to themselves by the name of a geographic location, especially one not associated with the land of Israel. I can supply three contemporary analogs. These three terms – Ashkenazim, Sephardim, and Mizrahim – all originate as place and/or people group names in the Hebrew language, and yet Jews/Israelites use them today to refer to their own people living in or coming from those regions:

Ashkenazim: “Germanic” (Jews from the European continent, originally ruled by German kings in the Holy Roman Empire)

Sephardim: “Spanish” (Jews from the Iberian peninsula)

Mizrahim: “Eastern” (Jews living in Muslim countries, typically “east” of Israel)

I am aware that there are issues with the use of these terms within modern Israeli culture, just as I

¹⁴¹ Josephus, *Against Apion*, 2.4.38-40.

know there are challenges of self-identification within my own Filipino culture. The purpose of making this comparison is to highlight the similarities in the semantic practice of using place names within Jewish culture to self-identify with no additional ethnic qualifiers. As we continue to explore the works of Josephus, we will see how the use of the group marker “Greeks” fits into this model as a designation for non-Jewish (primarily Northern Kingdom) Israelites.

5.3.2. “Greeks” in *The Jewish War and Against Apion*

Having provided evidence from the works of Josephus of the practice of Jews/Israelites referring to themselves by the names of other nations, we might stop there and claim victory, making the logical leap that “Greek” can now be understood to mean “Israelite” in some sense in certain contexts. However, our case would be stronger indeed if Josephus himself provided an example of such an explanation of the usage of the term “Greek.” And so he does, in a roundabout way.

An often-untapped area of research are the prefaces to Josephus’s works, which is where we find the following excerpt. In the preface to *The Jewish Wars*, Josephus explains at length why he is undertaking the writing of such a history: in large part, it is to correct the errors or outright lies of those who have attempted to document the events of the war before him. Having accomplished this goal in the first half of the preface, he goes on in the second half to delineate what he intends to include (and not include) in his account:

To narrate the ancient history of the Jews, the origin of the nation and the circumstances of their migration from Egypt, the countries which they traversed in their wanderings, the extent of the territory which they subsequently occupied, and the incidents which led to their deportation, would, I considered, be not only here out of place, but superfluous; seeing that many Jews before me have accurately recorded the history of our ancestors, and that these records have been translated by certain *Greeks* into their native tongue without serious error.¹⁴² (emphasis added)

¹⁴² Josephus, *The Jewish War: Books 1–7*, ed. Jeffrey Henderson et al., trans. H. St. J. Thackeray, vol. 1, Loeb Classical Library (Cambridge, MA; London; New York: Harvard University Press; William Heinemann Ltd; G. P. Putnam’s Sons, 1927–1928), 11.

Here we find “Jews” and “Greeks” mentioned together and distinguished from one another. From this text alone, you might argue that there is nothing to suggest that “Greeks” as used in this instance refers to non-Jewish Israelites, and you would be correct. However, Josephus provides additional detail for this claim in *Against Apion*, as pointed out in a footnote on this excerpt by Thackeray in the Loeb Classical Library edition, in which Thackeray says who these “Greeks” were:

An allusion to the works of Demetrius, Philo the elder, Eupolemus, etc.; cf. Ap. i. 218, where Josephus speaks in the same terms. Subsequently he thought that these earlier works still left room for a new “archaeology” (A. i. proem).¹⁴³

In this section of *Against Apion* that Thackeray references, Josephus is combating the claim that the Jewish race is not all that ancient (the first century version of genealogical snobbery - the older your people are, the more clout you have). In the midst of his argument, he lists a number of historical records that include evidence of the antiquity of the Jewish/Israelite people, while at the same time poking the authors of those work in the collective eye for getting their history wrong:

The majority of these authors have misrepresented the facts of our primitive history, because they have not read our sacred books; [217] but all concur in testifying to our antiquity, and that is the point with which I am at present concerned. Demetrius Phalereus, the elder Philo, and Eupolemus are exceptional in their approximation to the truth, [218] and [their errors] may be excused on the ground of their inability to follow quite accurately the meaning of our records.¹⁴⁴

The three people called out - Demetrius Phalereus, Philo the elder, and Eupolemus - are all identified as “Jews” by Eusebius. Writing in his *Ecclesiastical History* in the 4th century and defending the antiquity of the Jewish race just as Josephus had done, he summarizes excerpts

¹⁴³ Josephus, *The Jewish War: Books 1–7*, Book 1, paragraph 6, line 17, footnote b.

¹⁴⁴ Josephus, *The Life, Against Apion*, ed. T. E. Page et al., trans. H. J. Thackeray, vol. I, The Loeb Classical Library (London; Cambridge, MA: William Heinemann Ltd; Harvard University Press, 1966), 251.

from Clement of Alexandria's *Stromateis*:

And in them he has also made use of testimonies from the disputed writings, the book known as *the Wisdom of Solomon*, and the *Wisdom of Jesus the Son of Sirach*, [7] and the *Epistle to the Hebrews*, and those of Barnabas, and Clement, and Jude; and he mentions Tatian's book *Against the Greeks*, and Cassian, since he also had composed a chronography, and moreover Philo and Aristobulus and Josephus and Demetrius and Eupolemus, Jewish writers, in that they would show, all of them, in writing, that Moses and the Jewish race went back further in their origins than the Greeks.¹⁴⁵

Eusebius's list of "Jewish writers" (which Josephus is counted among) contains the same three historians listed by Josephus in *Against Apion*. These three are representative of those "certain Greeks" that Josephus refers to in the preface to *The Jewish War*. By examining the body of Josephus's work (and with the help of Eusebius), we now see that Josephus has, in this instance, referred to these Jewish/Israelite authors as "Greeks," thus demonstrating the use of this ethnic/geographic term to refer to Israelites in intra-Israelite discourse.

5.4. "Greeks" as "Gentiles"

Can Ἕλλην still be considered equivalent with Gentiles in certain cases? In the extant literature of the first century, the short answer is yes, as demonstrated above in Josephus's writings (see footnote 131; I will give a slightly longer answer at the end of this section). Can Ἕλλην still be considered equivalent to Gentiles anywhere in the New Testament? My answer to this question is somewhat complex, to which this section is dedicated.

As I suggest in chapter 2, section 2.2, the term Ἕλλην is ambiguous, and neither the conventional interpretation of "Gentile" nor my proposed interpretation of "non-Jewish Israelite" can be proven correct (or falsified) in isolation; both alternatives require context be the primary

¹⁴⁵ Lake Kirsopp, "Preface," in *The Ecclesiastical History and 2: English Translation*, ed. T. E. Page et al., trans. Kirsopp Lake and J. E. L. Oulton, vol. 2, The Loeb Classical Library (London; New York; Cambridge, MA: William Heinemann; G. P. Putnam's Sons; Harvard University Press, 1926–1932), 45. Here we see Eusebius, writing approx. 240 years after Josephus, using the term "Greeks" to refer to people universally of Greek culture, demonstrating the polysemy of the word.

driver in interpretation. That said, my personal conviction is that in every occurrence in Romans, Ἕλληνα indicates non-Jewish Israelites. And in each of those instances, Ἕλληνα is referring to “Gentiles.” Allow me to explain.

The people of the tribes of the Northern Kingdom of Israel were either carried off to other lands by the neo-Assyrians or assimilated into the cultures of their conquerors, who populated the land of Israel with their own people.¹⁴⁶ Even prior to the neo-Assyrian conquest of the Northern Kingdom, the people were involved in idolatry and had “committed adultery” against God, and therefore had abandoned the covenant (see Hosea). Those who were deported to other nations had in effect become “Gentiles,” living among them and practicing their ways. And yet, even down to the first century, we see that some Northern Kingdom Israelites retained their tribal affiliations, and some continued to honor Yahweh (albeit in a syncretistic manner).¹⁴⁷ I suggest that these people lived daily in the tension of these two identifications (I hesitate to use the anachronistic term “ethnicities” here). This “double identity” could be used by those people to good effect, emphasizing one background or the other in conversation to their personal benefit. At the same time, opponents/adversaries could also use their double identity against them, likewise emphasizing one background or the other to their detriment. I believe this double identity is responsible for the complexity of the arguments we see in Romans with regard to the application of the Torah to these “gentilized” non-Jewish Israelites. If you accept my alternative interpretation of Ἕλληνα, I assert that this double identity of Israelite/not Israelite, Gentile/not Gentile is in play whenever Paul uses the term in Romans. And I humbly submit that this is the case throughout the New Testament when Ἕλληνα is used, but alas the limits of this paper require

¹⁴⁶ 2 Kings 17:1-34; Hill and Walton, 583.

¹⁴⁷ Tobit 1:2, 7:3; Judith 6:15; Luke 2:36.

that I leave that discussion for another time.

Now I return to the question of whether Ἕλληνας in other first century texts like Josephus can still refer to “Gentiles.” The answer I gave was “yes,” but now I will qualify that answer slightly. Because the majority of non-Jewish Israelites became “Gentiles” in some sense, as just discussed, then whenever Josephus uses Ἕλληνας to refer to Gentiles generically, we can assume that within that group there is always the potential for the presence of a subset of the non-Jewish Israelites just mentioned. This point may seem academic, but it reveals once again the complexity of the term Ἕλληνας and the ambiguity inherent in its use. I repeat that the exegesis of this word is completely dependent on context, for both the traditional view and for my proposed view.

5.5. “Jews and Greeks” vs. “Jews and Israel”

I have presented evidence above, both logical and semantic, to support the assertion that the term “Greek” has been used in the New Testament and other texts contemporary with it to refer to non-Jewish Israelites. I have included in my assumptions that this group marker is referring primarily to Israelites of the former Northern Kingdom of Israel. Up until fairly recently, I was much more dogmatic about the division between the terms “Jew” and “Greek,” stating that the former referred specifically to Southern Kingdom Israelites from the former kingdom of Judah and the latter to Northern Kingdom Israelites from the former kingdom of Israel. My continued research of the primary sources as well as the experience of daily life has taught me that I must nuance this view slightly. We have stories in the extant literature recounting the movement of people between these two groups in both directions. There has been much written on the “Hellenization of the Jews,” and I do not intend to unpack this topic here due to the focus of this paper. An example of each type of movement, “Greeks” becoming “Jews” and “Jews” becoming

“Greeks,” will suffice. In the New Testament apocryphal text *The Acts of Pilate*, Jesus’s disciples are referred to as “Greeks” and proselytes who “become Jews.”¹⁴⁸ This passage demonstrates the “Judaizing” of Greeks. For an example of the opposite movement, I turn again to Josephus and *The Jewish War*:

Now just at the time when war had been declared and Vespasian had recently landed in Syria, [46] and when hatred of the Jews was everywhere at its height, a certain Antiochus, one of their own number and highly respected for the sake of his father, [47] who was chief magistrate of the Jews in Antioch, entered the theatre during an assembly of the people and denounced his own father and the other Jews, accusing them of a design to burn the whole city to the ground in one night; he also delivered up some foreign Jews as accomplices to the plot. On hearing this, the people, in uncontrollable fury, [48] ordered the men who had been delivered up to be instantly consigned to the flames, and all were forthwith burnt to death in the theatre. [49] They then rushed for the Jewish masses, [50] believing the salvation of their native place to be dependent on their prompt chastisement. Antiochus further inflamed their fury; for, thinking to furnish proof of his conversion and of his detestation of Jewish customs by sacrificing after the manner of the *Greeks*, [51] he recommended that the rest should be compelled to do the same, as the conspirators would thus be exposed by their refusal.¹⁴⁹ (emphasis added)

Josephus shares an account of a Jew who not only abandons his Jewish customs for expediency, but mandates that the rest of the Jews in Antioch be forced to do the same (cf. Romans 1:32).

These two examples expose the fluidity between these two terms and the people who use them, both to refer to themselves and to others. The rules of identification are not fixed either temporally or geographically but are rather tied to praxis. Nevertheless, both terms do have a geographic referent: the group marker “Greek” is connected to a number of cities founded under the former Grecian empire, while “Jew” is connected to the tribe of Judah and the former Southern Kingdom of Judah. I will revisit this distinction shortly.

Now let us return to the discussion of Judah and Israel, the Israelite kingdoms in the

¹⁴⁸ J. K. Elliott, *The Apocryphal New Testament: A Collection of Apocryphal Christian Literature in an English Translation* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1993, Kindle Edition), 172.

¹⁴⁹ Josephus, *The Jewish War: Books 1–7*, 519–521.

divided monarchy, and discuss how this distinction might differ from that of “Jew and Greek.” While I no longer hold to the strict definitions of “Greek” = Northern Kingdom Israelites and “Jew” = Southern Kingdom Israelites, it is worth noting that “Jew”/Judah is one half of both pairings being discussed and therefore could be said to skew the population in each of the groups. Therefore the “Jews” who returned from Babylon to the land of Israel were Judahites in the geopolitical sense - members of the tribes of Judah and Benjamin (and Levi).¹⁵⁰ They returned to Judah and restored their Yahwist cultic practices. Those Judahites who abandoned these practices were in one sense no longer “Jews,” while the Northern Kingdom Israelites who joined in the renewed Yahweh cult became “Jews.” So, the former designations of Judah and Israel, still existent and operative in the sacred texts of Israel, were not sufficient to describe the division of people between those still faithful to the covenant (subject to a variety of self-definitions) and those who were not. I suggest that “Greeks” became a term of “othering” used for those outside the covenant. Representing these two pairings graphically together to show the overlap gives an idea of how the groups relate:

¹⁵⁰ Recorded in Ezra and Nehemiah; cf. Josephus, *Antiquities of the Jews*, XI.3.10 (Whiston).

We find examples of this type of 2 x 2 matrix in various places in our modern context. Let us consider two examples by way of clarification. In the United States Civil War (1861-1865), the nation was split between the “North” and the “South,” a geographical division that took on ideological meaning. Those states in the North fought in the Union Army and were fighting to end slavery, while those states in the South became the Confederacy and fought to retain slavery. However, there were “abolitionists” living in the Southern states, just as there were people who continued to support slavery who lived in the North:

We could have the same discussion in today’s political climate in the U.S. concerning Republicans and Democrats and their stances on a number of hot topic issues: abortion, immigration, foreign trade, etc. The underlying division of Republican/Democrat, while being ideological rather than geographical, is akin to Israel/Judah, in the sense that these are “concrete” designations within the U.S. political two-party system (notwithstanding the existence of independents). On the surface, lawmakers and governors can be categorized as Democrats or Republicans, however this does not provide enough information to determine if they are “liberal” or “conservative,” nor are you able to determine what their stance is on any given topic by this designation alone.

We will see in “Synthesis,” the final section of this analysis, how Paul uses both of these pairings, Jews/Greeks and Judah/Israel, in different but supporting ways in his argument throughout the first eleven chapters of Romans.

6. **Synthesis - a New Hearing for Romans**

Evidence has been presented that refutes the traditional definitions of the terms “Jew,” “Israel,” “Gentile,” and “Greek.” Given the contextual understanding of OT citations in Romans 9 through 11 and the work of Jason Staples, we can no longer read “Jews” and “Israel” as synonymous group markers. A close reading of Romans suggests that Paul is primarily referring to Israelites from the former Northern Kingdom when he mentions “Israel.” The other occurrences of “Israel” in the letter refer to the whole nation of Israel as opposed to being a synonym for “Jew.” Likewise, the terms “Gentile” and “Greek” can no longer be viewed synonymously. “Greek,” as used by Paul in Romans, makes more sense as a group marker for non-Jewish Israelites, and the oft-repeated phrase “Jew and Greek” is shorthand for all Israelites born of the seed of Abraham. The term “Gentile,” also translated “nation,” refers to both the people of a particular land and the land itself; therefore, when used in prepositional phrases, e.g. “in/among the nations” or “from/out of the nations,” it can be used solely in the geographic sense and be referring to other peoples not originally from a nation but residing in that nation - like diaspora Jews/Israelites. Additionally, we have analyzed Paul’s use of the terms “Holy ones,” “called ones,” “beloved ones,” and “brothers/siblings,” all group markers used in the OT and NT by Israelites for self-identification. I suggest that this fact has been glossed over in most studies of the Pauline corpus and should be considered relevant to our exegesis of Romans given the other findings just mentioned. Below is an updated version of the group markers being discussed and the proposed new interpretations.

Group Markers		Accepted Applications			Proposed Applications			
	English	"Gentiles"	"Jews"	All Believers	Gentiles	Jewish Israelites	Non-Jewish Israelites	All Israelites
ἔθνη	Gentiles/nations	✓			✓*			
Ἰουδαῖος	Jews		✓			✓		
Ἕλληνες	Greeks	✓					✓	
Ἰσραήλ	Israel		✓				✓	✓
ἀδελφοί	Brothers/siblings			✓				✓
ἅγιοι	Holy (ones)			✓				✓
κλητοί	Called (ones)			✓				✓
ἀγαπητοί	Beloved (ones)			✓				✓

Table 2 - Group markers with new interpretations
* refers to people when in appropriate context

Now that we have examined the various group markers in Romans for their ethnic origins and “deconflated” our definitions of each from the other, we can return to the letter as a whole and propose how these new understandings affect our exegesis. While there is not space for a full commentary on Romans, my intent is to provide a somewhat detailed reading of several key passages that demonstrate the outworking of these exegetical adjustments in the overall interpretation of the letter.

6.1. Paul’s Audience - a Second Look

Past attempts at determining Paul’s audience in Romans have often been stuck in an “all or nothing” mindset, trying to identify a single, monolithic group of hearers for Paul’s message. In so doing, these attempts fixate on several “Gentile” related clues, namely the direct address to “Gentiles” in chapter 11 and Paul’s status as “apostle to the Gentiles,” echoed in chapter 15, and feel obligated to name “Gentiles” as the audience and thus force-fit the rest of their exegesis into this restrictive mold. More recent attempts acknowledge the multifaceted nature of Paul’s audience, but having done away with this restriction, they usually still end up identifying a primarily Gentile audience based in large part on the flawed understanding of the group markers just discussed.

I agree with recent commentators that Paul is addressing a diverse group in his letter to Rome, as evidenced by his direct address to Gentiles in chapter 11, but I am convinced that his primary audience is made up of Jewish believers. I have previously laid out how this reading is possible by presenting valid alternate understandings of the group markers first introduced in Romans chapter 1. Accepting this view as a given, let us walk through the first half of the chapter (1:1-15) and see how these separate elements work together to strengthen this reading.

Paul begins the letter (1:1-4) with a customary but somewhat lengthy self-introduction that is very “Jewish” in character: he is a servant of the “Christ,” who is identified as the “seed of David.” He concludes this section with another reference to the “Christ Jesus,” and names him as “Lord.” In v. 5 Paul refers to the “grace” received through an “obedience of faith” (a foreshadowing of the argument to be presented in v. 16) in all the nations. In v. 6, Paul offers a transition between the “From” and “To” sections of the salutation of the letter, connecting his audience to the statement made in v. 5 concerning the “grace” received in the nations: “in which [nations] you are also, you called ones of Jesus Christ” (author’s translation). Scholars have commented on the perceived awkwardness of this verse when read as a repeated reference to “Gentiles.” However, when read as a reference to diaspora Jews living in the nations, it simplifies the reading and makes sense logically and rhetorically.¹⁵¹

As we move to v. 7, we find a string of dative plurals that mark the “To” section of the salutation: “To all the holy ones, beloved and called by God, living in Rome: grace to you and peace from God our Father and the Lord Jesus Christ” (author’s translation). Paul is targeting the ears of his fellow Jewish believers with these well-known Israelite group markers. After a

¹⁵¹ See chapter 2 section “Gentiles, Greeks, and Barbarians,” for support from Crandall, Watson, and Mason.

passage of obligatory praise for his audience, he begins to tell them the purpose of his visit in v. 11, addressing his Jewish hearers as “brothers/siblings” in v. 13. He informs them in vv. 14-15 that, while the “Greeks and Barbarians” are his primary mission, he is happy to bring his gospel message to them as well, just as he has proclaimed the gospel to the Jewish diaspora in the other nations that he has visited. We have already discussed who the “Greeks” are in this Israelite-focused missive; who then are the “Barbarians”? I suggest that “Barbarians” could possibly refer, in this context, to other Israelites in the diaspora who live in other lands who speak other languages.¹⁵² The question is often asked, why is Paul preaching to already-believing Jews? The answer is usually something pastorally-minded, suggesting that even believers need to hear the gospel continuously for their good. But I believe this approach clouds Paul’s true intention here because we have missed the ethnic dimension of the “you” in v. 13. The Jews of Paul’s audience, while believers in Jesus as the long-awaited Messiah of Israel, are also still Jews, and part of the Jewish community in Rome. At this point in the formation of the church, most of them likely still attend synagogue with those Jews who have either not heard the full story of Jesus or are still hesitant to believe it. While hearing the gospel message again is indeed beneficial to the Jewish believers in Rome, it is the remaining Jews who do not yet believe that Paul has in mind. The “you” of v. 13 is an “all Jews in Rome” you. In this passage, Paul seems to be preempting any disagreement over whether Paul has the right to act as emissary to these devout Jews (Gal 2:7-8). Paul indicates that his gospel is for all, which includes all of Israel.

¹⁵² Josephus uses the phrase “Greeks and Barbarians” throughout his works, even dedicating *Jewish Wars* to the “Greeks and Barbarians.” In his translation of *Jewish Wars*, William Whiston included this telling footnote to the preface:

“Who these Upper Barbarians, remote from the sea, were, Josephus himself will inform us, sect. 2, viz. the Parthians and Babylonians, and remotest Arabians [of the Jews among them]; besides the Jews beyond Euphrates, and the Adiabeni, or Assyrians. Whence we also learn that these Parthians, Babylonians, the remotest Arabians, [or at least the Jews among them,] as also the Jews beyond Euphrates, and the Adiabeni, or Assyrians, understood Josephus's Hebrew, or rather Chaldaic, books of The Jewish War, before they were put into the Greek language.” (Flavius Josephus, location 133-137)

Paul will continue to address his fellow Jewish believers throughout the letter, with a brief aside to Gentile believers in chapter 11. With his audience identified as such and his mission clarified, Paul has set himself up nicely to present the often-quoted thesis of this letter, Romans 1:16-17.

6.2. The Thesis of Romans and Paul's Ethnic Argument

Scholars and theologians have long looked to Romans 1:16-17 as the thesis for the whole letter. I agree with this supposition, but I would like to focus initially on v. 16 separately, for reasons that will become immediately clear. For in v. 16, we find the first pairing in Romans of “Jew and Greek,” the primary phrase of investigation in this study:

For I am not ashamed of the gospel, for it is power from God leading to salvation for everyone who has faith – for Jew first and also for Greek. (author's translation)

This verse as much as any other factor has contributed to the interpretation of “Jew and Greek” to mean “all humankind” or “all the world.” Reading Romans abstractly and universally, many have taken “Jew and Greek” as a simple restatement of “everyone” (παντι). Knowing now that “Jew” was never used to represent all Israel and that “Greek” has been used to represent non-Jewish Israelites, “Jew and Greek” is better understood as representing the universe of all Israelites. Rather than a restatement of “everyone,” the phrase “for Jew first and also for Greek” indicates a qualified “everyone,” narrowing Paul's thesis, and thus the argument of Romans, to the people of Israel.

Before we move on, let us examine briefly the phrase “for Jew first and also for Greek.” While this is my own translation, it follows closely the traditional rendering of the text. Here is the original Greek:

Ἰουδαίῳ τε πρῶτον καὶ Ἑλληνι

This τε... καὶ construction is usually rendered in English “both... and” or “x and also y,” as I

have done in the previous paragraph (we will discuss the addition of *πρῶτον* separately below). However, an equally valid translation is “not only x, but also y.”¹⁵³ Translation is subjective and should always consider context. However, all of these possibilities coexist and overlap in the mind of the speaker and are represented any time this construction is used. The idea communicated by all three options is that two elements are included together in a new and surprising way. When this occurs, the first item is the known element (expected), and emphasis should be placed on the second item (unexpected). It is interesting that exegetes who argue for a Gentile audience for Romans ignore this structure and reverse it, suggesting that Paul as apostle to the Gentiles is also proclaiming his gospel to Jews, and that the priority is to the Jews first (*πρῶτον*). The term “Greek,” traditionally viewed as synonymous with “Gentile,” comes in second place and is rhetorically an afterthought, so their logic goes, even though the structure dictates that it is the “Greek” who is being emphasized. What happens to this reading if we substitute in the “not only x but also y” rendering in this verse?

For I am not ashamed of the gospel, for it is power from God leading to salvation for everyone who has faith – not only for Jew first but also for Greek. (MT)

This version makes clear that the emphasis is on the inclusion of the “Greek.” This understanding, however, breaks the traditional model of Paul’s argument directed to Gentiles: if he were directing his argument toward Gentile believers, who already have faith and are part of the community, why would he be trying to convince those Gentiles that Gentiles should be included along with Jews? However, when you read Romans as Paul addressing his fellow Jews and arguing for the inclusion of all Israel, including non-Jewish Israelites, the pieces fall into place coherently.

The final piece of the puzzle in this passage is how we should understand the inclusion of

¹⁵³ BDAG, 993.

the word *πρῶτον*. In the NT, the *τε πρῶτον καὶ* construction is found only in this verse and two others in Romans, 2:9 and 2:10. In fact, it is uncommon to find a single word dividing *τε* and *καὶ* in the New Testament; if these two words are not immediately adjacent, it is because they are connecting clauses or full sentences. So the question arises, why is *πρῶτον* placed here? Traditional translations and interpretations apply the “firstness” of this adverb to “Jew,” the first element in the clause. But if that is the correct reading, why not place *πρῶτον* directly before *Ἰουδαίῳ*? Some might argue that by putting *πρῶτον* outside the *τε... καὶ* construction, it would apply to both “Jew” and “Greek” and thus change the intended meaning. However, I would argue that having *πρῶτον* in the middle of the phrase should equally be read as applying to both elements in the phrase. No matter how you translate *τε... καὶ*, the concept of “and also” applies the “firstness” to both elements, Jew and Greek. This has never made sense when “Greek” has been understood as equivalent to “Gentile.” But now that we can read “Greek” as referring to non-Jewish Israelites, the “firstness” of Israel can be applied to both terms in the phrase. With this reading, we can now readily find Scriptural warrant to support it: all discussion in the gospels of the priority of proclaiming the good news to “the lost sheep of Israel” can be brought to bear in Paul’s argument (Matt 10:5-7, Matt 15:21-28; cf. Mark 7:24-30), as well as those verses in the Scriptures that talk of a new covenant for “the house of Israel” (Hebrews 8:10, Rom 11:26), referencing both kingdoms in the divided monarchy (Heb 8:8, Jer 31:31-34). Paul is making the case for gospel priority to all of Israel, both Jews and non-Jewish Israelites.¹⁵⁴

¹⁵⁴ Paul’s argument here is a tempered version of Jesus’s own position: with this statement in 1:16, Paul gives equal priority to Jews and non-Jewish Israelites; Jesus, assuming that Jews are “righteous,” gives priority to “sinners,” presumably those Israelites not following Jewish customs (Luke 5:30-32). It appears that both Jesus and Paul are partaking in word play with the term “righteous,” which is used to describe both a moral condition as well as being used as a group marker for those in the covenant of Israel.

6.3. Rom 1:17 - “The Righteous by Their Faith Shall Live”

As we move to v. 17, we find Paul quoting Habakkuk 2:4b: “as it is written, “The righteous shall live by their faith.” (ESV) The traditional reading is that Paul’s quotation of Hab 2:4b in v. 17b is a parallel statement, recapitulating the idea of v. 17a. Watson exemplifies this reading in his description of the parallel structure, noting that the antecedent in v. 17a is dependent on the citation in v. 17b.¹⁵⁵ He also notes the “lack of a gloss on ‘will live’,”¹⁵⁶ but insists on a parallelism contained within the verse. If we stay with the premise that there is some level of equivalency between the two statements, we might represent them logically this way:

Righteousness from God is revealed from faith for faith = The Righteous shall live by faith

On the surface, this seems logical: both sides of the equation contain a reference to righteous/righteousness as well as to the idea of faith. But this is not the type of parallelism that we find in the Psalms; there is not a one-to-one equivalency of terms. And, as noted by Watson, there is a dangling reference to “life/living” in the second half that is not in the first half. The way to rectify this is by expanding our view to v. 16, where “salvation” is mentioned. We also find persons, the “Jew” and the “Greek,” to match with “the righteous one” (as translated by the NASB). We present these elements in a more detailed logical representation:

¹⁵⁵ Watson, *Paul and the Hermeneutics of Faith, Second Editions* (London: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2016), 42.

¹⁵⁶ Watson, *Paul and the Hermeneutics of Faith*, 42 (footnote 47).

<u>Rom 1:16-17a</u>		<u>Rom 1:17b</u>
Salvation	≈	Life
Jew and Greek	≈	Righteous
Faith	=	Faith
Revealed	≈	Written

Figure 2 Parallelism in vv. 16 and 17

In this configuration, there is indeed a degree of parallelism in structure between the two halves, with one significant change: “righteous” of v. 17b is paired with “Jew and Greek” of v. 16. This approach removes “the righteousness of God” from the parallelism, but not from the overall equation – it is the righteousness of God that makes Paul’s statement possible. Watson, to his credit, supports this arrangement later in his monograph, but he fails to make changes to his original parallelism structure. In a section where he argues that the “righteousness of Jesus Christ” in Rom 3:22 does not refer to the faithfulness of Jesus, he states:

Paul’s original thesis – about the righteousness of God that is by faith – took the form of an interpretative gloss on the Habakkuk citation. Although the gloss sought to clarify and amplify the quotation at several points, there was no indication that the prophetic ‘by faith’ was understood as referring to the faith or faithfulness of Christ himself. *‘The one who is righteous by faith’ is not Christ but the believer (compare the reference in 1.16 to ‘everyone who believes, the Jew first and also the Greek’)*.¹⁵⁷ (emphasis added)

Watson has (knowingly or unknowingly) adjusted his proposed parallelism from being contained with v. 17 to including elements from v. 16, replicating in text the diagram in Figure 2 above. Whereas the first clause talks about salvation for “everyone,” qualifying “everyone” by adding “Jew and Greek” (implying “everyone” in an Israelite context), the second clause states that the

¹⁵⁷ Watson, *Paul and the Hermeneutics of Faith*, 67.

“righteous” will have “life” (the parallel to “salvation” in the first clause). With this parallelism properly identified, we can now ask: what point is Paul trying to make rhetorically by quoting Hab 2:4b? To answer this question we must look at the pre-Romans reception of this verse.

6.4. Habakkuk 2:4b Reception

Let us examine Hab 2:4b from two vantage points: first, from within Habakkuk itself; second, as received and elaborated upon by the Qumran community in the text *Pesher Habakkuk*.

6.4.1. *Habakkuk 2:4b in Context*

As we consider Habakkuk 2:4b within Habakkuk, a few data points for this book: scholars place the writing of Habakkuk in the 6th century BCE in the Southern Kingdom of Judah, prior to the Babylonian captivity, most likely during the reign of the Judean king Manasseh.¹⁵⁸ Coggins and Han state that the book of Habakkuk “derives its unifying theme from persistently pursuing a question as to what God is going to do about the wicked in order to rectify an evil situation.¹⁵⁹” This theme carries throughout this small book, to include the section containing 2.4b. Here the author contrasts the “prideful” of 2:4a (assumed by most scholars to designate the Babylonians) with the “righteous” of 2.4b (assigned to the people of God, Judah). Renz comments on the juxtaposition of “righteous” and “faith/faithfulness” and declares “there is little doubt that any who abandon faithfulness would no longer be considered “righteous” in accordance with this prophecy.¹⁶⁰” There is an exclusionary spirit to this verse, as God is contrasting the methods of conquest of the Babylonians with the patience and trust of the people of God.

¹⁵⁸ Richard J. Coggins and Jin H. Han, *Six Minor Prophets Through the Centuries: Nahum, Habakkuk, Zephaniah, Haggai, Zechariah, and Malachi*, 2011, 37.

¹⁵⁹ Coggins and Han, *Six Minor Prophets*, 38.

¹⁶⁰ Thomas Renz, *The Books of Nahum, Habakkuk, and Zephaniah* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 2021), 466.

6.4.2. *Habakkuk 2:4b in the Dead Sea Scrolls (Peshar Habakkuk)*

We see this exclusionary tenor of Habakkuk 2:4b continue in the Qumran sect as they reinterpret Habakkuk for their particular situation in the commentary on Habakkuk, *Peshar Habakkuk* (1QpHab).¹⁶¹ Lim states in his commentary on *Peshar Habakkuk* that in this first century BCE work, the author of the peshar sees “the oracles of the prophet Habakkuk as predictive of the events that took place in the pesharist’s time.¹⁶²” The commentary is apocalyptic in content and style, “reflecting the belief that divine action was manifest in his days and the end-time was imminent, if also apparently delayed.” The pesharist speaks to his community, referring to them as “the men of truth, doers of the law, whose hands will not drop from the service of truth when the end-time is protracted for them.¹⁶³” If there is any hesitation in hearing the boundary-marking, exclusionary nature of these comments from the pesharist on Habakkuk 2:3cd, all doubt is removed when you read his comment on 2:4b:

Its interpretation concerns all doers of the law in the house of Judah whom God will deliver from the house of judgment on account of their suffering and their faithfulness in the Teacher of Righteousness.¹⁶⁴

We see that in Qumran, like in the 6th century BCE original context, Habakkuk 2:4b is used to delineate the “righteous” to the exclusion of others. As we move from the original audience of Habakkuk to Qumran, however, the definition of who is considered “righteous” and who is considered “other” changes.

¹⁶¹ Timothy H. Lim, *The Earliest Commentary on the Prophecy of Habakkuk (Oxford Commentary on the Dead Sea Scrolls)* (London: OUP Oxford, 2020, Kindle Edition), 1.

¹⁶² Lim, *The Earliest Commentary*, 1.

¹⁶³ Lim, *The Earliest Commentary*, 104.

¹⁶⁴ Lim, *The Earliest Commentary*, 107.

6.4.3. *Habakkuk 2:4b in Romans 1:17b*

When we arrive back at Romans, we can see from these other accounts of Habakkuk that Paul does not draw Habakkuk 2:4b out of a grab bag of verses to apply arbitrarily, abstractly, propositionally, and/or universally as a proof-text to win an argument; he is invoking a well-established line of reasoning that already existed within Jewish/Israelite culture for centuries and persisted, in various forms, to his day.¹⁶⁵ And Paul, like the writer of *Pesher Habakkuk*, has redefined for his audience who the “righteous” are by linking this term with the group markers “Jew and Greek” – suggesting that both Jewish Israelites (those following Torah) and non-Jewish Israelites (those not following Torah) can be counted among the “righteous” through faith. By planting this rhetorical flag in the ground, Paul invites a refutation of this claim, which he gets in Rom 1:18ff.

6.5. Romans 1:18-32 – a Speech-in-Character Rebuttal to 1:16-17

Douglas Campbell has famously proposed that Romans 1:18-32 should be understood as prosopopoeia, speech-in-character.¹⁶⁶ Campbell avers that 1:18-32 is a section of prosopopoeia, but he admits that there appear to be no verbal or textual markers to indicate the beginning of another “voice” speaking. He even surmises that this absence of verbal/textual cues has caused other exegetes to miss reading 1:18-32 as prosopopoeia. He then goes to work laying out a list of characteristics found in the text that mark it out as a speech-in-character passage: 1) the self-contained structure of the passage; 2) the condensed occurrence of alpha-privatives; 3) the dense

¹⁶⁵ Francis Watson, *Paul and the Hermeneutics of Faith*, 47. See also Timothy H. Lim, “Why Did Paul Cite Habakkuk 2:4b?”, *The Expository Times* 133.6 (2022): 225–32, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00145246221075893>, 227: “Paul used the half-verse to polemicize against those Jews, like the Essenes, who understood it as a faithful observance of the Jewish law.”

¹⁶⁶ Campbell, *The Deliverance of God*, 808.

number of third-person plural verbs; 4) a variety of puns and wordplay; and 5) the inclusion of several long, distinctive vice lists.¹⁶⁷

Campbell posits a single interlocutor, the “Teacher,” a “Jewish Christian sage,¹⁶⁸” and refers to 1:18-32 as his “rhetorical opening.¹⁶⁹” While Campbell identifies parallels between this section and Paul’s thesis in 1:16-17, this description as an “opening” betrays the fact that there is a disconnect between Paul’s words and the Teacher’s words. “Opening” implies that the Teacher is beginning his own argument, rather than responding to what Paul has just said. Campbell describes it thus:

The apostle summarizes compactly in Romans 1:18–32 what he takes to be the Teacher’s usual opening—his arresting προοίμιον, or exordium. Here Paul provides what we might call a cameo of this material.¹⁷⁰

By designating this section as an “exordium,” Campbell treats it as the Teacher’s introduction, even suggesting that the Teacher is providing his own thesis, separate from what Paul has put forth:

The Teacher’s rhetorical prelude begins—as Paul presents it—with an important thesis: “the wrath of God is revealed from heaven against all [human] ungodliness and wickedness¹⁷¹ ...”

Campbell assumes that 1:18-32, in his reading of the passage as speech-in-character, is floating freely, an insert dropped somewhat awkwardly into the flow of Paul’s argument. This awkwardness and disconnectedness disappear, however, when we read Paul’s quotation of Hab 2:4b in 1:17b as a contested use of this citation. The interlocutor(s) and their argument(s) are

¹⁶⁷ Campbell, *The Deliverance of God*, 816.

¹⁶⁸ Campbell, *The Deliverance of God*, 810.

¹⁶⁹ Campbell, *The Deliverance of God*, 828.

¹⁷⁰ Campbell, *The Deliverance of God*, 828.

¹⁷¹ Campbell, *The Deliverance of God*, 828.

presented in direct response to Paul’s thesis:

Paul: For it is power from God leading to salvation for everyone who has faith, not only to the Jew first but also to the Greek; for in it the righteousness of God is revealed, from faith, for faith. As it is written, “But the righteous shall live by faith!”

Jewish interlocutor: Surely the wrath of God is revealed from heaven against all ungodliness and unrighteousness, from people who suppress the truth in unrighteousness... (author’s translation)

By recognizing the confrontational nature of Paul’s statement in 1:16-17, we reconnect the last half of chapter 1 to the first half in a way that makes strong logical, linguistic, and rhetorical sense. With that accomplished, let us return to a discussion of ethnic markers and see what 1:18-32 contains that supports an intra-Israelite reading.

6.6. 1:18-32 - Israelite-specific Allusions in the Text

Now that we have established that Paul’s thesis concerning “Jew and Greek” is an intra-Israelite argument advocating for the inclusion of both Jews and non-Jewish Israelites in God’s plan of redemption, how does this impact the traditional reading of the last half of chapter 1? Accepting Campbell’s premise that this section is a form of speech-in-character does not in itself change the traditional understanding that this is a “universal” condemnation of all people, Gentiles and Jews. But if Paul’s argument is focused on Israel, the logical conclusion is that this opposing response should also focus on some subset of Israelites. This is indeed what we find, and yet modern scholars have either missed the references or dismissed them as universal statements of condemnation rather than indicating an Israelite-specific group as the object of discussion. Here are three concepts used in 1:18-32 that meet this criteria:

“Ungodliness and unrighteousness”: this pairing is found in 1:18. Its opposite, “piety and righteousness (εὐσέβεια and δικαιοσύνη) is a two-word shorthand used by Jews to refer to the Ten Commandments. Paula Fredriksen explains:

“Justice” and “piety” in this context are not pious abstractions: they are a two-word code for a core tradition of the Sinai covenant, the Ten Commandments. The first five commandments comprise the first table of the Law, *eusebeia*, governing relations with God (exclusive worship; no images; no abuse of God’s name; keeping the Sabbath; honoring parents). The second five, or second table of the Law, *dikaiosynē*, govern relations between people (thus, forbidding murder, adultery, theft, lying, and coveting).¹⁷²

As Fredriksen points out, these two terms are not abstractions, but are concrete pointers to the Mosaic Law. She goes on to elaborate how Paul applies the Ten Commandments selectively to “pagan” believers, all the while rightly insisting that Gentiles cannot become Jews. And yet she does not make the connection between the “piety” and “justice” shorthand and its antithesis found in 1:18. I contend that v. 18, taking its cue from 1:17b and attempting to distinguish who is “righteous,” presents at the beginning of the interlocutor’s argument the disqualification of non-Jewish Israelites due to their failure to follow the Mosaic Law, coded in the mirror shorthand of “ungodliness” and “unrighteousness.”

Those who know God: v. 21a says, “For although they knew God, they did not honor him as God or give thanks to him.” (ESV) There is an implied assumption of “knowing God” on the part of the third person objects of this section. This “knowing” points back to the truth that is held by the “unrighteous” ones in v. 18b. Every modern translation (NKJV, NRSV, ESV, NLT, NASB, NIV, CSB, LSB, NET) renders the verb *κατέχω* as “suppress,” suggesting that the people are “suppressing the truth” by (through, by means of) their unrighteousness. However, elsewhere in the New Testament, including in Paul’s undisputed letters (1 Cor 7:30, 11:2, 15:2, 2 Cor 6:10, 1 Thes 5:21, Philemon 1:13), *κατέχω* is rendered as “maintaining” or “holding fast” to something, and this option makes sense in Rom 1:18b as well. These non-Jewish Israelites, who did not follow the Ten Commandments faithfully (by Judaism’s standards), committed these acts of unrighteousness even while they possessed the truth. And what truth was that? The truth about

¹⁷² Fredriksen, *Paul*, “Introduction,” location 111.

God, as amplified in v. 19: “For what can be known about God is plain to them, because God has shown it to them.” (ESV) These passages are read universally as applying to all humans, with an appeal to “natural law” and general revelation through creation. However, once again, Fredriksen identifies the concept of “knowing God” as a shorthand marker for “Jews” as the chosen people of God:

This divine ethnicity, refracted through the lens of prophetic eschatology, reveals and highlights three interconnected ideas: first, that *Israel alone has “known” God*; second, that the *other nations have not known God*; third, that at the End, these nations, too, will know God.¹⁷³ (emphasis added)

This explanation of the “knowing” of God is embedded in Fredriksen’s discussion of the “ethnicity” of God and the familial connection between “Israel’s God” and Israel itself. Even though God is over all the other elohim, Fredriksen states that, according to Jewish tradition, “Israel’s God himself is ‘Jewish.’”¹⁷⁴ She insists that Gentiles will eventually know God too, but not until “the End,” in the eschatological future:

The point to bear in mind here is that, whether for Isaiah or for Paul, *the more intense the pitch of apocalyptic expectation, the greater the contrast between Israel and the nations*. Why? Because the *narrative* function of the nations in these traditions is precisely to represent not-Israel, all those other peoples who have not known God and who do not know God. Eschatological redemption emphasizes and intensifies this high contrast between Israel (knowing God) and everyone else (not knowing God until the End).¹⁷⁵ (italics original)

Fredriksen has done an outstanding job defining and laying out the parameters for “knowing God,” but misses the opportunity to apply this logic to her interpretation of Rom 1:18-32.

Nowhere does she make the connection that those who already knew God in v. 21 might be non-

¹⁷³ Fredriksen, *Paul*, loc 2203.

¹⁷⁴ Fredriksen, *Paul*, loc 2203.

¹⁷⁵ Fredriksen, *Paul*, loc 2217.

Jewish Israelites.¹⁷⁶ I concur with Fredriksen’s definition of “knowing God” as applying to Jews/Israelites and assert that v. 18b-19 and v. 21 should be read as referring to non-Jewish Israelites.

The triad of beastly idols: Romans 1:22-23 describes people engaged in idol worship:

Claiming to be wise, they became fools, and exchanged the glory of the immortal God for images resembling mortal man and birds and animals and creeping things. (ESV)

The traditional understanding of these verses is as a condemnation of Gentiles and their idol-worshipping ways. However, several commentators have noted parallels between v. 23 and Psalm 106:20:¹⁷⁷

They exchanged the glory of God
for the image of an ox that eats grass. (ESV)

This verse recounts the story of the golden calf (Exodus 32), when the undivided nation of Israel induced God’s wrath by constructing and then worshipping an idol of gold in the form of a calf at the foot of Mount Horeb. The initial lexical connection between the verses is based on the verb ἀλλάσσω, translated “exchanged” and found in Rom 1:23 and the LXX version of Psalm 106:20, and the concept of exchanging the “glory” (δόξα) of God for something else. The comparison breaks down slightly, however, when we examine the “something else” in both verses: Rom 1:23 refers to images in the form of man and three different animals, whereas Psalm 106:20 only refers to an ox. Nevertheless, this approximation is enough for some exegetes to suggest that this verse refers to the idolatry of both Gentiles and “Jews,” where “Jews” is used in the traditional

¹⁷⁶ Fredriksen, *Paul*, loc 2330. In this section, she refers to the nations not knowing God and cites Rom 1:18-32, but only to point to the vice lists: “When Paul’s pagans adhered steadfastly to the good news brought by his message (the RSV’s “believed in the gospel”), they ceased worshipping their own gods and committed themselves to the god of Israel through his son (the cluster of ideas around πιστεύω, “to be steadfast”). Made right by God toward God, they were likewise pneumatically enabled to make right toward each other by acting rightly toward each other—“not like the ἔθνη who do not know God” (1 Thes 4.5; cf. Rom 1.18–32 and 13.13–14, for “typically pagan” bad behaviors).”

¹⁷⁷ Alec J. Lucas, “Reorienting the Structural Paradigm and Social Significance of Romans 1:18-32,” *JBL* 131, no. 1 (2012), 121-141. Lucas lists several commentators supporting this view, including Origen, in footnote 43.

sense as referring to all Israelites. By this sleight of hand, this presumed allusion to Ex 32 (and thus these verses in Romans) is read as universally applying to all people.

I propose that there is another Old Testament allusion that accounts for all elements of Rom 1:23 by turning to the book of Hosea - a book written to the apostate Israelites of the Northern Kingdom of Israel in the divided monarchy. In Hosea 4:6-7 we find the same parallel concerning the “exchanging” of glory:

My people are destroyed for lack of knowledge;
 because you have rejected knowledge,
 I reject you from being a priest to me.
 And since you have forgotten the law of your God, I also will forget your children.
 The more they increased,
 the more they sinned against me;
 I will *change* their glory into shame. (ESV, emphasis added)

There is a difference in the ideas conveyed by Rom 1:23 and Hos 4:7: in Romans, the “exchange” action is performed by the people, whereas in Hosea, it is performed by God. However, if we examine the structure of Hos 4:6, the back-and-forth “exchange” between the people and God implies an understood “exchange” of glory in v. 7. I paraphrase for illustration:

You rejected knowledge
 I reject you

 You forgot the law
 I will forget you

 [You exchanged my glory]
 I will exchange your glory

Turning to the tripartite collection of beasts in Rom 1:23, we find its direct parallel in the LXX version of Hos 4:3, adjacent to the previous quotation:

Therefore shall the land mourn, and shall be diminished with all that dwell in it, with the wild beasts of the field, and the reptiles of the earth, and with the birds of the sky, and the fish of the sea shall fail:¹⁷⁸

¹⁷⁸ Lancelot C. L. Brenton, *The Septuagint with Apocrypha*, 1073.

While the order of the animals is different than that found in Rom 1:23, all three creatures are represented. What is more, this triad of animals is only found six times throughout the Hebrew Scriptures - Gen 1:30, 6:7, 8:17, Psalm 148:10, Ezek 38:20, and Hos 2:18. However, when we take into account the LXX, the beasts/birds/creeping things occurrences in Hosea increase to three times: 2:18 (LXX 2:20), 4:3, and 2:12 (LXX 2:14). By comparing the Hebrew versions with the LXX, you can see the deliberateness with which these changes were made by the LXX translators to harmonize all three occurrences:

Some might argue that in each of these instances in Hosea the animals in this list are not directly implicated as objects of idol worship, and therefore are not truly a match for the sentiment being

communicated in Rom 1:23. However, taking Hosea chapter 4 as an example, the entire case being prosecuted by the prophet addresses the idol worship of the people and its attendant activities: the chapter starts with the charge of unfaithfulness to God, followed by a vice list; the author then quickly implicates the priesthood as the responsible party, detailing how they have led the people astray; he states the Lord will punish them “because they have forsaken the LORD to cherish whoredom, wine, and new wine...” (vv. 10,11). Prostitution is mentioned several times in this chapter, as it is throughout the book, which commentators often associate with temple prostitution in service of the idols being worshipped.

Even with this detailed argument in chapter 4, there is no explicit statement that the animals listed were being made into idols and worshipped. However, I humbly suggest that this three-fold reference to creatures as idols in Rom 1:23 could be considered connected by association to the same collections found in Hosea, and thus point to the whole book of Hosea, which is written as an indictment of the idol worship that occurred in the Northern Kingdom of Israel.

In Hosea 13:2, the animal imagery as idols comes completely together, as Israel continues to come apart:

And now they sin more and more,
and make for themselves metal images,
idols skillfully made of their silver,
all of them the work of craftsmen.
It is said of them,
“Those who offer human sacrifice kiss calves!”

This imagery of “kissing calves” evokes from Israel’s history the golden calf incident of Exodus 32, similar to Ps 106:20. Might the occurrence of a triad of animal images found in Hosea 2:12, 2:18, and 4:3, evoke even more? Just as in the ten plagues brought upon Egypt by YHWH through Moses, where each plague involved an animal tied to an Egyptian deity, could the

animals in Hosea mirror the idols worshipped by the Northern Kingdom Israelites?

By including the triad of animals in Rom 1:23 as an allusion to the same lists of animals in Hosea, Paul, in the voice of his interlocutor(s), provides a subtle but compelling link to the condemnation of non-Jewish Israelites, those descended from the Northern Kingdom tribes, who, in the eyes of their Jewish siblings, are apostates and therefore “unrighteous.”

I suggest that these three elements found in Rom 1:18-32 – allusion to the Torah (Ten Commandments), “knowing” God, and idolatry in the book of Hosea – together make a strong case for considering this “speech-in-character” section as an indictment, not against Gentiles or all humanity, but against non-Jewish Israelites.

6.7. Habakkuk 2:4b as Outline for Romans 1-8

Having identified Rom 1:16-17 as Paul’s initial salvo in a debate concerning who should be considered “righteous,” we connected it rhetorically and logically to Rom 1:18-32 as the impetus for this speech-in-character counterargument. However, Habakkuk 2:4b, quoted in Rom 1:17b, has a larger role to play in the letter. Having used this citation as his opening thesis, Paul will use Hab 2:4b as an organizer for his entire argument in chapters 1 through 8.¹⁷⁹ To demonstrate this, let us look first at the word order of Hab 2:4b, in the original Hebrew of Habakkuk as well as the Greek and English of Romans:

וְצַדִּיק בְּאַמוּנָתוֹ יִתְקַן:

ὁ δὲ δίκαιος ἐκ πίστεώς μου ζήσεται

¹⁷⁹ Watson, *Paul and the Hermeneutics of Faith*, 47. In footnote 61, Watson alludes to a similar insight from Nygren: “Among commentators on Romans, Anders Nygren is unusual in emphasizing the importance of the Habakkuk citation, in which he finds ‘the whole message of the epistle’ (*Commentary on Romans*, Eng. Tr., London: SCM Press, 1952), 81. Paul elucidates the first part of the citation (‘the one who through faith is righteous...’) in chs 1-4, the second half (‘...shall live’) in chs 5-8 (28-32). Although Nygren’s thesis is often rejected on the grounds that it diminishes the significance of chs 9-11, that need not be the case...” Watson seems to be tacitly supporting Nygren’s reading, against the bulk of his peers, albeit somewhat surreptitiously through a footnote. Thanks to Dr. Jacob Rodriguez for pointing me to Watson’s similar discussion of Hab 2:4 in this regard.

... but the **righteous** by his **faith** shall **live**.

The progression of terms in both the Hebrew and the Greek is righteous -> faith -> life. The typical English translation obscures this word order, usually rendered “the righteous shall live by faith” or similarly; here I have translated to match the word order of the original. When we compare the rhetorical topics being argued by Paul in chapters 1 through 8, we discover that his material follows the pattern found in Hab 2:4b:

The chain links in the diagram above represent the connectedness and overlap between each of these sections - these three themes are interwoven throughout these eight chapters, as well as throughout the rest of the letter to the Romans. However, using this Habakkuk saying as a mnemonic, Paul takes each element of Habakkuk 2:4b and addresses it in order, redefining each one for his interlocutor(s) and his audience. Paul’s interlocutors are a particular faction of Jewish believers who argue that because apostate Israelites are no longer “righteous” and therefore no

longer part of the family of God, they could not re-enter the family through Christ because of their previous break from the covenant. In chapters 1 through 3, Paul destroys this assumption and shows his opponents that even Jews have been sinful and therefore “unrighteous,” concluding that their belonging to the family of God was not predicated on their behavior, but rather on their trust in God’s own righteousness toward the covenant, specifically through Jesus Christ. In chapter 4, he moves on to discuss the ideas of “faith” and “faithfulness,” using the story of Abraham as the backdrop and anchor point for why faith/trust is the key to the familial relationship with God rather than performance, so that “they are heirs by faith, so that they are heirs by virtue of grace, being assured that the promise is to all the seed, not to those of the law only but also to those of faith like Abraham, who is the father of us all” (Rom 4:16, author’s translation). Finally, Paul turns to address questions of “life” in chapters 5 through 8, viewing it from various vantage points: death, sin, slavery, the Law, and lastly the Spirit. His overall message in this section is that Christ has come and conquered sin and death, bringing new life to all, both now and in the future, which we are to live in the Spirit.

6.8. Romans 9:1-5 - Introduction or Conclusion?

Having concluded his argument based on a refutation of each element in Habakkuk 2:4b, Paul starts a new section focused on “Judah” versus “Israel,” as examined in the section on Romans 9-11 above.¹⁸⁰ Because of the introduction of the term “Israelites” in Rom 9:4, the first occurrence in the letter of any form of the name Israel, the beginning of chapter 9 has been viewed as just that, a new beginning of a discrete section of the letter. Because of the traditional understanding of chapters 1 through 8, Rom 9-11 has often been viewed even as something of a non sequitur, with no connection at all to the first part of the letter. However, with the understanding that “Jew

¹⁸⁰ See section 4 of this chapter.

and Greek” is shorthand for all Israel, both Jews and non-Jewish Israelites, we must revisit how these two portions are connected. Allow me to suggest, knowing what has been proposed for chapters 1 through 8, that Rom 9:1-5 is just as fitting if not more so as a summary conclusion to the first 8 chapters. As Paul wraps up his grand argument for the inclusion of “Greeks” in the family of God, he makes one final plea to his Jewish audience to remember that the “Greeks,” these non-Jewish Israelites in the diaspora, are their siblings, and as genealogical descendants of Abraham are entitled to all the same covenant rights as the Jews themselves. As we shall see directly below, we actually do not need to decide that this passage is one or the other, either conclusion or introduction; it can and does function as both, acting as a bridge between the two sections of the letter.

6.9. Romans 9-11 - the Initiating Objection

In Rom 9:1-5, Paul offers his closing argument to the first portion of the letter, but he also introduces a new proposition, or at least clarifies a proposition that was just under the surface of his argument in Rom 1-8: all Israelites, even apostate ones, are still Israelites by nature of their birthright, and are still under God’s covenants to the Israelite people. We see this in the list of privileges enumerated in 9:4, and in their connection to the “patriarchs” or “forefathers” (πατέρες), as well as in their genealogical connection to the Christ himself. Structurally, this is similar to Paul’s declaration in Rom 1:16-17 - Rom 9:4-5 acts as a new thesis statement. This new thesis is connected with and supplemental to his original thesis, but it acts as a new anchor point for the argument in chapters 9 through 11. And, similar to his first thesis, this one in chapter 9 receives an immediate rebuttal from his interlocutor(s) beginning in Rom 9:6. This verse, usually read as an isolated proposition, has been at the center of the debate concerning who represents the “true Israel” since Irenaeus and Origen. Through the centuries, it has spawned

a number of supersessionist readings where Gentiles are now the “new Israel.” I am going to suggest an alternate reading, one that is supported by my understanding of the letter as an intra-Israelite debate. Let us first look at the verse itself logically and linguistically, helped once again by a set of Venn diagrams:

But it is not as though the word of God has failed.
For not all who are descended from Israel belong to Israel.

I will construct our Venn diagram in steps based on the logic found in the verse:

1. The universe we are working with includes “all who are descended from Israel.”

All who are descended from Israel

2. “Not all... belong to Israel” indicates that SOME do belong. So let us create those two groups.

All who are descended from Israel

3. Accepting that Paul’s interlocutors are Jewish, and given all that we have seen in Paul’s Old Testament quotations and allusions in chapters 9 through 11, it is logical to make this

assumption:

All who are descended from Israel

In Rom 9:6, Paul is voicing the objection of a Jewish interlocutor, making the point that Jews are still a part of Israel writ large and can represent the nation as a whole (thus fulfilling the covenant of God with Israel), while implying that their apostate Northern Kingdom siblings cannot. Judah, by their own reckoning, fulfills the covenant as the “remnant.”¹⁸¹ Because of our longstanding conflation of the terms “Jews” and “Israel,” the above thought experiment was unavailable to us. But now that we can distinguish between these two group markers, this straightforward reading of Rom 9:6 becomes evident and is arguably the most appropriate solution. There is no longer a need for spiritualized or esoteric interpretations to try to make sense of this statement. The supersessionist reading that posits Gentiles as the “new Israel” is no longer feasible given the availability of this solution.

Let us return, then, to Rom 9:4-5 and read 9:6 in sequence so that we can demonstrate the

¹⁸¹ This interpretation of 9:6b might seem to contradict Staples and his claim that Jews never thought of themselves as representing the whole of Israel in the eschaton; however, they can and do see themselves as the “remnant,” while not necessarily claiming that they should be considered “all Israel,” which matches Staples’s thesis. 9:6b is a counterpoint to Paul’s main argument throughout Romans, that Northern Kingdom Israelites (Greeks) are allowed to return to God through faith in Jesus. This statement then becomes the “straw man” that Paul refutes in chapters 9-11.

point/counterpoint structure, as we did in Rom 1:16-17. This time, I will present the text as a dialogue between Paul and an interlocutor:

Paul: They are Israelites, and to them belong the adoption, the glory, the covenants, the giving of the law, the worship, and the promises. To them belong the patriarchs, and from their race, according to the flesh, is the Christ, who is God over all, blessed forever. Amen.

Interlocutor: But it is not as though the word of God has failed. For not all who are descended from Israel belong to Israel... (ESV)

We can paraphrase and represent these two statements graphically:

Notice that 9:6 is not a negation of 9:4-5; it does not suggest that all Israelites are not part of God's covenant, just that they are not necessary to the covenant for God's word to be fulfilled. Both statements, in fact, when read abstractly, are true. However, the difference is in the follow-on conclusions and implications intended by each side of the argument. Paul is (and has been) arguing for inclusion; his Jewish interlocutor is arguing (and has been through chapters 1-8) for exclusion. As we saw in my earlier discussion of OT citations in chapters 9 through 11, these two poles drive the dialog in this section. Since I have already discussed Romans 9 to 11 in some detail above, I will not include that exegesis here.

6.10. Romans 11:13-24 - a Gentile Aside

As discussed in the section "Paul's Audience - a First Look," 11:13 is the one place we can be relatively certain that Paul is directly addressing Gentiles in his audience due to the phrase "Now

I am speaking to you Gentiles” (ὕμῖν δὲ λέγω τοῖς ἔθνεσιν). Since we can now read Rom 9-11 up to this point as an intra-Israelite debate, this first direct address to Gentiles can be treated as an excursus, separate from the previous argument, though connected logically and rhetorically. Paul is briefly explaining to any Gentile believers present that there is a purpose for his proclaiming to the nations, and that is to save some of his “flesh” (μου τὴν σάρκα).¹⁸² He goes on then to warn his Gentile hearers not to think too highly of themselves, constructing one of the most famous extended metaphors in all of Scripture, the cultivated and wild olive trees representing Israel and the new Gentile believers respectively. Gentiles, the cuttings from the “wild olive tree,” are grafted into the “cultivated olive tree,” which represents the nation of Israel. The “broken-off branches” (v. 17) are apostate Israelites (presumably non-Jewish Israelites primarily from the former Northern Kingdom), supposedly removed to make room for the “wild olive branches” to be grafted into Israel. But Paul clarifies that the broken-off branches can be grafted back into Israel. Presumably the Jews are still part of the cultivated olive tree, not having been “cut off.” Therefore, this illustration makes clear the three different parties - Jews, non-Jewish Israelites, and Gentiles - that Paul has in mind in this section, and indeed throughout the letter. This reading integrates with and supports the intra-Israelite reading of chapters 9-11 and the rest of the letter, while cleaning up the awkwardness of the traditional reading that posits Gentiles as the primary audience throughout the letter.

6.11. Romans 11:25-36 - Conclusion of Paul’s Argument

This “Gentile aside” concludes in v. 24. We know this because it is here that the olive tree metaphor is wrapped up, but also because in v. 25, Paul uses the vocative form ἀδελφοί

¹⁸² The RSV and ESV erroneously translate σάρκα as “Jews,” which obscures the fact that all of Paul’s kin, including non-Jewish Israelites, are included in his missionary goals.

(brothers/siblings), switching the conversation back to his Jewish interlocutors, identified as his kin.¹⁸³ From v. 25 to the end of the chapter, Paul makes his final case for the inclusion of all Israelites in the family of God, regardless of past actions, stating in 11:29 “For the gifts and the calling of God are irrevocable.” (ESV) Pointing once again to the equally questionable behavior of the Jews, he concludes in 11:32: “For God has consigned all to disobedience, that he may have mercy on all.” (ESV)

6.12. Romans 12-16

The focus of this paper is on Paul’s argument in the first 11 chapters of Romans and how a reordered understanding of the various ethnic markers in the letter provides a strong foundation for reading this debate as between Paul and a faction of Jewish believers concerning the return of non-Jewish Israelites to the family of God through their faith in God, made possible by God’s faithfulness to the covenant through Jesus the Messiah. These changes impact the exegesis of chapters 12 to 16, but due to space constraints I will not address these chapters here. I will briefly discuss the implications for further research on these chapters of Romans in the conclusion of this paper.

¹⁸³ See section “Brothers/Siblings” above.

Chapter 5 - Conclusions

1. Summary of Findings

As I hope I have demonstrated in this paper, there are good exegetical and historical reasons to characterize Paul's audience in Romans as a trichotomy consisting of Jewish Israelites (Jews), non-Jewish Israelites (referred to as "Greeks" and connected with "Israel," the former Northern Kingdom of Israel, in OT passages quoted in chapters 9-11), and non-Israelites (Gentiles). With this audience composition now in view, we can properly understand Paul's rhetoric and determine that he was debating a Jewish faction in Rome (real or rhetorical) concerning the specific question of whether apostate non-Jewish Israelites might be granted access back into the family of God. Gentiles, while also part of Paul's overall discussion, are tangential to his main argument as constructed in chapters 1 through 11. The occurrences of "Gentiles/nations" in Rom 1 were conclusively shown to be plausibly regarded as geographic references, which located diaspora Jews "in the nations," where they overlapped with Paul's primary mission to "the nations" and the "uncircumcised." Paul was proclaiming the gospel not only to Gentiles, but also to those apostate Israelites living among them and thus working toward the restoration of the kingdom of Israel, the reconstitution of both the Northern Kingdom of Israel and the Southern Kingdom of Judah into the family of God.

Our ability to read Romans in this way comes into sharp focus when we set aside the notion that Paul was the promoter of all the propositions expounded in the letter; instead, we tune our ears to hear him posing arguments put forth by various interlocutors (both friendly and fractious) and in turn responding to those arguments. This method has been employed by several scholars in their exegesis, sometimes by identifying instances of "speech in character" within the

text (most notably Douglas Campbell and Stanley Stowers¹⁸⁴), other times by indicating that Paul is speaking “rhetorically,” stating something as himself that he clearly does not agree with so that he can then provide a counterpoint. However, this method of reading and understanding Romans has not been consistently applied across the whole letter. The result is that exegetes pick and choose where to apply this logic while ignoring other instances of “argumentative speech,” thus building support for one particular reading or refuting other readings through their omissions. These alternate and often contradictory readings continue as scholars argue over the presence or absence of discourse markers, all the while ignoring the linguistic logic of the words in each passage. Instead of concerning ourselves with who may or may not be speaking at any given point in the letter, our exegesis is better served by paying attention to the logical content of each phrase and determining if it supports or counters the main argument at each step. In this way, by recognizing a dialogue of *ideas* rather than people, we are able to hear the full beauty of Paul’s rhetoric, experiencing it as an integrated grand argument. With this shift, the people involved are not removed from the argument - the people are what is being argued about. By focusing on the interchange of ideas rather than the speaker, we are able to follow the flow of the argument and finally understand the message that Paul is attempting to convey: non-Jewish Israelites, even though apostate and considered by some as no longer part of the house of Israel, are still members of God’s chosen family and are welcome to return simply by having faith in the Messiah, Jesus.

When we apply this method, the most significant change in our understanding of Romans comes where you do not expect it - in what is often called the “theme of Romans,” 1:16-17, specifically in v. 17b, where we see the quotation of Hab 2:4b. Once we understand the historical

¹⁸⁴ Stowers, *A Rereading of Romans*, 36-37. Stowers famously writes on diatribe in Romans and indeed posits speech-in-character at a couple points in the letter, but alas not in chapter 1 as Campbell does.

context of this OT quotation and its earlier reception and usage in *Pesher Habakkuk* of the DSS, we can see that this citation, “but the righteous by their faith shall live,” is a challenge to Paul’s opponents because of its connection to both “Jews and Greeks” (i.e., all Israelites, not only those defined as “righteous” by a particular group), who are all rescued through the righteousness of God merely by trusting in him.

This reading of 1:17b as Paul’s instigating argument is followed by a speech-in-character section in the subsequent verses in chapter 1 that refutes the claim that formerly apostate Israelites can participate in God’s righteousness and be part of his family once again. Rom 1:18-32 contains three allusions to Israelites, two that apply to all Israel, and a third allusion that specifically calls out Northern Kingdom idolatry: 1) the echo of the shorthand for Torah, “godliness and righteousness,” in v. 18; 2) the reference to people who “know God” in vv. 19-21; and 3) the charge of exchanging the glory of God to worship idols in the form of “birds, four-footed animals, and creeping things,” an animal triad found three times in the LXX version of Hosea, a book written primarily about the apostasy of the Northern Kingdom. This section should no longer be read as either a screed against Gentiles or a statement of the universal depravity of all humankind, but as a particular argument by a faction of Jews against their fellow Israelites who at one time ceased following God but now wish to return to the fold through the promise of Jesus the Messiah.

With 1:17b properly understood as the launchpad for Paul’s entire argument, we can now see that chapters 2 through 8 are a direct response to each of the terms in the quotation of Hab 2:4b:

וְצַדִּיק בְּאֱמוּנָתוֹ יִתְקַן:

ὁ δὲ δίκαιος ἐκ πίστεώς μου ζήσεται

... but the **righteous** by his **faith** shall **live**.

The RIGHTEOUS by FAITH shall LIVE (1:17b)		
Righteousness 1:17b – 3:26	Faithfulness 3:21 – 4:25	Life 4:17 – 8:39

Paul uses Hab 2:4b as an advance organizer for his refutation, structuring his rhetoric to respond in turn to each of the words in Hab 2:4b/Rom 1:17b. Unfortunately, the beauty and simplicity of this structure has been obscured by the attempts to describe and divide Romans using the components of classical rhetoric.

Finally, in chapters 9 through 11, Paul inserts the “Jew and Greek” language in 10:12 in the midst of a host of OT citations that, in their historical context, refer to the Northern Kingdom of Israel, solidifying the connection between Northern Kingdom Israelites and the term “Greek,” and thus also cementing the connection between chapters 1-8 and 9-11. We can now read these eleven chapters together as an integrated whole, start to finish, and marvel at Paul’s complex but straightforward argument for the full restoration of Israel. These adjustments to the text reveal the original cohesiveness and coherence of Paul’s message. In this reading, Paul is definitely operating “within Judaism”; however, with the realization that Paul is advocating for all Israel, not just Jews, this reading might more appropriately be called “Paul within Israelism.” I have already suggested earlier that this description, while accurate, is a bit clunky. Given Paul’s own words in Rom 11:1, I humbly suggest “Paul the Israelite” as an apt description and name for this new approach.

In this collection of adjustments to the exegesis of Romans that I am proposing, I am nowhere suggesting that Gentiles are not Paul’s primary mission, nor indeed that Gentiles are not part of his mission at all. What I am suggesting is that his specific argument in Romans targets

the very singular question concerning the disposition of non-Jewish Israelites in the new covenant of Jesus Messiah. Likewise, I am not arguing against the “cosmic” nature of justification and salvation and their availability to all peoples. What I am arguing for is that the positions that Paul takes in Romans are in service of the controlling argument that he is prosecuting against his opponents. Having stated and hopefully clarified my proposal in this way, it is worthwhile to note that a logical progression from this position is that we must reevaluate Paul’s statements in Romans as to whether they can still be applied to the more general assumptions concerning God’s economy of justification and salvation, or if those assumptions must be supported elsewhere in Scripture or adjusted.

Having reached the end of this thesis, you may still not be convinced of everything or anything that I have proposed, and that is to be expected given the significant shift in understanding that I assert. However, given the information that I have provided, I do not believe my claims can be brushed aside – they must be answered. For anyone wishing to refute my position, they must satisfactorily answer these questions more effectively than the case I have made:

- If you still claim that Paul uses the terms “Jew” and “Israel” synonymously, how do you resolve the ambiguity in the multiple definitions of Israel?
- If you still claim that Paul uses the terms “Gentile” and “Greek” synonymously, how do you resolve the ambiguities in the multiple definitions of each term?
- If you still claim that OT citations in chapters 9-11, e.g. 9:25-26, should be applied to Gentiles, how do you minimize/eliminate the expectations/reactions of Israelites to the original meaning of each citation in context?
- How do you explain the flow of the letter and relieve the apparent discontinuity

between chapters 1-8 and 9-11 as recognized in the traditional interpretation of Romans?

- How do you more convincingly explain the discussion of the Torah and Paul's application of it to "Greeks," acknowledging that recent scholars have pointed out the non-applicability of the law to Gentiles?
- Regardless of your answers to the above questions, how do you deal with non-Jewish Israelites living in the first century in discussions of the Torah, covenant, the restoration of Israel, circumcision?

These are the key questions that need to be considered if you are attempting to construct a more coherent explanation of the debate in Romans 1-11; more questions could be added, but these will suffice to make the point. The traditional view of flow of Romans 1-11 is broken and has been so for a long time. By understanding Paul's intent in using the ethnic group markers that he does, we can properly interpret Romans as a letter written to Jewish believers, with an extended argument in the body of the letter that addresses a specific argument concerning the exclusion of non-Jewish Israelites who were once estranged from God but now desire to rejoin God's people Israel through the work of Jesus. With true Gentiles present as part of the audience of Romans, Paul briefly addresses them before drawing his argument to a close, exhorting all three communities – Jews, non-Jewish Israelites, and Gentiles – to rejoice in the grace of God toward all people.

2. Implications for Further Research

These shifts in understanding, if accepted, open new avenues leading to a host of additional exegetical pathways to explore. While touched upon briefly in this paper, a thorough examination of the group marker "Greek" in the rest of the Pauline corpus is warranted, as is a

similar study of Acts, the other NT text where the combination of “Jew and Greek” occurs. For the gospels and the balance of New Testament texts, where the combination of “Jew” and “Greek” does not occur, it is still worthwhile to reexamine each of these writings, both to reevaluate how they use the term “Greek” in this new light, and to read them from the perspective of non-Jewish Israelites, those associated with the former Northern Kingdom of Israel, looking for changes in the narrative based on their presence. Outside of the NT, I have admittedly not delved into all Second Temple writings or all early Christian texts, nor have I consulted rabbinic sources like the Mishnah or the Talmud. These may yield additional insights concerning Northern Kingdom Israelites and their acceptance and/or rejection within the Jewish and Greco-Roman cultures of the first century.

Theologically, if one accepts the presence of non-Jewish Israelites in the New Testament, this fact simultaneously clarifies longstanding quandaries and reveals new questions. All discussions of Torah previously applied to Gentiles with confusing effects can be reinterpreted with non-Jewish Israelites in view, a group of people about whom debates concerning covenant and law make sense. At the same time, this new consideration sheds light on the existence of multiple positions concerning the answer to those questions. If you are an Israelite genealogically, but your family has been living among “pagans” for generations so that even you consider yourself a Gentile, what is your status with respect to Torah if you desire to return to the family of God?

When considering systematic theology and the Reformation in particular, the assertions made in this paper call for a return to the arguments of Campbell in his opus *The Deliverance of God* and his battle against the shortcomings of the system he has labeled “Justification Theory,”

the traditional model of salvation espoused by most Protestants.¹⁸⁵ In view of the new understanding of Paul's rhetoric in Romans concerning "justification by faith" as discussed in the "Synthesis" section of chapter 4, the whole structure of this theory should be inspected, judged for its stability, and likely replaced (in concert with Campbell) by a new system that takes into account these newly discovered insights.

In addition, a series of other questions are suitable to consider:

- If Paul's argument in Romans is about non-Jewish Israelites, how does this affect our understanding of Paul's view of Gentiles as members of the family of God?
- How does our understanding of Paul's argument in Galatians change with this new reading of Romans?
- How does this new information change our understanding of Paul's mission to be "the apostle to the nations"?
- Should Paul's mission more appropriately be characterized as focused on the restoration of Israel? If so, how do these insights change our view of the compatibility of Jesus's and Paul's stated and perceived goals/missions?
- What does the realization that any discussion of "Jew and Greek" refers to an intra-Israelite debate do to our theories concerning the "parting of the ways" between Jews and Christianity? More to the point, is this "parting of the ways" just a continuation of the animosities found in the divided Kingdom of Israel?
- Given this newest perspective, should the dichotomy "circumcised" and "uncircumcised"

¹⁸⁵ Campbell, *The Deliverance of God*, 85.

be reexamined as an intra-Israelite distinction?

Finally, from a historical theology and reception history perspective, we must ask when, why, and how this understanding of three different groups became conflated and collapsed into what we see today as two, “Jews” and “Gentiles.” There are likely multiple factors that contributed to this change, both from a social evolution perspective as groups assimilated into one another, and from an exegetical/reception perspective, as later scholars and theologians attempted to universally apply the truths of Scripture to all believers, making interpretive decisions to support their orthodoxy and orthopraxy that ignored and eventually forgot the tripartite distinction.

Even if you accept as valid every claim put forth in this paper and agree with me that the rhetoric of Romans was now truly solved, take heart – there is still much work to do. The impact of these assertions needs to be fleshed out in Romans, in the rest of the Pauline letters, and throughout the New Testament. Lord willing, I will be granted the opportunity and privilege to witness and take part in that adventure. *Soli Deo Gloria.*

Appendix A
Jew/Israel tables from Jason Staples

3Table 1.1 Jews and Israelites in JosTable 1.1 Jews and Israelites in Josephus¹⁸⁶

	Israel/Israelite	Per 1,000	<i>Ioudaios</i>	Per 1,000
<i>Ant.</i> 1–10	174	1.12	27	0.17
11	14	1.02	90	6.55
12–20	0	0	530	3.85
<i>War</i>	0	0	468	3.73
<i>Life</i>	0	0	24	1.52
<i>Ag. Ap.</i>	0	0	51	2.48

Figure 1 Jews, Israelites, and Hebrews in Josephus¹⁸⁷

¹⁸⁶ Staples, *Paul and the Resurrection*, 110.

¹⁸⁷ Staples, *The Idea of Israel*, 45.

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